

Guidelines (Best Practical Options) for Practical Ecosystem Approach Deliverable 2.3

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Table of contents

List of figures	4
List of tables	4
List of main abbreviations	5
1. GES4SEAS Project Summary	6
2. Deliverable 2.3 summary and objectives	8
2.1 Deliverable summary	8
3. Introduction and scope	13
4. Risk and opportunity assessment and management	22
4.1 Conceptual basis - Introduction to environmental Hazards and Risk	22
4.2 Analytical tools available – Bow-tie analysis	28
4.3 Guide for operationalisation	36
5. Assessment of Best Options for Practical Ecosystem-Based Approaches	43
5.1 What makes an ecosystem-based approach practical? (Assessment criteria)	43
5.2 Assessment methods	44
5.3 Results	54
6. Discussion and Conclusions	82
6.1 Risk and opportunity assessment and management	82
6.2 Data requirements on activities, pressures, eco-components, impacts and ecosystem goods and services	83
6.3 Methods available and scales in operationalizing the approach	86
6.4 Conclusions (way forward)	89
7. References.....	93
8. Appendices.....	97
8.1 Appendix 1. SEAS4GES Decision-Support System tool and factsheets	97

List of figures

Figure 1. The socio-ecological system aiming to unify the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework, the means of degrading the natural system and recovery management measures, and the ecological structure and functioning to ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits continuum. From: Elliott (2023).	28
Figure 2. A simplified generic Bow-tie structure overlain by the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework (see text).	29
Figure 3. Simplified Bow-tie with DAPSI(W)R(M) overlain – to determine causes and consequences and to agree on the responses throughout the sequence, as created by proprietary software (Cormier et al., 2019).	30
Figure 4. Bow-tie Analysis as a Problem-Structuring Method with the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework embedded (First used in the EU CERES project as a novel attempt to use BT analysis for climate change repercussions for fisheries and aquaculture) (Cormier et al., 2013, 2018, 2019).	31
Figure 5. The explained background to elements of the Bow-tie method – the ‘escalation factors’ may enhance or hinder the action of the prevention, mitigation, compensation, adaptation and control measures (see Cormier et al., 2019).	32
Figure 6. Bow-tie for climate change effects on OWF EU VECTORS Project (See also Burdon et al., 2018).	33
Figure 7. A complex example Bow-tie from the EU H2020 CERES project [includes a key to the mitigation and control measures] (Elliott et al., 2020b).	34
Figure 8. Generic Bow-tie (created using Bow-Tie XP).	36
Figure 9. A unified ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits model. From: Elliott (2023).	40
Figure 10. Flowchart for structuring a Bow-tie diagram for risk and opportunity assessment and management.	42
Figure 11. The SEAS4GES tool.	49
Figure 12. Example of user input to the SEAS4GES tool (filter #1).	50
Figure 13. Example of output from the SEAS4GES tool (compliance matrix).	51
Figure 14. Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) elements addressed by the tools assessed, currently (block colour) and potentially (after further development and adaptation; patterned colours). See text, Tables 7 and 8 for the names of the tools and EBM elements corresponding to the ID# in the figure.	59
Figure 15. DAPSI(W)R(M) components used by the assessed tools as input (left) or output (right), as single or multiple variables (ES = ecosystem services; SG&B = societal goods & benefits). The % represents the overall relative frequency of use of a DAPSI(W)R(M) component across all 34 tools.	62
Figure 16. Frequency of spatial scales (left) and temporal scales (right) of the assessments undertaken by the tools. Whether the individual scale is assessed on its own by a tool, or in combination with 1, 2 or more other scales is also shown. Spatial scales: Site level (e.g., < 10 km ²), Local (e.g., 10-100 km ²), National (e.g., 100-10,000 km ²), Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 km ²), European (e.g., > 100,000 km ²). Temporal scales: Short-term (e.g., seasonal), Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year), Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years), Long-term (e.g., > 10 years).	71
Figure 17. Frequency of uses for the assessed tools. Blue lines at the bottom indicate the most frequent (from top to bottom) combinations of uses for an individual tool.	72
Figure 18. Frequency of roles of the assessed tools in marine governance. Blue lines at the bottom indicate the most frequent (from top to bottom) combinations of roles for an individual tool.	73
Figure 19. Frequency of types of expertise required by the assessed tools.	74
Figure 20. Flow of information among tasks in WP2 and to other WPs in GES4SEAS. EBM: Ecosystem-Based Management.	92

List of tables

Table 1. Elements of Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) (and their applications) relevant to GES4SEAS. From: Papadopoulou et al. (2023).	14
Table 2. Types of tools used to support delivery of the elements of Ecosystem-Based Management. From: Papadopoulou et al. (2023).	17
Table 3. Typology of Hazards in Coastal and Coastal Wetland Area. Adapted and expanded from Elliott et al. (2014), in Elliott et al. (2019).	23

Table 4. The 10-tenets for successful and sustainable marine management – used to create the responses using management measures. 32

Table 5. Examples of the causes and consequences, which can be incorporated in a Bow-tie Scenario/Storyline for GES4SEAS 39

Table 6. Outline of the topics addressed by the questions (Q) in the online survey (‘response options’ is left blank where open text response was required)..... 45

Table 7. Unique tools assessed (including generic tool groups and specific tools within) and the level of familiarity of respondents (indicator of confidence). Values in the table are number of responses received by familiarity level and in total. The confidence score (as % of the maximum confidence recorded across the tools) is also provided in the last column, accounting for both the number of responses received and the familiarity level of the respondents. 55

Table 8. Identification (ID#) and name of Ecosystem-Based Management elements considered in this study. . 58

Table 9. DAPSI(W)R(M) components used as input by the individual tools. Column headings: A= activities; P = Pressures, S = effects on the state of species (spp), habitats (hab) or ecosystem services (ES); I = Impact on welfare (societal goods & benefits, SG&B); R = response and management measures. Values in the table indicate use as single (1) or multiple variables (2). No use is marked by dark grey cells. 63

Table 10. Data requirements for DAPSI(W)R(M) components to be used as input by the assessed tools. Column headings: DAPSI(W)R(M): A= activities; P = Pressures, S =effects on the state of eco-components (eco) or ecosystem services (ES); I= Impact on welfare (societal goods & benefits, SG&B); R = response and management measures. Data type: Quant = quantitative; semi-quant = semi-quantitative; qual = qualitative. The tools for which each variable was reported by respondents are indicated by their unique #. 65

List of main abbreviations

BBN – Bayesian Belief Network	GES – Good Environmental Status
CEA – Cumulative effects assessment	KG – Knowledge graph
CIA – Cumulative impact assessment	LS(s) – Learning Site(s)
DAPSI(W)R(M) [framework] – Drivers, Activities, Pressures, State change, Impacts (on Welfare), Responses (as management Measures).	MEM(s) – Marine ecosystem model(s)
DST – Decision Support Tool	MSFD – Marine Strategy Framework Directive
EBA(s) – Ecosystem-based approach(es)	MSPD – Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
EBM – Ecosystem-based management	PAB – Practitioners’ Advisory Board
ES – Ecosystem Services	PACE – Plan, Act, Check, Evaluate
EwE – Ecopath with Ecosim	PoM(s) – Programme(s) of Measures
E2E – End-to-end	SCP – Systematic conservation planning
FCM – Fuzzy cognitive mapping	SDM – Species distribution models
	SG&B – Societal goods and benefits

1. GES4SEAS Project Summary

Human activities at sea (e.g., maritime transport, extraction of living and non-living resources, etc.) and in coastal areas (e.g., agriculture, leisure and recreation, etc.) have expanded considerably, leading to an increased level of pressures and subsequent degradation of ocean health and, ultimately, human health. Single and cumulative impacts of these activities are likely to increase, driven by human demands and enhanced by climate change.

Human activities evolve following socio-economic drivers leading to pressures, which often are studied in isolation from each other even though their impacts on marine ecosystems can interact, making the effects cumulative (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic or a combination). Knowledge on these interactions and their cumulative effects in the marine environment has increased in recent years, but huge challenges still remain to be solved. Thus, there is little predictability to inform decision-making processes, especially on ecological tipping points, which, if exceeded, could lead to a point of no-return for the system. In this context, an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach to the management of human activities at sea and on land should ensure that the combined pressure of such activities is kept within levels compatible with achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) (requirements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive – MSFD), against a background of climate change. This means that the capacity of marine and coastal ecosystems to respond to human-induced changes is not compromised, enabling the sustainable use of marine goods and services by present and future generations.

Thus, the main objective of GES4SEAS is to inform and guide marine governance in minimizing human pressures and their impacts on marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, while maintaining the sustainable delivery of ecosystem services. This will be achieved through developing an innovative and flexible toolbox, tested, validated, demonstrated and upscaled, in the context of adaptive EBM approach. The toolbox will allow competent authorities to assess and predict the effect of multiple stressors (including climate change) and pressures from human activities, at the national, sub-regional, regional and European level. Ultimately, this will ensure they achieve GES, and support different policies at national, European and global levels (e.g., Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), Biodiversity Strategy 2030, United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)).

Stakeholders and the key competent authorities (including national, regional and European levels) are integrated in a Practitioners' Advisory Board (PAB) to co-create and validate the toolbox and the EBM

approach. This will result on a real problem-solving approach with iterative and incremental development steps.

GES4SEAS will also rely on existing multi-actor networks to involve and engage with stakeholders. This multi-actor approach will ensure that the research and deliverables are relevant to marine managers all around the world. Lastly, it is important to highlight that the toolbox will be tested and demonstrated at 11 Learning Sites covering all European regional seas (and also overseas), and environments. Thus, it is expected that GES4SEAS will achieve Technological and Societal Readiness Levels 6. This will be achieved by the participation of 20 partners, covering the four European regional seas and Canada.

It is expected that GES4SEAS will:

- Operationalize integrative and holistic solutions for EBM, based upon a software toolbox for analysing, assessing and mapping cumulative pressures, GES and ecosystem services.
- Provide evidence (and training) to key stakeholders of the benefits of using the toolbox that will be developed in GES4SEAS for assessing the environmental status of marine waters and the ecosystem services considering the effects of multiple pressures so opt for using it.
- Ensure the EBM approach and guidelines for the management of Invasive Alien Species (IAS), harmful algal blooms (HABs) and jellyfish, the approach for monitoring top predators are used by end-users.
- Investigate, using models, the best ways to obtain thresholds of GES/non-GES status and tipping points (system breaking points).
- Reach and engage a wider society, and specifically young people and educators, on key messages steaming from this project, so GES4SEAS contributes to societal ocean literacy and responsible behaviours.

2. Deliverable 2.3 summary and objectives

This deliverable, “D2.3: Guidelines (Best Practical Options) for Practical Ecosystem Approach”, reports on the following tasks:

Task 2.3. Propose Best Options for practical Ecosystem-based Approaches to fill gaps in understanding the effects of multiple and cumulative pressures.

Subtask 2.3.1. Define and operationalize the concepts of risk and opportunity assessment and management (for example using Bow-tie analysis) and provide instructions for the Learning Sites (in WP5).

Subtask 2.3.2. Determine the data requirements and provide instructions for the Learning Sites concerning activities, pressures, ecosystem components, impacts and ecosystem goods and services (in WP5).

Subtask 2.3.3. Indicate the assessment methods available and scales in operationalizing the approach (in WP3-4) and provide instructions for the Learning Sites (in WP5).

Several key terms used in this deliverable have been defined in the terminology report (Smith et al., 2022¹). The tool groups and elements of EBM reported here have also been previously identified and defined in Deliverable 2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

This Deliverable 2.3 specifically addresses the following objectives:

O2.2 Determine the available knowledge, gaps and the process for making the framework operational in WP3-5.

O2.3 Develop a scientific state-of-the-art knowledge base that is fit-for-purpose to guide EBM towards achieving all the relevant policy goals, including invasive species, HABs, jellyfish and top predators.

2.1 Deliverable summary

The GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.3 “**Guidelines (Best Practical Options) for Practical Ecosystem Approach**” further develops the conceptual framework and knowledge base for EBM (from Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 in

¹ https://www.ges4seas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/GES4SEAS__Report-Definitions-and-Lists-17112022final.pdf

WP2) by identifying the best options for the practical implementation of EBM. In particular, this deliverable reports on 3 separate subtasks.

Define and operationalize the concepts of risk and opportunity assessment and management and provide instructions for the Learning Sites.

Determining and addressing the effects of human activities on the marine system is the basis of EBM. It is, in essence, a risk assessment and risk management procedure, which may also be applied to determine the opportunities for active management of the seas, including restoration. The Deliverable presents the conceptual basis for environmental hazards and risk in the context of the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework, a cause-consequence-response framework which aims to protect the natural ecological structure and functioning while ensuring that the seas support ecosystem services from which society obtains goods and services after inputting complementary assets and human capital. Guidance for operationalising the concepts of risk and opportunity assessment and management is provided, through the use of Bow-tie analysis. As part of ISO 31000 risk management guidelines, IEC 31010 defines Bow-tie analysis as a qualitative assessment of the management controls to reduce or prevent the likelihood of an event (the results of pressures) and the reduce the magnitude of the consequences (the natural and societal impacts) of such event. While it was originally developed for industry risk assessment and management, this approach has been since implemented in a marine environmental context, e.g., in EU projects to address risks determined by climate change on the renewable energy sector (VECTORS) or on the aquaculture and fishery sectors (CERES).

In GES4SEAS, Bow-tie analysis will enable the Learning Sites (LSs) to identify the cause-consequence-response pathways (storyline) linking: (i) the main issues/concerns regarding risks to achieving GES and require management of the human activities and their relevant pressures in the LS; (ii) the causes and consequences of such risks, and (iii) how the causes (human activities) can be best managed to reduce the pressures to a level that will allow GES to be achieved and maintained. The deliverable gives instructions for the LSs on how to build the storyline through Bow-tie diagrams using information obtained from stakeholder consultation (WP1) or from project partners within the LS (WP5).

Determine the data requirements and provide instructions for the Learning Sites concerning activities, pressures, ecosystem components, impacts and ecosystem goods and services.

The Deliverable presents the analysis of the ecosystem-based approaches (EBAs) available to undertake assessment in support of EBM. Starting from the EBAs identified and reviewed in tasks 2.1 and 2.2, information on the characteristics of the available EBA tools was obtained through stakeholder consultation via an online survey completed by 45 between internal (GES4SEAS) and external experts. The survey gathered information about: (i) the purpose and context of the use of a tool (e.g., the EBM elements it addresses, who uses it, its relevance for marine governance); (ii) the type of assessment the tool provides (e.g., which DAPSI(W)R(M) components are involved, what are the scales of the assessment); (iii) the requirements of the tool in terms of data (type and variables), expertise and other resources, and (iv) any strengths and weaknesses, including barriers for practical implementation of the tool. This information is summarised in factsheets for the different tools in Appendix 1.

The analysis of the information regarding data requirements has highlighted that different tools may incorporate different combinations of DAPSI(W)R(M) components (activities, pressures, state change on ecosystem components and services, impacts on human welfare and on societal goods and benefits). The specific data requirements will depend on the tool being applied in a LS, but the analysis across the tools has highlighted that, whatever tool is used, it will most likely require data on activities and/or pressures in the case study area and on the state of the ecosystem components ('eco-components'). Guidance for the LSs on the specific variables that may be required by the different tools to measure activities, pressures, ecosystem components and services, and societal impacts on goods and services is provided in the Deliverable. These data may be qualitative (e.g., occurrence), semi-quantitative (e.g., measured on a Likert scale) or quantitative (e.g., counts/abundance of an eco-component, intensity of a pressure), and some tools may also accommodate expert judgment. Spatial distribution and/or temporal series for the data may be required in some cases. The flexibility of a tool with regard to its data requirements (i.e., the ability to accommodate qualitative or semi-quantitative data where quantitative data are not available) widens the applicability of the approach to cases where data availability may be poor. However, LSs are cautioned that using lesser quality data may also lead to less informative outputs (i.e., less detailed in the type of information they provide) and which may be less trustworthy (i.e., characterised by a higher uncertainty or lower confidence).

Indicate the assessment methods available and scales in operationalizing the approach (in WP3-4) and provide instructions for the Learning Sites.

The Deliverable reports on 34 tools available to undertake assessment in support of EBM. These include 20 generic types of EBAs, and 14 examples of specific tools within these generic EBAs, identified based on the knowledge and expertise of the respondents to the online survey (as relevant to GES4SEAS). Each tool has a specific combination of characteristics (what it can do, how it is used, what data it needs, what skills, what limitations, etc.), which may make a tool more or less suitable for practical use depending on the EBM context in which it is applied (i.e., one-size-fits-all does not apply). Indeed, each LS likely has different priorities regarding the specific issue to address in the context of EBM, the type of output they require to support it and the availability of data and expertise they can use for this purpose.

In order to provide the LSs with instructions about the EBA(s) that best apply to their case study, a Decision Support Tool (DST), SEAS4GES (Selection of Ecosystem-based Approaches for Good Environmental Status), has been developed in Excel (its possible integration into the GES4SEAS toolbox being developed in WP4 is being currently discussed) and is provided along with this deliverable. SEAS4GES, used in combination with the tool factsheets, allows to match the requirements and capability for EBM of a LS (and indeed of any user) with the tool characteristics and thus identify the best practical option(s) available to the LS. For example, where cumulative effects/impacts are to be assessed, the specialised tools developed for this purpose (namely cumulative impact spatial mapping in general, and the improved 'Halpern' version being developed by GES4SEAS along with CIMPAL and PlanWise4Blue as specific examples) are most suited, although they need to be used in combination with other tools (e.g., GIS, species distribution models) to provide spatial information and incorporate a risk-based approach. These spatial tools are sufficiently flexible to accommodate evidence of variable quality on any activity, pressure or receptor. They may operate at a range of spatial scales, from site level (< 10 km²) up to broader European scale (> 100,000 km²), but do not require temporal data (although research is being undertaken towards the production of temporal outputs). Impact risk-linkage-chain-frameworks (e.g., ODEMM) and risk-based approaches (e.g., Bow-tie) are the next best option to assess cumulative effects/impacts, although these are tools for gross risk identification, and they operate in a semi-quantitative way at best; in addition, they do not (or need further work to) produce spatially or temporally resolved outputs (recent developments in the impact risk-linkage-chain-framework approach address these limitations).

The Deliverable also provides **recommendations** on the next steps for the LSs to move towards the practical implementation of EBM (WP5). These include: (i) to clearly identify the specific EBM issues relevant to the case study based on partners and stakeholder consultation; (ii) to apply Bow-tie analysis to frame their specific issue and map the relevant cause-consequences linkages; (iii) to use the SEAS4GES DST (in combination with insights from D2.1, D2.2 and the narratives and factsheets from D2.1 and this Deliverable, respectively) to identify the best practical option(s) (tools) to address the specific EBM issues in the LS; (iv) to test the tools that are applicable (e.g., based on current data availability) and identify evidence gaps (WP5), which will help to inform data collation needs for future assessments. A timescale for implementing these steps in GES4SEAS is suggested, with links with other relevant project activities (e.g., capacity building in WP3) also identified.

3. Introduction and scope

The work undertaken in Task 2.3 and reported in this Deliverable 2.3 aims to provide guidelines for practical ecosystem-based approaches to fill gaps in understanding the effects of multiple and cumulative pressures. It is emphasised here in particular, and in GES4SEAS in general, that determining and addressing the effects of human activities on the marine system is, in essence, a risk assessment and risk management procedure (Cormier et al., 2019; Elliott et al., 2020a). This requires a cause-consequence-response framework which aims to protect the natural ecological structure and functioning while ensuring that the seas support ecosystem services from which society obtains goods and services after inputting complementary assets and human capital (Elliott, 2023). This is the basis of EBM, which in turn requires one or more tools to be implemented.

Despite this, while such an approach is designed as a means of tackling the adverse consequences of human activities in the sea, recent work has also emphasised that a similar approach can be used to determine the opportunities for active management of the seas, including restoration (e.g., Elliott et al., 2020b, from the CERES project). Hence, it is important to employ opportunity assessment and management techniques that are likely complementary to risk assessment and management and a pro-active approach to marine management.

The conceptual/knowledge base for this work has been set up in Task 2.1, where the ecosystem-based approaches addressing multiple and cumulative pressures have been documented, and more specifically in subtask 2.1.2., identifying existing EBA approaches (including input/output measures such as pressure and impact mitigation, reduction and restoration). This baseline work is reported in Deliverable 'D2.1. Ecosystem management approaches based on a review of the activity-pressures-effects chain towards achieving Good Environmental Status in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive' (Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

D2.1 reviewed the origin of the concept of EBM and its use in major EU policies and by Regional Sea Conventions and international institutions (see also Smith et al. (2022) providing definitions of all relevant terminology for the GES4SEAS project²). It deconstructed the term into essential EBM principles and into 18 elements of EBM (and their applications) representing specific aspects or issues that may need to be addressed/assessed in an EBM process (Table 1). D2.1 also identified 19 categories of tools (tool groups) that, alone or in combination, may be used to deliver these EBM elements (Table 2). The D2.1. analysis has shown that there must be a given complement of tools, i.e.,

² https://www.ges4seas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/GES4SEAS__Report-Definitions-and-Lists-17112022final.pdf

a toolbox, to satisfy the many principles of EBM and that no single tool is likely to fully satisfy all aspects of EBM.

The EBM elements and tool groups identified in Task 2.1 constitute the building blocks of Task 2.3, where further analysis of the tool characteristics is undertaken to provide guidance on the best practical approaches. The tools considered are mostly assessment tools, i.e., they are used to inform on the potential state (structure, functioning and dynamics) of the marine ecosystems, considering the array of interactions between their components (natural and human), the issues affecting them, e.g., anthropogenic pressures, cumulative effects exerted on ecosystem components, effects on ecosystem services and societal benefits, effects of management measures. Through these assessments, the ecosystem-based approaches support decision-making towards the integrated management of the ecosystem.

Task 2.3 also builds on the work undertaken in Task 2.2 'State-of-the-art in support of EBM approaches to address HABs, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators' (Deliverable D2.2, Katsanevakis et al., 2023). D2.2 provided the scientific background on drivers-pressure-state-impacts links of these components, their linkages to ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits, including human health and welfare, the existing gaps of knowledge, and the existing experiences on monitoring, predicting and managing these events and their consequences. Some of the tools identified in Task 2.1 and analysed in Task 2.3 have also been used to address the specific issues considered in Task 2.2 and for which EBM is endorsed.

Table 1. Elements of Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) (and their applications) relevant to GES4SEAS. From: Papadopoulou et al. (2023).

EBM element	Brief description
Cumulative effects assessments -CEA	Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA) (used here interchangeably with Combined Effects Assessment, Cumulative Impact Assessment (CIA); In combination Effects Assessment; Cumulative Pressure and Impacts Assessment) is the assessment of ecosystem changes that accumulate from multiple stressors, both natural and manmade. CEAs are holistic evaluations of the combined effects of human activities and natural processes on the environment, constituting a specific form of environmental impact assessment.
Good Environmental Status -Marine Strategy Framework Directive (GES MSFD) assessments	The assessment (as both a process and a product) undertaken for the purposes of the MSFD. As a process, it is a procedure by which information is collected and evaluated following agreed methods, rules and guidance. It is carried out periodically (in a 6-year cycle) to determine the level of available knowledge and to evaluate the environmental status. As a product, it is a report that synthesises and documents this information, presenting the findings of the assessment process, typically according to a defined methodology, and leading to a classification of environmental status in relation to the determination of Good Environmental Status (MSFD GES).

EBM element	Brief description
Whole ecosystem assessments	Whole ecosystem assessments like MSFD do exist but without the same strict structure and requirements of the MSFD. These include regional assessments, e.g., in the Baltic Sea (HELCOM), in the Atlantic Ocean (OSPAR Commission), in the Mediterranean (UNEP-MAP), or in the Black Sea (Black Sea Commission).
Ecosystem Services (delivery, impacts, valuation)	This includes assessments of ecosystem services (ES) in terms of delivery, impacts, and value. Ecosystem services are the final outputs or products from ecosystems that are directly consumed, used (actively or passively) or enjoyed by people.
Special biotic effects/impacts	These include multiple examples. A major one is sex segregation (i.e., when the sexes of a species live apart, either singly or in single-sex groups). Documenting the underlying causes of sexual segregation is important for management and conservation reasons, as differential exploitation of the sexes by humans (e.g., by spatially focused fishing in key areas or hunting) can lead to population decline. Other examples (not an exhaustive list) include looking at the impacts of climate change and other pressures (e.g., pollution, fishery) on sex ratios or sex-changing in certain species. Understanding the factors influencing species distributions is also crucial for implementing effective EBM and conservation practices.
Specific ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions)	This includes a very wide range of ecosystem functions with varied research and management interests. The MSFD, in line with its requirement for ‘good environmental status’ and ‘clean, healthy and productive oceans and seas within their intrinsic conditions’, additionally requires that ‘the structure, functions and processes of the constituent marine ecosystems allow those ecosystems to function fully and to maintain their resilience to human-induced environmental change’.
Activities-pressures-footprint	Determining the overall effects of human activities on the estuaries, seas and coasts, as a precursor to marine management, requires quantifying three aspects: (i) the area in which the human activities take place, (ii) the area covered by the pressures generated by the activities on the prevailing habitats and species, and (iii) the area over which any adverse effects occur. These three features correspond to the activities-footprints, the pressures-footprints and the effects-footprints (the latter being explicitly addressed in the EBM element below).
Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints)	As with the category Activity-pressure footprint, this category brings in a spatial element in the assessments of impacts and effects, which is an essential part of EBM and EU conservation policies (e.g., HD and MSFD). As effects and impacts are more difficult to identify and assess, activity and pressure footprints are often used as proxies.
Links activities pressures impacts	Linking activities, pressures, and impacts is an essential part of the MSFD and a crucial element of EBM. DAPSI(W)R(M) (Drivers, Activities, Pressures, State change, Impacts on human Welfare, Responses by Measures) or DAPSES-MMM (socio-economic Drivers, human Activities, Pressures, State of environment, Ecosystem Services – Management (policies and governance), Measures, Monitoring) are examples of the conceptual frameworks mapping these links.
Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues	This includes primarily assessments on major regional issues such as Invasive alien species (IAS), Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), jellyfish blooms and eutrophication.
Single species, ecosystem components state change	This includes assessments of single species status (e.g., under CFP for commercial species, under MSFD for descriptor D1 Biological Diversity or D3 Commercial fish and shellfish species) or assessments of habitats (e.g., for reporting for HD or within an MPA or within a region) and looking at changes of status due to pressures.
Threatened habitats and species	This includes documenting the status and distributions of species and habitats at risk at global, regional or local scales.

EBM element	Brief description
Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation	This includes targeted and specific pressure and impact reduction or mitigation measures. There are many examples, and a few are given here. For example, various management options have been proposed to mitigate the impacts of IAS in the marine environment, including, amongst others, physical removal, promotion of commercial exploitation, and environmental rehabilitation. Other pressure and impact reduction methods include rebuilding fish stocks to Maximum Sustainable Yield levels (in line with CFP and EU SDG goals) and above to reduce negative impacts on marine ecosystems, increasing the selectivity of the fishing gears, and implementing the landing obligation to reduce bycatch and unwanted catches contributing to the decline of marine resources and of protected species.
Spatial and other measures	This includes spatial and other measures related to the management response and management footprint. Well-known spatial measures include, for example, the ban on trawling in the deep habitats in the Mediterranean and the North-east Atlantic or in particular areas (e.g., over-protected habitats).
Climate change	This element is relevant to EBM in planning mitigation and adaptation actions and evaluation phases from both managers’ and scientists’ points of view. Modelling tools can address changes in species distributions due to climatic effects, and these insights are relevant to the planning phase of conservation spatial planning and restoration prioritisation. For the evaluation and assessment phase, it would be useful to know whether the outcome of the evaluation is affected by (an unmanageable exogenic pressure like) climate change as well as the trajectory of change.
Uncertainty	Uncertainty applies to all the EBM process phases in that the managers prefer to get advice that includes uncertainty/confidence both in terms of consequences of planning scenarios or management plans and in assessment outcomes. Not all tools are able to account for uncertainty/confidence.
Risks	A risk in the environment occurs when natural or anthropogenic hazards affect human health, welfare or something valued by society. This includes risks from human actions or inaction, risks to ecosystem components due to spatial overlap with activities and pressures, and risks related to specific biotic effects (e.g., sex-related fishing impacts or fishing impacts on nesting or nursery areas). Different tools may address different aspects of risk.
Other Policy Requirements, e.g., MSPD, BHD, Biodiversity Strategy	This EBM element addressed the ability to satisfy different policy needs (other than MSFD), e.g., by providing outputs relevant to the MSPD or the Biodiversity Strategy and the proposed EU Nature Restoration Law, or providing assessments that may support the BHD or the needs of RSC (e.g., OSPAR, HELCOM, Black Sea Commission).

Table 2. Types of tools used to support delivery of the elements of Ecosystem-Based Management. From: Papadopoulou et al. (2023).

#	Tool group	Brief description
1	Conceptual models	Conceptual models (including mental models, decision trees, decision matrices, mind maps, argument mapping, flow charts, organograms, etc.) are a graphical representation of a system (e.g., natural ecosystem, socio-economic system, socio-ecological system). They visually represent the complex relationships within a system through a network of nodes (the main components of a system) and vectors/links (the pathways linking those components, often in a cause-consequence relationship). They usually play an important role in communication and common understanding between developers and users (Rodila et al., 2015). They may also form the basis of a quantitative assessment and, thus, future mathematical descriptions and predictive models, or draw the methodological procedures to be followed on the basis of homogenised criteria.
2	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping	Semi-quantitative mental models are an advance on conceptual models (see above for conceptual models) in that the linkages between nodes (the system’s main components) are not just documented, but the direction and strength of the interaction are specified, allowing for simple scenario investigation. Perhaps the most used Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM) tool is the Mental Modeler.
3	Knowledge Graphs	A knowledge graph is a structured representation of knowledge that encapsulates information on entities, their attributes, and their relationships. It consists of ‘nodes’ (representing entities) and ‘edges’ (representing the relationships between them), and can be visualised as a network or a graph. It is a type of information source used by search engines and other applications to provide users with more relevant and accurate information. A knowledge graph might be usefully viewed as a combination of a graphical network diagram allied to a database providing information on each node and link.
4	BBN probabilistic models	Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs) are models that graphically and probabilistically represent correlative and causal relationships among variables and that account for uncertainty. BBNs are an advance on conceptual models (see above for conceptual models) in that the linkages and the strengths of the links (the dependencies and interdependences) between nodes (the model’s variables) are quantified through conditional probability tables or distributions.

#	Tool group	Brief description
5	Risk-based approaches exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (e.g., Bow-tie)	Bow-tie is an industry-standard ISO-31000 compliant method for producing conceptual models. It addresses a risk or problem (as the central knot of the Bow-tie) and indicates the causes of that problem (to the left of the knot of a Bow-tie) and the consequences that occur because of the problem (to the right of the knot). Various controls can be placed on the left of the hazard to prevent the hazard from occurring, or on the right to reduce/mitigate/compensate for the magnitude of any consequences. As such, the tool is defined as a qualitative assessment of the management controls to reduce the likelihood (prevent) of an event (pressure) and to reduce the magnitude of the consequences (impacts) of such event (it is not an impact assessment).
6	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (Halpern et al., 2008)	The global human impact assessment (Halpern et al., 2008) is a spatial assessment where layers of pressures and ecosystem components (e.g., species, species groups, habitats), spatialised across a grid of selected resolution, are combined. Their spatial overlap and weight scores representing the sensitivity of the ecosystem components to each of the pressures are used to derive an index expressing cumulative impacts/effects.
7	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (e.g., ODEMM)	An assessment methodology developed, e.g., in ODEMM and AQUACROSS projects, which traces sector–pressure–ecosystem component pressure pathways (also known as ‘linkage chains’) and scores them through expert judgement and data where available.
8	Single spp. model (life cycle, stock assessment)	Single-species models are mathematical representations used to study and understand the dynamics of a particular species within an ecosystem. The models focus on the population size, growth, and interactions of a single species, while often considering its interactions with its environment and other factors that influence its population dynamics. These models can incorporate limited ecosystem or multispecies information. Examples of single-species models are dynamic energy budget (DEB) models, metapopulation models, dynamic population models and individual-based models (IBM).
9	Biogeochemical models	Biogeochemical models capture two-way interactions between the biology and chemistry of ecosystems. They are used to simulate how abiotic and biotic variables interact through time and across space and provide a means to explore management scenarios in relation to climate change and changes in the flow of nutrients from land into the ocean.
10	Food web models (e.g., multispecies models, EwE)	Food-web models are a particular type of ecosystem models, which simulate the structure and flow of energy and nutrients between ecosystem components and are commonly used for quantifying food-web interactions in a whole-ecosystem context. Food web models aim to understand the trophic patterns, population dynamics among predators and prey, and implications for system stability, as well as matter/energy flows among the nodes as an ecosystem or ecological network statically, in time or in time and space. Examples of such type of models are Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) and Ecological Network Analysis (ENA). EwE are a specific example of marine ecosystem models (MEMs).

#	Tool group	Brief description
11	Marine Ecosystem Models (MEMs, e.g., E2E)	Ecosystem models describe the interactions between at least two ecosystem components (e.g., populations, species, functional groups), whereby the interactions are real ecological processes (e.g., predator–prey interactions, large and small perturbations, dispersal). Ecosystem models are often visualised as networks, and end-to-end (E2E) models are one type of ecosystem model. They are a mathematical representation of an entire ecosystem, which integrates physico-chemical oceanographic descriptors and organisms ranging from microbes to higher-trophic-level organisms (including humans) and links to the marine socio-economic aspects. This approach was developed from the need for quantitative tools for Ecosystem-Based Management, particularly models that can deal with bottom-up and top-down controls that operate simultaneously and vary in time and space and that are capable of handling multiple impacts.
12	Habitat suitability / Species distribution models	Species distribution models (SDM, also referred to in the literature as habitat suitability models, predictive habitat distribution models or ecological niche models) are used to predict the spatial distribution of a species (e.g., the likelihood of its presence or density) based on its observed relationship with environmental conditions. This modelling approach can be seen as an operational application of the ecological niche. Different modelling techniques can be used, including both correlative models (also known as climate envelope or bioclimatic models, e.g., based on generalized linear or additive regression models, classification and regression trees, Random Forest, maximum entropy algorithm) and mechanistic approaches to SDM.
13	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation	The natural capital approach to policy and decision-making considers the value of the natural environment for people and the economy, providing a tool to support the protection and management of the natural environment and to facilitate the engagement of stakeholders within management decisions. Natural capital accounts are developed to assess and monitor the contribution of natural resources to economic activity.
14	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation	This group includes tools such as: (i) Bio-economic models, i.e. integrated economic-ecological models used for resource management and sustainable resource use; (ii) Valuation of Societal Benefits, which determines the ‘total social value’ (comprising of ecological value, economic value, and socio-cultural value) of marine ecosystem services leading to benefits for society; (iii) Cost-benefit analysis (CBA), a core tool of public policy consisting in the systematic process of calculating the benefits and costs, expressed in monetary units, of policy options and projects (environmental CBA is the application of CBA to projects or policies that have the deliberate aim of environmental improvement or actions that somehow affect the natural environment as an indirect consequence).

#	Tool group	Brief description
15	Spatial planning models and tools (e.g., GIS, VAPEM, related to use)	Spatial planning models, adapted to the marine ecosystem, are tools used to help planners and policymakers make informed decisions about the use of marine space and resources. The models are designed to provide insights into the potential impacts of different planning scenarios, and to help identify the most effective strategies for achieving specific planning goals. Examples of tools within this tool group are Geographic Information Systems (GIS, computer-based tools used to store, analyse, and visualize spatial or geographic data) and VAPEM tool (Ecological Assessment and Marine Spatial Planning Tool, a decision support tool which integrates the environmental risk information, together with the technical and socio-ecological information linked to wave energy projects, into a Bayesian model).
16	Systematic conservation planning tools (e.g., MARXAN)	Conservation planning is the process of locating, configuring, implementing and maintaining areas that are managed to promote the persistence of biodiversity and other natural values. Systematic conservation planning (SCP) uses an explicit and transparent methodology to locate and design new reserves complementing the existing network of protected areas by applying explicit criteria for implementing conservation actions and adopting explicit objectives and mechanisms for maintaining the needed conditions in protected areas required to foster the persistence of the protected ecological features (used as surrogates for overall biodiversity), as well as adequate monitoring schemes and adaptive management. This is based on clear goals (translated into operational targets) and recognizes the level of achievement of conservation goals in the existing protected areas. Decision support tools have been developed to facilitate systematic conservation planning, the most widely used being MARXAN (a suite of spatial prioritization decision support tools to design networks of protected areas that capture a set amount of biodiversity for the least cost) and ZONATION (operating on spatial data about ecological features, costs, and threats, also utilizing information about uncertainty and connectivity).
17	Simple assessment index (e.g., M-AMBI)	Simple assessment indices are methods for classifying marine systems according to human pressures and include those focusing on the primary community structural variables (abundance, species richness, and biomass) and derived community structural variables (such as diversity indices, abundance and biomass ratios, and evenness indices). These indices can also include functional analyses such as those involving feeding guilds and their responses to organic matter inputs or other human pressures (such as the so-called 'biotic indices'). There are dozens, if not hundreds, of biotic indices covering different biological elements, which include phytoplankton, zooplankton, macroalgae, seagrasses, macroinvertebrates and fishes. M-AMBI (Multivariate AZTI's Marine Biotic Index) is an example of a multivariate index for macroinvertebrates.

#	Tool group	Brief description
18	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (e.g., HEAT, BEAT and CHASE)	The indicator-based multi-metric assessment tools integrate quantitative indicators to inform of the integrated state of the assessment area. Tools have been developed for hazardous substances (CHASE), eutrophication (HEAT) and biodiversity (BEAT). The indicators use a threshold value indicating an acceptable state from an unacceptable state, and the indicators can be grouped within the tool to best reflect the assessment topic.
19	Overarching assessment tools (e.g., NEAT and OHI)	NEAT stands for “Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool”. It is a tool primarily for biodiversity assessment but can, in principle, be used for other types of status assessment, too. The tool is useful for environmental assessments as it has been designed for exactly that purpose. Usually, it is applied to status assessment, describing the status of an ecosystem using state indicators for various ecosystem components divided into separate values for specific habitats inside a spatial assessment unit.

4. Risk and opportunity assessment and management

This section reports specifically on Subtask 2.3.1 and aims at defining and operationalizing the concepts of risk and opportunity assessment and management (for example, using the ISO Accredited industry-compliant tool called Bow-tie analysis) towards providing instructions for the Learning Sites (LSs; in WP5).

4.1 Conceptual basis - Introduction to environmental Hazards and Risk

The coastal and marine environment is subject to many hazards, each with causes and consequences of which marine environmental managers should be aware. In essence, hazards may occur either naturally or by human actions, and they become risks when they adversely affect something valued by humans, such as health, welfare or property (i.e., the objectives of environmental protection as in ISO 31000); consequently, the risk is the probability that a hazard will lead to those adverse consequences on humans and so will include the severity of those consequences. In some cases, human responses to one hazard may increase the risk and make the consequences even more severe – for example, removing coastal protection due to mangroves may make the repercussions of cyclones and tsunamis even more severe. Hazard is the cause of an adverse effect compared to risk, which in contrast is the probability of effect (i.e., the likely consequences) potentially leading to more severe consequences to humans. The severity of the risk can be measured by the number of people or the value of the assets likely to be affected. At its most severe, the concept of disaster then represents the interplay between the social and the natural systems.

Responses by society to hazards result from a perception of risk, and the willingness to act depends on the perception and evidence for the consequences. The response in terms of management measures or rather technical measures is to reduce "risk" to a level that is tolerable by society even though perceptions vary individually. For example, the placement of storm surge barriers occurred as a response to the 1953 storm surge in the North Sea and in anticipation of similar events in the future. While Smith and Petley (2009) consider that natural risk can be defined as the damage expected from an actual or hypothetical scenario triggered by phenomena or events following natural events, the previous definitions suggest that that damage should relate to humans to be regarded as risk.

Coastal and marine hazards may be natural or anthropogenic (Table 3) and are divided into those over which individuals or communities have some control, for example, by not inhabiting vulnerable areas, and those where they have no control, for example, tectonic failure or extreme landslip (see Elliott et

al., 2014, 2019). Such hazards then require to be tackled using technological, governance and economic approaches, for example, whether we have the capacity in methods, laws and funding to modify and protect coastal landscapes against the influence of hazards or whether we need the capacity to mitigate their effects by financially supporting adaptive measures. A management measure to reduce or nullify that risk could involve merely removing people from the area in which they would be subject to the hazard.

Table 3. Typology of Hazards in Coastal and Coastal Wetland Area. Adapted and expanded from Elliott et al. (2014), in Elliott et al. (2019).

Hazard	Natural or Anthropogenic?	Examples
A) Surface hydrological hazards	Natural but exacerbated by human activities	High tide flooding, spring tide and equinoctial flooding; flash flooding, El Niño Southern Oscillation/North Atlantic Oscillation patterns; flow delivery repercussions of catchment modifications (land use increasing sediment loading, dams decreasing peak flows and sediment loadings, etc.)
B) Surface physiographic removal by natural processes - chronic/long-term	Natural but exacerbated by human activities	Gradual erosion of soft cliffs by slumping, estuary bank erosion by prevailing currents
C) Surface physiographic removal by human actions - chronic/long-term	Anthropogenic	Land claim, removal of wetlands for urban and agricultural area
D) Surface physiographic removal - acute/short-term	Natural	Cliff failure, undercutting of hard cliffs and intermittent erosion
E) Climatological hazards - acute/short-term	Natural but exacerbated by human activities	Storm surges, cyclones, tropical storms, hurricanes, offshore surges, fluvial and pluvial flooding
F) Climatological hazards - chronic/long-term	Natural but exacerbated by human activities or anthropogenic	Ocean acidification, sea level rise, storminess, ingress of seawater/saline intrusion
G) Tectonic hazards - acute/short-term	Natural	Tsunamis, seismic slippages, earthquakes
H) Tectonic hazards - chronic/ long-term	Natural	Isostatic rebound, subsidence
I) Anthropogenic microbial biohazards	Anthropogenic	Sewage pathogens
J) Anthropogenic microbial biohazards	Anthropogenic	Alien, introduced and invasive species, Genetically Modified Organisms, bloom-forming species
K) Anthropogenic introduced technological hazards	Anthropogenic	Failures or mismanagement of infrastructure, coastal defences, catchment impedance structures (dams, weirs)
L) Anthropogenic extractive technological hazards	Anthropogenic	Removal of space, removal of biological populations (fish, shellfish, etc.); seabed extraction and oil/gas/coal extraction leading to subsidence
M) Anthropogenic acute chemical hazards	Anthropogenic	Pollution from one-off spillages, oil spills

Hazard	Natural or Anthropogenic?	Examples
N) Anthropogenic chronic chemical hazards	Anthropogenic	Diffuse pollution, ocean acidification, litter/garbage, nutrients from land run-off, constant land-based discharges, aerial inputs
O) Anthropogenic acute geopolitical hazards	Anthropogenic	Terrorism attacks leading to damage to infrastructure
P) Anthropogenic chronic geopolitical hazards	Anthropogenic	Wars created by shortage of resources (e.g., land, water, minerals)

At the same time, coastal management and global agreements must ensure that biodiversity is protected and that management actions implemented at national levels and potentially affecting the natural structure and functioning are sustainable in the long term. Developed countries have the financial and technological means to reduce the vulnerability and thus risk to the effects of change, such as climate change (e.g., Blasiak et al., 2017; Ding et al., 2017), such as building defences, but this is an expensive option. Underlying this is the need and requirement to protect societal benefits such as infrastructure and urban areas, while at the same time protecting the natural system and its delivery of ecosystem services. Hence, while we have the capacity to engineer the coastline to protect it from hazards, this would be at the risk of creating a non-natural system, thus contravening nature conservation agreements and laws. Coastal industries will be similarly faced with such decisions in protecting their assets while at the same time ensuring that their activities do not adversely affect natural systems.

In wider terms, natural phenomena that can create risks can be divided into two main categories depending on the source of the causes: endogenous phenomena and exogenous phenomena in relation to their source, respectively, within or on the Earth’s surface. Endogenous causes, for example, include those which can release huge amounts of energy from seismic or tectonic events, and thus are seen as earthquakes and volcanic eruptions and tsunamis, wrongly termed tidal-waves, which emanate from these. Exogenous phenomena, such as landslides, floods and accelerated erosion (of beaches and riverbeds), are often, but not necessarily always, linked to extreme meteorological events and act on the Earth’s surface, tending to modify the landscape. The nature of the landscape has to be such that it cannot accommodate such forces without resulting modification; for example, flat landscapes will exhibit greater change by flooding than ones with greater elevation. Such phenomena are an expression of the internal and external geophysical dynamics and represent the natural evolutionary processes. However, by interacting with societal components (population, settlements, infrastructure, etc.) they frequently define risk conditions. While natural systems have the capacity to adjust to such natural changes, it is only when the natural and societal aspects interact

that we see hazards and risk, both terms being used in relation to human uses of the geographical space.

Floods, landslides, the instability of the coastline, abrupt subsidence and substratum failure are all either the cause or effect of natural events, which are generally grouped as hydrogeological phenomena. All of these are likely to affect coastal industries and populations adversely. These changes result from the interaction between meteorological events and the geological, morphological and hydrological environment, in which humans either play an important role by making the landscape more susceptible to change or are significantly affected (Torresan et al., 2014). Clearly, natural phenomena can cause disasters, but human actions often make them more severe. For example, in assessing the causes and consequences of the Katrina hurricane in August 2005, Austin (2009) showed that the situation was made worse in Southern Louisiana. These included its often-poor human population being less able to withstand the changes, a long history of coastal modification by natural and man-made levees and other modifications through canal construction and the oil exploration and extraction industries. In essence, the loss of coastal wetlands removed a capacity to cope with natural events such as hurricanes, a poor and poorly prepared population was unable to cope with the after-effects, and a large amount of unsuitable city infrastructure then increased the repercussions of the hurricane.

While determining the individual effects of each of these hazards and risks, the major challenge for the environmental and operational managers of coastal activities is determining the effects of several or many hazards acting together. These interactions, termed cumulative impacts or effects assessment, may be synergistic (additive) or antagonistic (cancelling) (see below).

The environmental manager/marine user will be concerned with each and every effect of their activities from inception through construction and operation to decommissioning. The activities will each have a footprint (i.e., where and when the activities take place and where they are licenced), which then gives rise to perhaps larger pressures-footprints, as the mechanisms of effects, and then to perhaps even larger effects-footprints in space and time of both the natural and societal systems (Elliott et al., 2020c). However, the manager will also have to be concerned with the effects of other activities inside the management area (causing endogenic pressures) and those changes inside an area due to factors outside the immediate management area (exogenic pressures). In essence, an environmental regulator will be able to sanction activities occurring within in an area through permits, consents, licences or authorisations, whereas the exogenic pressures require initiatives outside the management area, such globally controlled carbon emission regulations.

The essence of management for an industry or individuals, whether environmental or operational, is undertaking risk assessment and management and, where possible, opportunity assessment and opportunity management.

Risk assessment includes knowing:

- what and where are the causes of the problems, and what changes do they cause;
- what is their impact on ecosystem structure and functioning, including both the natural and human domains of the ecosystem;
- what are the repercussions for ecosystem valuation based on economy-ecology interactions, and
- what are the future environmental changes and economic futures for the industry.

Consequently, risk management includes knowing:

- what governance framework is there;
- what do stakeholders need, i.e., what are the priorities and concerns of other stakeholders;
- what are successes and failures;
- what can the industry, regulators or society do about the problems, hazards and risks, and how can they address them now and in the future; and
- how robust is the decision-making.

This requires knowing and using the above (Table 3) hazard and risk typology, showing what risks and hazards are created by activities, the responses of the receiving environment and the natural and societal receptors to the activities/pressures/effects, and the controls (Programmes of Measures, PoM) that are imposed on those activities by the regulators. Again, by definition, a hazard can occur in the environment, whether naturally or by human actions, and then it becomes a risk if it affects something we value. Those risks can be exacerbated by human actions, for example, by removing natural coastal defences, thereby leading to greater coastal erosion. This complexity of many activities, pressures and effects all operating in an area requires the need to consider Cumulative Impacts Assessment (CIA)/Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA) (NB, both terms have been used interchangeably in the literature thus the choice appears to merely be semantics and the preferences of an author (Blakley and Franks 2021)).

It is considered here that CEA/CIA This has many challenges with the need to determine:

- ways of increasing our limited ability to measure the spatial and temporal effects-footprints of pressures from named activities;

- the extent, duration and frequency of the pressures from an activity, not just the activity itself in a given place at a given time (note that the term activity is not equivalent to the term pressure);
- the relative effects of pressures from outside an area overlaying those caused by the industry itself;
- the weighting given to the different effects-footprints in space and time, not just assuming they are added (synergistic) linearly and arithmetically (they could be antagonistic (cancelling) or even linked exponentially);
- knowing what is in an area, what activities are present, what receptors there are, and what is their relevance;
- tackling the effects-footprints on the mobile receptors (mostly species, such as birds, fish and marine mammals passing through an area), not just the sedentary receptors (habitats and benthic species);
- accepting the assumption that CIA relates to ‘all impacts of all activities’ not just ‘all impacts of one activity/sector’ (the latter is just an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) carried out properly);
- whether there is a tipping point or threshold to an undesirable state when all impacts are taken together, and the effects-footprints overlap;
- the process of the effect of the activity of an industry and its pressures increasing the chances of moving from an impact on the natural receptors to those on the human receptors, thus moving along the continuum from ecosystem structure and functioning of ecosystem services to societal goods and benefits;
- for larger water bodies, playing a role in tackling the conceptual difficulties in the continuum from an EIA to CIA to Strategic Environmental Assessment, Maritime Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Zone Management;
- ensuring that PoMs are sufficient to control the sums of the activities, their pressures and effects on the natural and social systems both within and between nationally-defined management areas;
- finally, and perhaps the largest challenge, that the current system of managing activities (and their pressures and effects) are within national boundaries according to those nation-state administrative bodies and so managing transboundary areas and water bodies requires coherence and equivalence across boundaries (Cormier et al., 2022; Elliott et al., 2023).

4.2 Analytical tools available – Bow-tie analysis

4.2.1 Introduction to Bow-tie diagrams

Marine management fits within an overall DAPSI(W)R(M) (pronounced dap-see-worm) framework, the cause-consequence framework that links Drivers, Activities, Pressures, State change, Impacts (on human Welfare) and Responses (as management Measures). This is required to determine the risks and hazards to the marine system from natural and human causes and how those risks and hazards can be overcome using a programme of management measures (Elliott et al., 2017). In turn, such an approach can also be used to determine the opportunities in the marine system, which can be affected using a holistic management system (e.g., as carried out using a stakeholder-led approach in the EU FP7 Project CERES, Elliott et al., 2020b). This, in turn, is embedded in a systems analysis approach for integrated marine management (Elliott et al., 2020a), as indicated by Figure 1 (from Elliott, 2023).

Bow-tie analysis is an industry-propagated analytical approach for risk assessment and management, which can be easily adapted for opportunity assessment and management – essentially a cause-consequence-response approach (IEC/ISO, 2009). It is an ISO-31000 compliant method for producing conceptual models (Cormier et al., 2013, 2018, 2019). It addresses a risk or problem and indicates the causes of that problem, ways to prevent those causes and mitigate the resulting consequences that occur because of the problem.

Figure 1. The socio-ecological system aiming to unify the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework, the means of degrading the natural system and recovery management measures, and the ecological structure and functioning to ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits continuum. From: Elliott (2023).

As the proposed structure for the Bow-tie diagram analysis in this project, the central knot of the Bow-tie diagram represents a particular risk (e.g., loss of profits for a specific fishery due to climate change, or risk of not meeting GES). The left side lists pathways of potential causes (Figure 2 – generic model), whereas the right-side lists consequences resulting from the event. Controls to reduce or prevent the consequences are positioned along the pathways of risks on the left (solutions to prevent the central event) and on the right (mitigation/compensation and recovery from the central event). The prevention measures are aimed at stopping the hazard, stopping the hazard becoming a risk or reducing the likelihood that the hazard will occur or create consequent risks. Escalation factors, which undermine the effectiveness of a given control, can also be added with additional barriers. Hence, the scheme can accommodate uncertainty in risk management. The performance of management control in managing or reducing these uncertainties relies on a suite of barriers that eliminate, avoid or control the likelihood of a given risk to occur or to mitigate or recover from the consequences of a given risk. Barriers implemented closest to the sources of the risk (e.g., at the site of an activity) provide the greatest assurance in reducing uncertainty in achieving environmental management objectives. At the same time, determining the prevention or response to risk allows the opportunities to be defined for the sector in question to accommodate impacts and enhance growth successfully.

Figure 2. A simplified generic Bow-tie structure overlain by the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework (see text).

A key advantage of this method is that the Bow-tie concept visualises the risks being considered in one clear and easy-to-read picture (see Figure 2, or the Figures 3 and 4, as created by the proprietary software Bow-Tie XP³). Shaped like a Bow-tie, the diagram creates a clear differentiation between preventative and mitigation/compensation/adaptation measures – effective ways to prevent an event from happening, and if it does, ways to mitigate any effects; the latter step will also include any compensation, adaptation and control measures. The power of a Bow-tie analysis is that it shows a summary of numerous risk scenarios in a single, easy-to-follow picture that can be understood by all levels of an organisation, as well as the general public. In short, it provides a simple, visual explanation of a risk that would be much more difficult to explain otherwise.

Figure 3. Simplified Bow-tie with DAPSI(W)R(M) overlay – to determine causes and consequences and to agree on the responses throughout the sequence, as created by proprietary software (Cormier et al., 2019).

³ <https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en-gb/solutions/enablon/bowtie/bowtiexp>

Figure 4. Bow-tie Analysis as a Problem-Structuring Method with the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework embedded (First used in the EU CERES project as a novel attempt to use BT analysis for climate change repercussions for fisheries and aquaculture) (Cormier et al., 2013, 2018, 2019).

Originally designed for use within sectors such as the aviation industry and health and safety practices, the Bow-tie concept is a risk management tool supplementing cause-and-effect and impact assessments to manage the risks of potentially catastrophic events in a broad range of industry sectors. It provides a systematic approach to assuring control over environmental, health and safety hazards. It is increasingly used for the ecosystem approach and mapping environmental and ecological risks and their management (e.g., Burdon et al., 2018; Elliott et al., 2020b). This approach has been recommended by ICES and the Department for Fisheries & Oceans Canada as their preferred risk assessment and management methodology (Cormier et al., 2013).

The DAPSI(W)R(M) framework is easily overlain onto the Bow-tie analysis, making it ideal for ecological risk assessment and management (Figures 1-4). This encompasses Drivers, Activities, Pressures (as mechanisms of change), State change (on the natural system), Impact (on human Welfare), and Responses (using management Measures), which are based on the 10-tenets for successful and sustainable marine management (Elliott, 2013; Barnard and Elliott, 2015) (Table 4). In essence, the D, A and P are the left-hand side causes of both the central problem and the consequences (both the central knot and the right-hand side consequences reflect the S (on the natural system) and the I(W) on the human system. The R(W) management initiatives are then reflected by the prevention and mitigation/compensation controls acting on the causes.

Within recent ecological applications of this process (Elliott et al., 2020b), potential opportunities arising from the problem/central event have also been explored. These can be represented on the Bow-tie diagram on the right-hand side together with the consequences.

Table 4. The 10-tenets for successful and sustainable marine management – used to create the responses using management measures.

To be successful, management measures or responses to changes resulting from human activities should be:

- Ecologically sustainable
- Technologically feasible
- Economically viable
- Socially desirable/tolerable
- Legally permissible
- Administratively achievable
- Politically expedient
- Ethically defensible (morally correct)
- Culturally inclusive
- Effectively communicable

In summary (see Figure 5), a Bow-tie depicts: what is the problem of concern, what are the causes, what are the prevention mechanisms, what are the mitigation/compensation measures, and the consequences (and if there are any opportunities).

Figure 5. The explained background to elements of the Bow-tie method – the ‘escalation factors’ may enhance or hinder the action of the prevention, mitigation, compensation, adaptation and control measures (see Cormier et al., 2019).

4.2.2 Examples of Bow-tie use in previous EU projects

Figures 6 and 7 are examples of Bow-tie diagrams used in two recent EU projects, VECTORS and CERES, showing how the Bow-ties can be adapted for each unique situation either through the use of specialist structured software (Figure 6, VECTORS) or via the use of conceptual diagrams (Figure 7, CERES). The examples given were created by stakeholder-led panels.

Figure 6. Bow-tie for climate change effects on OWF EU VECTORS Project (See also Burdon et al., 2018).

Key to control and mitigation measures

Ranked High

- 1. Catch and release:** promote the catch and release of endangered native species
- 2. Control trade in marine species:** control and punish the trade of endangered native species
- 3. Stock management:** Larger investment in maintaining existing stocks
- 4. Fisheries management:** Increasing the open season and the quotas to be considered.
- 5. Technology:** very important to adapt technologies for the site characteristics.

Ranked Medium

- 6. EU legislation:** Cheaper insurances for losses
- 7. Stock enhancement programs:** programmes oriented to enhance mussel seed settlement and recruitment
- 8. Local legislation:** Investment in more effective control of production and sales and updating of aquaculture law
- 9. Habitat management:** increasing the area destined for mussel seed collection and mussel settlement structures

Ranked Low

- 10. Government incentives:** More investment in government vet/climate agencies
- 11. Technology:** more research oriented to improve harvesting techniques and cultivation structures
- 12. Government incentives:** Subsidies to buy seed
- 13. Promote alternative resources:** control exotic species to decrease the interspecific competition

No ranking given

- a. Local legislation:** allow to farm other species not currently allowed
- b. Local legislation:** less restrictions in farming practices
- c. Promote alternative resources:** look for the most suitable species for the sites
- d. Government incentives:** reduce the taxes and fees on farming, incentives on diversification of species and products
- e. Promote alternative resources:** Increase "gastronomic" tourism or other nautical/climate tourism activities
- f. Promote alternative resources:** explore new commercial markets

(Ack. John Icelly, Algarve)

Figure 7. A complex example Bow-tie from the EU H2020 CERES project [includes a key to the mitigation and control measures] (Elliott et al., 2020b).

4.2.3 Terminology of management measures – definitions

Once the causes and consequences of changes to the GES within LSs have been determined, the more important part of this sequence is determining management measures to prevent or accommodate the consequences. The management measures adopted in risk assessment and risk management terminology rely on prevention, mitigation, adaptation, compensation and control. In general,

mitigation is used to reduce the adverse effects, adaptation is a means of coping with those effects, and compensation is a means of accommodating those effects.

In general, the term mitigation can be used for almost all management measures and in the Bow-tie analysis here, the type of mitigation measures depends on the central event. In terms of the Bow-tie, it is usual to attempt to prevent the central event from occurring. A Bow-tie diagram and the ISO standards aim to structure the management risk along proactive (prevention) and reactive (mitigation and recovery) management strategies, where proactive strategies provide the least uncertainty of achieving policy objectives while reactive strategies have the most uncertainty of achieving objectives.

In contrast, when adaptation is used, as in the case of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), it does not classify the risks in terms of management strategies because it focuses on the consequences of climate events (heat, storms, etc) and the effects of climate change on the environment and people. The IPCC uses a risk assessment approach based on likelihood and consequences (impacts) (e.g., Hidalgo et al., 2022), while the Bow-tie is a risk management approach aimed at reducing the effects of uncertainty in achieving objectives by implementing (i) proactive management strategies to prevent the problems that could undermine the objectives, and (ii) reactive management strategies to reduce the consequences when the proactive management strategies fail. It is emphasised that management may merely mean removing the pressures and allowing the system to recover.

The definitions above have led to the development of the generic Bow-tie (Figure 8), which is based on three standards: the IEC/ISO (2009) definitions and their concepts, the application in environmental management in the Australian standards HB 203: 2012, and the most recent version of IEC/ISO 31010:2019 which generalised the measures as preventative and reactive management measures (Cormier et al., 2019). These show that prevention controls the cause to reduce the likelihood of an event, mitigation reduces the magnitude of the consequences of an event, and recovery controls recover from the consequences of an event that could not be mitigated. IEC/ISO 31010: 2019 introduced the concept of cascading events, where a consequence of an event becomes the cause of a subsequent event. This version also includes management activities to support the implementation of a control in addition to escalation factors and controls.

The further management measure, compensation, is used to allow both the ecological system and the users to accommodate adverse changes even if the changes are not prevented. There are three types of compensation (Elliott et al., 2016) – (i) to financially compensate the users, such as fishers, for the loss of income, (ii) to compensate the resource, such as by restocking or replanting, and (iii) to

compensate the environment by re-creating or creating new habitat to allow for the loss in-situ or elsewhere.

Figure 8. Generic Bow-tie (created using Bow-Tie XP).

4.3 Guide for operationalisation

4.3.1 Bow-tie diagram creation within GES4SEAS

Within GES4SEAS, the approach aims to use case-studies (the relevant storyline(s) for each of the LSs) to produce Bow-tie conceptual models, which can be formed by asking the following question: “*What are the main issues/concerns in your LS regarding risks to achieving GES and require management of the human activities and their relevant pressures?*”. This important question frames the storyline(s) for each LS and will form the central knot of the Bow-tie. Once the storyline(s) for each LS has/have been selected, the main question to interrogate the storyline is: “*In relation to the selected storyline, what are the causes and consequences of risks to achieving GES in your LS, and how can the causes (human activities) be best managed to reduce the pressures to a level that will allow GES to be achieved and maintained?*”.

The causes relate to the drivers, activities and pressures identified in the LS, using information from the high-level stakeholders in WP1 in GES4SEAS, as well as those acknowledged by the project partners within the LS (WP5). This should then cover the endogenic causes (those emanating from within the LS and in which both the causes and consequences can be addressed by management measures inside the LS) and the exogenic causes (those emanating from outside the LS and in which

the causes are controlled globally but the consequences have to be addressed inside the LS, for example, climate change). In order to answer this, the questions needed to specify that storyline (i.e., to build the Bow-tie) are:

- What causes this/these issue(s)/concern(s)? What pressures are caused by human activities?
- What are the consequences of the issue(s)/concern(s)? What are the consequences to specific descriptors?
- What opportunities (if any) come from the issue(s)/concern(s)? What are the drivers that are seeking the opportunities?
- What can be done as management measures (i) to prevent the issue(s)/concern(s) from happening, (ii) to adapt, control, mitigate and/or compensate for the consequences if the issue(s)/concern(s) does/do occur? How can these measures reduce the pressures and what mitigation is needed when GES is not achieved or maintained?
- What factors can enhance the management measures, and what factors can cause them to fail? What are the escalation factors that contribute to the pressures and undermine GES?

Some semi/quantitative assessment is likely to be needed in the GES4SEAS operationalisation of the Bow-ties, and a **semi-quantitative assessment** could be easily integrated when questioning stakeholders and others (see above, relating to causes, consequences, mitigation/prevention, and opportunities). This could be achieved by asking expert stakeholders to distinguish more/less likely causes, or higher/lower risk of consequences. For example, this approach was used in the CERES project and was done via an online questionnaire sent to stakeholders for each storyline with back-end software that could (semi)quantitatively assess responses and answers via computer to rank outputs of most/least impact.

To allow a **fully quantitative assessment**, indicators for the different elements of the Bow-tie would need to be identified, for example:

- How do we measure the cause (e.g., pressure)? Do we measure the indicators for the pressures as listed in MSFD 2017/848?
- How do we measure the biodiversity change, etc.? Do we measure the indicators for GES as listed in MSFD 2017/848?

As shown here, it is emphasised that in the context of GES4SEAS, and the application to European water bodies, the definitions and approaches given in the Directive, its Annexes and its Guidance documents should be used where possible. The tools/models provided in WP2, WP3 and WP4 in GES4SEAS and available to the LSs could allow us to parametrise/quantify the different cause-effects links within the Bow-tie framework (e.g., how much the provision of a benefit is expected to change

(based on its quantitative indicator) as a consequence of a change in the biodiversity component (non-mitigated or mitigated)?).

Different models/tools, including conceptual approaches, may be able to quantify different parts of the Bow-tie, with the Bow-tie providing the framework for linking all these models into assessing the storyline. This would also allow the identification of gaps (general or specific to the LS) where some links cannot be quantified (e.g., due to a lack of data or models to do so). Alternatively, as performed in CERES, a Bayesian Belief Network (BBN) model could be built using the Bow-tie as the conceptual model to define its structure.

4.3.2 GES4SEAS scenarios/storylines as a basis for the Bow-tie diagrams

The stocktaking of pressures and impacts in Task 5.1 of GES4SEAS will allow the LSs to generate one or more storylines in their case study area to determine and quantify the causes and consequences of change in both the natural and socioeconomic systems. It is important at this early stage to keep the initial generation of the Bow-tie diagrams simple and linked to the GES4SEAS project aims. The aim is to create a list of all the possible elements that can go in the Bow-tie, bearing in mind that they may occur along different levels of the chain of cause-consequences that lead to the main problem and that span from it. When defining the Bow-tie for their specific problem of interest, the LSs can create from these lists whatever is relevant to their case (or add missing elements) and link them as appropriate. It is important to define and be clear about the central problem/aspect and present it in terms easily understood by the stakeholders – hence, the central problem/issue is the main aim of the approach.

Therefore, as with CERES, a single Bow-tie can (and should) include the elements of both the ecological and societal aspects. Table 5 gives examples of the causes and consequences which can be incorporated into a Bow-tie storyline or storylines at the LSs.

GES4SEAS aims to determine the methods and approaches relating to the assessment of GES and, where it is not met, the means of marine management to rectify this. Hence, there is a need to include the cascade from Natural Capital (Habitats and Species), Ecosystem Services (Processes) and Societal Benefits. The first two components are within the 'natural environment' and are reflected in the State change component in DAPSI(W)R(M), whilst the Societal Benefits relate to humans and, therefore, are in the 'societal domain' are reflected in the Impacts (on Welfare) component. Figure 9 identifies the Natural Capital, Ecosystem Services and Societal Benefits within a generic marine system and may be useful for users when considering elements to incorporate into Bow-ties.

Table 5. Examples of the causes and consequences, which can be incorporated in a Bow-tie Scenario/Storyline for GES4SEAS

Causes		Consequences (adverse or opportunities)
<p>Loss of natural connectivity. Anthropogenic loss of connectivity. Introduction of anthropogenic structures. Introduction of contaminants. Removal/reduction of a commercial species. Removal/reduction of a non-commercial species. Removal/reduction of an iconic species. Reduction/loss of particular/named habitat area. Reduction of named habitat quality. Increased exploitation of a biological resource. Increased exploitation of a physical resource. Change to water quality. Change to sediment quality. Climate change – increased acidification. Climate change – increased SLR. Climate change - increased temperature. Climate change – change to species distribution. Climate change – physico-chemical water quality changes (other than those specified above). Climate change – increased storminess. Climate change – changes in seasonal/temporal patterns of abiotic/biotic processes. Reduction of primary production – water column. Reduction of primary production – bed. Overall reduction in ecosystem service a, b, Changes to the sum of biological traits. Changes to the habitat mosaic. Reduction/loss of functionality of an area (and the multiple habitats within) (e.g., as essential fish habitat).</p>	<p>Central ‘knot’ or problem of concern: <u>The reduction in (or failure to meet) the Good Environmental Status in the Learning Site area</u></p>	<p>Loss of employment. Change of the method of exploitation. Resultant change to health of named species. Resultant change to a named ecological community. Change to exploiting other species/new markets. Loss of societal goods and benefits, of income or cultural benefits. Loss of physical resources (e.g., space, seabed). Loss of biological resources (e.g., fisheries). Reduction of ability to cope with/mitigate for climate change effects" (incl. reduction in carbon storage, lower protection against extreme events, etc.). Influence on EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. Influence on SDG14. Breach of Marine Strategy Framework Directive. Breach of Maritime Spatial Planning Directive. Breach of Bird Directive or of Habitat and Species Directive. Breach of Regional Seas Conventions demands. Overall reduction in societal benefits x, y, Reduction of commercial species population(s) leading to a loss of societal goods and benefits. Activities change or displacement outside the Learning Site area (and related social-economic consequences, e.g., loss of certain types of businesses, impact on local communities). Loss of local culture, tradition and values. Increased competition for the (more) limited resources. Increased prices/costs (incl. Market price of resources, costs for accessing/extracting the resources (goods) or benefits under the changed conditions). Loss of tourism.</p>

Figure 9. A unified ecosystem services and societal goods and benefits model. From: Elliott (2023).

Formulating a Bow-tie based on a generic problem may be challenging as the causes and consequences of the central issue/problem can include both natural and anthropogenic factors, which are often interrelated. Hence, a Bow-tie should be designed for a specific problem, for example: a central specific problem regarding a reduction in environmental quality and hence an ability to meet GES, such as the loss (of area or quality) of biodiversity. It is, therefore, easier to identify the cause(s) and consequence(s) of a focused, specific central problem (both linked to the natural and the anthropogenic aspects) passing through the centre of the Bow-tie. It would be straightforward then to e.g., colour code natural or anthropogenic elements differently for ease of understanding.

As carried out for the CERES project, it may also be appropriate to have one cause leading to another cause and one consequence leading to another consequence, etc. Consequently, that project derived chained BTs. The models created in CERES also colour-coded adverse consequences differently from opportunities. In addition, and as linked to the underlying rationale for the project in GES4SEAS, there is the need to keep in mind the environmental quality repercussions to the ecological and socio-economic aspects.

4.3.3 How to form the Bow-tie diagrams

Although there is proprietary software for creating Bow-tie diagrams, as used to create several of the above diagrams, it is emphasised that this can be achieved more simply using Power Point (as in the CERES project). As shown in the examples in Elliott et al. (2020b), once several or many Bow-tie diagrams have been created, the common elements and conclusions can be determined.

Step 1: The central problem.

Also known as the knot, the event being the problem or the issue, this is key to forming the Bow-tie or what is the problem of concern? Examples of possible central events could be:

- The possibility of any of the hazards and risks identified in Table 3.
- Environmental consequences of construction, operation and/or decommissioning techniques of human activities.
- Economic costs or benefits of different technologies in the activities.
- Environmental consequences of climate change on the habitats, ecosystems or activities.
- Enhanced climate change adaptation and mitigation.
- Influence on other marine uses and users.
- Economic benefits of adaptation techniques.

Step 2: Causes and their prevention/mitigation/compensation:

- What are the causes of the central event/problem?
- What mechanisms can prevent these causes from leading to the central event?
- What management measures can be applied to reduce the magnitude or likelihood of the central event happening due to the causes? (e.g., to adapt, control, mitigate or compensate?)
- What factors can enhance the management measures, and what (escalation) factors can cause them to fail?

Step 3: Consequences and opportunities:

- What are the consequences (negative) arising from the central event/problem if no actions were to be taken? (e.g., the effects on the ecosystem and its habitats, Ecosystem Services and Societal Goods and Benefits)?
- Are any opportunities (positive consequences) arising from the central event/problem?
- What management measures (based on the 10-tenets) can be applied to reduce the magnitude or likelihood of the consequences (e.g., to adapt, control, mitigate or compensate)?
- What enhancement measures can be applied to reduce or increase the benefits from any opportunities (positive consequences)?

- What factors can enhance the management measures, and what (escalation) factors can cause them to fail?

Hence, the approach can be presented as a framework for tackling the problem and identifying opportunities (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Flowchart for structuring a Bow-tie diagram for risk and opportunity assessment and management.

5. Assessment of Best Options for Practical Ecosystem-Based Approaches

This section reports specifically on Subtasks 2.3.2 and 2.3.3 and aims to provide a Decision Support Tool (DST) that will guide the LSs in WP5 in identifying the best options (tools) for the practical implementation of EBM. Identifying the best practical options is conditional to factors including, e.g., data requirements and availability (Subtasks 2.3.2) and scales of the assessment (Subtasks 2.3.3).

5.1 What makes an ecosystem-based approach practical? (Assessment criteria)

No single, individual approach (a tool or combination of tools) is always the best option for any practical implementation of EBM (i.e., one-size-fits-all does not apply). Rather, the best option(s) depend(s) on the circumstances and requirements of the specific EBM in the case study. Hence, ‘best’ takes the meaning of ‘most suitable for the circumstances’ relevant to the specific application. The work done here aims at building a DST for the LSs (and any user) to apply to identify the tool(s) that best apply in their cases, given their specific needs and expectations for EBM.

The first step towards this was identifying the key characteristics of the available approaches that can determine their higher or lower suitability for practical implementation under different conditions. It is important to note that the available approaches (as identified in D2.1; Papadopoulou et al., 2023) are not management tools *per se*, but rather, they are essentially ecosystem-based assessment (EBA) tools that can be used to support the EBM process throughout its different phases (Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Given the overall aim of Task 2.3 (to identify “Best Options for Practical Ecosystem-based Approaches”), the first question that was asked was “What factors make an EBA practical?”. By answering this question, it is possible to identify criteria against which an approach may be assessed in order to determine its suitability for practical implementation, i.e., to assess its applicability.

In this context, the three key factors that were considered took into account the following aspects:

- The EBA tool is **fit for purpose**, i.e., the tool allows to address the specific needs related to the management issues relevant to the case study. For example, these needs may be qualified based on which element(s) of the EBM the user aims to deliver, the scales at which the assessment is to be undertaken, whether uncertainty needs to be estimated, etc.
- The **resources available** to the user for the assessment are sufficient to implement the tool in the case study. Resources can be the data or evidence available, which may be of different

types and quality (data or expert judgment, qualitative or quantitative data regarding different ecosystem components, etc.). Resources can also be skills and expertise required from the user of a specific tool, equipment (e.g., high computational capacity computers), economic resources (e.g., to pay for the acquisition of certain software), staff time, etc.

- There also may be assumptions made by the tool, or **limitations** in its applicability that the user needs to be aware of to implement the tool and use its outputs correctly. These identify possible weaknesses of a tool, also including possible barriers the user may encounter to its implementation. Along with knowledge of the strengths, this information would support the user in the tool's practical application.

The criteria outlined above were used to formulate a series of key questions that could be used to gather information on the available EBA tools and to match them with the specific users' needs, allowing for the subsequent identification of the best (or optimal) option(s) applicable for that specific case. The methods applied for this are described in section 5.2 below.

5.2 Assessment methods

5.2.1 Data gathering

An online survey was developed using the Jisc Online Survey system⁴ to collect information regarding the 19 tool groups identified in Deliverable 2.1 (and specific tools within these groups) relevant to their application in support of EBM (Papadopoulou et al., 2023). The survey was structured as a questionnaire that first identified the particular tool being assessed and subsequently sought information on those key characteristics that may influence how it is used in an EBM context (see outline of the questionnaire in Table 6).

These characteristics included:

- What the tool is used for in terms of the element(s) of EBM it may deliver, its typical applications and users;
- What type of assessment the tool may provide, in terms of elements of the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework and GES descriptors or criteria covered, the spatial and temporal scales involved, and whether confidence or uncertainty are assessed;
- What type of data, expertise or other resources the tool requires to be applied (in relation to data/skills rich and data/skills poor situations);
- What the strengths and weaknesses of the tool are, including assumptions affecting the outcomes and barriers to its application.

⁴ <https://beta.jisc.ac.uk/online-surveys>

Wherever possible, the answers were standardised by providing the respondent with options to select (Table 6). Free text entries were also allowed for the respondent to provide specific details or clarification on their input.

Respondents were also asked to identify their familiarity with the tool subject of the questionnaire (Q4 in Table 6). This information was used to qualify the confidence level associated with the individual response during the data processing (see Data analysis, section 5.2.2).

The online survey was circulated to all GES4SEAS researchers and Practitioners' Advisory Board (PAB) members, as well as externally to the project, including the participants of other ongoing sister Horizon Europe projects, such as MARBEFES and MarinePlan, and to targeted experts identified based on their experience in developing and applying some of the tools under assessment. The survey was initially open for completion from 4th July to 11th August 2023, with a secondary (targeted) release from 18th to 21st August 2023 to collate information on specific tools that had not been adequately covered by the returns from the original release.

Table 6. Outline of the topics addressed by the questions (Q) in the online survey ('response options' is left blank where open text response was required).

Section and Q#	Topic	Response options
B. Scope of response		
Q2	Tool group the response is about	Select one of 20 [19 tool groups as identified in D2.1 + 'Other']
Q2a	If 'Other': Specify	
Q3	Whether the response characterises the generic tool group or a specific tool within	Select one of 2 [Wider group; Specific tool]
Q3a	If 'Specific tool': Specify which tool	
Q4	Familiarity of the respondent with the tool	Select one of 4 [Expert; Very familiar; Familiar; Low]
C. (i) Purpose of the tool		
Q5	Assign tool to EBM elements addressed & PACE (Plan, Act, Check, Evaluate) phase (current & potential)	Select any option in a matrix [18 EBM elements x 5 (P; A; C; E; unsure) x 2 (current; potential)]
Q6	Whether the tool is used alone to deliver the EBM element(s)	Select one of 2 [Y; N]
Q6a	If 'N' - Why and which other tools are required	
Q6b	Further comments on tool capability	
Q7	Tool current use - how/ whom by	Select any of 9 [Official MSFD reporting; EU projects; EU Technical Groups; RSC assessment groups; EEA assessments; IECS WGs; Gen. Fish. Comm. Medit. Groups; other NCA; Other]
Q7a	If 'Other': Specify	
Q8	Relevance of the tool to marine governance	Select one of 2 [Y; N]

Section and Q#	Topic	Response options
Q8a	If 'Y': what it is used for	Select any of 8 [Targets setting/development; Monitoring programmes delivery; Tracking progress against action plans; Remediation/management measures design; Inform decision-making; MSFD thresholds development; Indirect use (supporting evidence for policy development); Other]
Q8b	If 'Other': Specify	
C. (ii) Capability of the tool		
Q9	DAPSI(W)R(M) components used by the tool (as single/multiple variables, as input/output)	Select any option in a matrix [8 components (Activities, Pressures, Species (State change), Habitats (State change), Ecosystem Services (State change), Societal Goods & Benefits (Impact on welfare), Response measures, Other) x 2 (as input/output) x 2 (as single/multiple variables)]
Q9a	If 'Other': Specify	
Q10	Whether the tool assesses GES Descriptors and/or Criteria	Select one of 4 [N; Y-Descriptors; Y-Criteria; Y-both]
Q10a	If 'Y': list Descriptors/Criteria	
Q11	Whether the tool requires or provides spatial/temporal inputs or outputs, and which type	Select any option in a matrix [5 (spatial input, spatial output, temporal input, temporal output, not relevant) x 3 types (quantitative, semi-quantitative, qualitative)]
Q11a	Additional notes on Q11	
Q12	Specify spatial scales (if spatial aspects are relevant)	Select any of 5 [Site (< 10 km ²); Local (10-100 km ²); National (100-10k km ²); Regional (10k-100k km ²); European (> 100k km ²)]
Q13	Specify temporal scales (if temporal aspects are relevant)	Select any of 4 [Short term (seasonal); Short-med term (1 Year); Med-long term (1-10 Years); Long term (> 10 Years)]
C. (iii) Requirements of the tool		
Q14a	For the relevant DAPSI(W)R(M) components (as per Q9): Type of data - Quantitative	
Q14b	For the relevant DAPSI(W)R(M) components (as per Q9): Type of data - Semi-quantitative	
Q14c	For the relevant DAPSI(W)R(M) components (as per Q9): Type of data - Qualitative	
Q14d	Whether expert judgement can be used if data are not available	Select one of 2 [Y; N]
Q15	Expertise required	Select any of 9 [None; Statistical; Analytical; Modelling; programming (e.g., R); GIS; Ecological knowledge, Don't know; Other]
Q15a	If 'Other': Specify	
Q16	Whether specific software is required	Select one of 5 [N; Y-free; Y-at a cost; Don't know; Other]
Q16a	If 'Other': Specify	
Q16b	Links/references to software/training	
Q17	Whether other resources are needed	Select one of 3 [Y; N; Unsure]

Section and Q#	Topic	Response options
Q17a	If 'Y'/'Unsure': Specify	
D. (i) Assumptions/ Limitations of the tool		
Q18	Whether assumptions are made which restrict the tool's applicability	Select one of 4 [Y; Y-assumptions, but no restrictions; No; Unsure]
Q18a	If 'Y'/'Unsure': Specify	
Q19	Whether the tool is suited to data/skill rich or data/skill poor situations	Select any option in a matrix [4 (data/skill x rich/poor) x 4 suitability (no; poor; moderate; good)]
Q19a	Potential barriers to tool use	Select any of 6 [No monitoring data available; No full compatibility with policy requirements; Requires specific monitoring programmes; No thresholds/targets; Other]
Q19b	If 'Other': Specify	
Q19c	How barriers can be overcome	
D. (ii) Confidence/ Uncertainty		
Q20	Confidence/Uncertainty information used in inputs	Select one of 3 [Y; N; Don't know]
Q20a	If 'Y': Specify	
Q21	Confidence/Uncertainty information produced with outputs	Select one of 3 [Y; N; Don't know]
Q21a	If 'Y': Specify	
E. Final remarks		
Q22a	Tool strengths	
Q22b	Tool weaknesses	
Q22c	Additional comments	

5.2.2 Data preparation and preliminary analysis

Initially, the questionnaire returns were explored to identify a definitive list of tools that were assessed by the respondents. As the survey allowed a respondent to contribute either with knowledge of the tool group in general (out of the list of 19 tool groups that were initially provided) or of a specific tool within a tool group, these responses were differentiated as separate tools for the analysis (although the characteristics of a specific tool were likely to be a subset of the features of the generic group the tool belonged to).

Responses for an individual tool, where available, were explored and merged before the analysis. Where inconsistencies between replicate responses were identified for a certain question, the frequency of the different responses and the level of expertise of the respondents (as an indicator of confidence) were considered. Data provided by respondents with low familiarity with a tool (defined as cases where they heard of the approach but had not used it themselves and were not fully aware

of its application) were excluded from the analysis, whereas other responses with higher levels of confidence were available.

The data were also explored for inconsistencies in the responses of an individual expert across questions (e.g., highlighting possible misinterpretation). Where possible, such inconsistencies were amended through consultation with the respondent where needed.

The processed dataset was subject to a preliminary analysis to identify general characteristics across all tools supporting EBM. A frequency analysis of the responses obtained across all tools was applied to identify, for example:

- Which elements of EBM are most frequently delivered by the tools assessed, and how frequently the assessment requires tools to be used in combination;
- Which DAPSI(W)R(M) components are included in the assessments, and what type of data are required to document them;
- Which spatial and temporal scales are most commonly addressed;
- How the tools are commonly used and by whom;
- What evidence types are required, and how frequently expert judgment can be accommodated in the assessment;
- Which skills or other resources are most frequently required;
- What are the strengths and weaknesses (incl. barriers) most commonly identified across all tools.

The analysis was undertaken across all the tools and also specifically for those subsets of tools that allow the delivery of the EBM elements at the core of GES4SEAS (namely tools used for cumulative impact assessment and MSFD GES assessment). The results of the analysis, with the answers to the questions above are given in sections 5.3.1 to 5.3.6 of this report.

5.2.3 Development of a Decision Support System - SEAS4GES

As noted earlier, it is important to recognise that there is no single 'best' approach that can be adopted by LSs to cope with and satisfy all potential circumstances, but rather that the optimal approach will vary according to both the specific needs of the user, and the nature and extent of available supporting data.

A DST, SEAS4GES (Selection of Ecosystem-based Approaches for Good Environmental Status), has been developed using the detailed information from the questionnaire returns to help guide the LSs in identifying the optimal option(s) to implement an ecosystem-based approach supporting EBM.

The SEAS4GES tool (Figure 11) is currently provided as a beta version, produced as a proof-of-concept, and it is recognised that several areas might be improved with further focussed development. Functionality has been deliberately restricted to allow the tool to run without macros or other VBA coding. It was produced using the Microsoft 365 Excel tool, running under Microsoft Windows 11. The current version (β 2.01) has been checked using the McAfee 'Total Protection' antivirus suite (version 1.11.279, release 16.0 R111), and no threats were found.

Figure 11. The SEAS4GES tool.

The SEAS4GES tool provides a **user interface** (which comprises a user input tab and two principal output tabs) and a series of dynamic links to **(PDF) factsheets** (see Appendix 1 to this report) that provide the LSs with additional information (as narratives) about the tool(s) selected. The user input tab of the SEAS4GES tool consists of two parts, allowing the tool to initially assess tool suitability with regard to users' needs, and subsequently with regard to the tools' operating requirements. These two elements are expanded on below:

Filtering by user needs - what does the user want to do? This first section contains six 'filters' which, together, outline the user's needs. The tool takes the user's responses and compares them against the functionality of each of the range of 34 possible EBAs under consideration⁵, as previously defined through the responses to the online survey questionnaire.

These six filters specifically address scales of assessment and are particularly relevant to subtask 2.3.3. They specifically identify:

- the particular elements or applications of EBM that you need to address;
- whether there are particular aspects of marine management that the user is interested in;

⁵ An additional tool - GES4HABs decision tree (a specific tool within the group of conceptual models) – has been identified and has been proposed in Task 2.2. As information on this tool was received at a later stage of the D2.3 reporting, it could not be included in the analysis undertaken in this report and in the SEAS4GES DST (where it is currently represented as part of the generic tool group Conceptual models, #1). The information provided for this specific tool has only been included as a factsheet (Appendix 1) for now, but there are plans to add it in the next iteration of the DST.

- whether there are particular GES Descriptors that the user is interested in;
- whether the user needs the tool to produce spatial outputs (e.g., maps) and, if so, at what scale(s);
- whether the user needs the tool to produce temporal outputs (e.g., future projections/forecasting) and, if so, at what scale(s); and
- whether the user requires a measure of the level of confidence in the outputs from the tool.

As the checkboxes against the options for each filter (see Figure 12 for an example) are selected/deselected, the SEAS4GES tool will assess how many of the options are satisfied by each approach and express this as a percentage 'compliance' score that represents the extent to which the user's needs are satisfied by each approach.

Part 1: Filtering by user needs - what do you want to do?	
Filter.01	Which particular element or application of EBM do you need to address? Select all that apply:
Cumulative effects assessments - CEA	<input type="checkbox"/>
GES MSFD assessments	<input type="checkbox"/>
Whole ecosystem assessments	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ecosystem Services (delivery, impacts, valuation)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Special biotic effects/impacts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pressures-Activities footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Links activities pressures impacts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Single species, ecosystem Components State change	<input type="checkbox"/>
Threatened habitats and species	<input type="checkbox"/>
Climate change	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Spatial and other measures	<input type="checkbox"/>
Uncertainty	<input type="checkbox"/>
Risks	<input type="checkbox"/>
MSPD	<input type="checkbox"/>
Birds and Habitats Directives	<input type="checkbox"/>
Biodiversity Strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 12. Example of user input to the SEAS4GES tool (filter #1).

Filtering by available information and skills - what are you able to provide? This second section contains a further six 'filters' which, together, outline the range and nature of data and skills that you and your organisation are able to provide. Again, the tool compares the user's responses against the requirements of each of the 34 possible EBAs under consideration.

This second block of filters identifies:

- Whether quantitative data are available for specific DAPSI(W)R(M) components: A (Activities), P (Pressures, Spp (Species), Hab (Habitats), ES (Ecosystem Services), & SGB (Societal Goods and Benefits);
- Whether semi-quantitative data available for specific DAPSI(W)R(M) components: A (Activities), P (Pressures, Spp (Species), Hab (Habitats), ES (Ecosystem Services), & SGB (Societal Goods and Benefits);
- Whether qualitative data are available for specific DAPSI(W)R(M) components: A (Activities), P (Pressures, Spp (Species), Hab (Habitats), ES (Ecosystem Services), & SGB (Societal Goods and Benefits);
- Whether, where empirical data are not available, expert judgment might be used as a potential alternative source of data;
- What specific expertise the user or their wider organisation is able to apply to their use of the approach; and
- Whether the data that the user has available includes associated confidence/uncertainty information.

Together with the checkshets, these filters specifically address data requirements for activities, pressures, ecosystem components, etc., as relevant to subtask 2.3.2 (itemised by tool).

Again, as the checkboxes against each filter are selected/deselected, the SEAS4GES tool dynamically assesses how many of the needs of each tool are selected/deselected, and will express this as a percentage 'compliance' score that represents the extent to which the requirements of each approach are satisfied by the data and skills that the user or LS has at their disposal.

The first **output provided by the SEAS4GES** tool is a simple matrix that shows the percentage compliance scores for each approach against each of the 12 filters (filters 1-6 representing the user's needs, and filters 7-12 representing the approaches' requirements) (see Figure 13).

SEAS4GES Selection of Ecosystem-based Approaches 4 GES
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Ver β 2.01

Compliance scores for each approach, by needs and requirements

Filter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Filter 1: User requirements - what are you looking for?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 2: Available information & skills - what are you able to provide?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 3: Quantitative data available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 4: Semi-quantitative data available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 5: Qualitative data available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 6: Empirical data available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 7: Expert judgment available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 8: Confidence/uncertainty information available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 9: Specific expertise available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 10: Empirical data available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 11: Expert judgment available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Filter 12: Confidence/uncertainty information available for specific variables?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Figure 13. Example of output from the SEAS4GES tool (compliance matrix).

Across the matrix, higher values indicate where an approach represents a 'better' option given the assessment needs of the user or the ability of the user to satisfy the requirements of an approach. Conversely, lower scores indicate where an approach is less suitable. The cells in the matrix are colour-coded to aid interpretation: those approaches that have compliance for a given (user) need or (approach) requirement above 66% are shaded green; those in the 33-66% range are shaded orange; and those below 33% are shaded red. However, when the SEAS4GES tool is first opened, all cells in the matrix are blank (reflecting that no comparisons have yet been made between user needs and the approaches' capabilities, or between the available data and skills and the approaches' operational requirements). As the user provides responses to each of the 12 filters, the matrix is populated (and colour-coded) row by row. In this way, the user can see where potential limitations on using particular approaches lie.

Given the vast number of potential combinations of user needs and tool requirements that are assessed against the 34 possible approaches, it was not feasible to generate category breaks based on a formal frequency assessment of the full potential set of assessment outputs. In lieu of such an objective approach, a simple pragmatic approach was adopted to aid interpretation. For this, values of 33% and 66% were selected to represent the boundaries between nominally low, medium, and high levels of compliance, and are primarily intended simply to allow colour-coding to be used in the graphical (matrix) output to help support the rapid visual interpretation of the derived data.

Note that it is possible to go back and revisit filters at any point, modifying your response to assess the impact on tool compliance.

The second output is a prioritised listing of the 34 approaches. This list is dynamically sorted using the average compliance score for each approach so that the likely optimal approaches are at the top of the list, and the less appropriate approaches are towards the bottom. Again, the list is colour-coded to aid interpretation: currently, those approaches that have an average compliance for a given (user) need or (approach) requirement in excess of 66% are shaded green; those in the 33-66% range are shaded orange; and those below 33% are shaded red.

Through these two outputs, the user is provided not only with a clear insight into which approach(es) are likely to provide optimal support to practical EBM in their LS, but also an insight into the specific areas of relative strength or weakness of each approach relative to the specific conditions surrounding its use within the LS.

Factsheets of the tools provide the user with additional information (as narratives) about the tool(s) selected so that they can make decisions about how to best proceed with the application, while being

aware of the tool's strengths, weaknesses and limitations (these factsheets are presented in this report as Appendix 1).

Using questions with pre-defined, standardised answers that characterise the condition under which the user wants to implement an EBA was considered the best approach to develop the filters for the DST interface, and these closed responses largely mirrored the information collected through the online survey. In general terms, open-text answers or other forms of corollary information about the tool that were collected through the online survey were not deemed to be suitable for use as potential filters. However, such survey responses may contain important information about the tool and its use, which the user needs to be aware of before proceeding with the tool implementation (e.g., its limitations and strengths, whether other tools are required, and relevant references and links). This information (and other information about the tool as captured by the survey questionnaire) is therefore provided as a series of PDF factsheets that are linked to the tool(s) (see Appendix 1). These factsheets are available directly from the SEA4SGES tool, each embedded (as clickable PDF 'objects') on the 'Results - list & factsheets' tab of the SEAS4GES tool.

The additional information summarised as narratives in the factsheets includes, for example:

- Whether the tool requires the use of other tools in combination to deliver on the EBM element (based on responses to Q6 in the online survey questionnaire);
- How the tool is commonly used, by whom and whether it is relevant for marine governance (based on responses to Q7-Q8 in the online survey questionnaire);
- Which specific components of the DAPSI(W)R(M) categories are covered by the tool (e.g., specific activities, pressures, species groups, etc.) (based on responses to Q9a in the online survey questionnaire) and the specific data used for them (based on responses to Q14a-c in the online survey questionnaire) - (this is specifically relevant to subtask 2.3.3);
- What specific resources (if any) are required (e.g., software) and associated sources of information (references/links) (based on responses to Q16-Q17 in the online survey questionnaire);
- What the possible limitations of the tools are, in terms of assumptions affecting applicability, potential barriers and ways to overcome them (based on responses to Q18-19 in the online survey questionnaire);
- What the main strengths and weaknesses of the tool are (based on responses to Q22 in the online survey questionnaire).

The factsheet narratives also indicate the variability of responses for a tool, where replicate data were available, and references and links, where provided by the respondents. For the benefit of the LSs,

links with the tools being developed in other WPs and associated capacity-building activities and resources developed in GES4SEAS are also mapped in the factsheets.

5.3 Results

A total of 63 questionnaire returns were received from 45 respondents. The returns provided full coverage of all the 19 tool groups considered, with an additional tool group, 'Size spectrum models', also being identified.

Almost all tools were assessed at the generic tool group level, with additional assessments for specific tools for some groups. The only exceptions were 'Semi-quantitative mental models' and 'Food web models', for which the responses characterised only specific tools rather than the tool group in general (namely Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling developed in Mental Modeler, and Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE), respectively). These specific tools will likely be the most common representative tools of the group as used by researchers.

When responses for specific tools were differentiated from those for the generic tool group they belong to, a total of 34 unique tools were identified. Table 7 shows the list of unique tools, numbered from 1 to 19 according to the original list of tool groups (see D2.1), with the decimal digit denoting the generic tool group (.0) or a specific tool within the group (.1, .2, etc).

In total, 83% of responses (52 out of 63) were provided by people who were experts on the tool (i.e., they have used the tool and are proficient with its operation, and/or they have been directly involved in the approach or tool's design and/or development; 30 responses) or very familiar with it (i.e., they have experience of using the tool and understand its operation; 22 responses) (Table 7). An additional 13% (8 responses) were provided by people familiar with the tool (i.e., they have used the tool but only 'at arm's length' and have not been too engaged in the detail of its operation). Only 3 responses were provided by people with low familiarity with the tool (i.e., they have heard of the approach but have not used it themselves and are not really aware of its application). A decision was made to ignore these latter data, also considering that other responses with higher confidence (familiarity level) were available for these tools (Table 7).

The tools that received most survey responses were the generic tool group 'Cumulative impact spatial mapping (e.g., Halpern et al., 2008)', which received the highest number of responses (7), followed by generic tool groups 'Simple assessment index (e.g., M-AMBI)' and 'Overarching assessment tools (e.g., NEAT, OHI)' (4 responses each), and most often at the expert level hence with higher confidence (Table 7). This is likely a reflection of the predominant expertise most relevant to the GES4SEAS project.

Most of the other tools (27) received one or two responses. However, it is emphasised that the confidence in the tool assessment should take into consideration not only the number of responses but also the level of expertise of the respondent. The majority of the tools that received only one or two responses were assessed by respondents with high level of knowledge of the tools (experts or very familiar), thus increasing the confidence on the response received. Indeed, 94% of the tools overall received at least one survey response at the ‘expert’ (21 tools) or ‘very familiar’ level (11 tools). Only two tools (the generic tool ‘Single species models’ and the specific tool ‘Biogeochemical models: DCPM box model’) were assessed by respondents which were, at best, only ‘familiar’ with the tool, and therefore, the information obtained for these tools carries lower confidence.

Such confidence can be summarised as a value calculated as the number of responses obtained for a tool, weighted by the level of expertise of the respondent (with weights of 1 for ‘expert’, 0.5 for ‘very familiar’, 0.1 for ‘familiar’; responses with low familiarity were excluded from the analysis). This confidence score, expressed as % of the maximum value recorded for the tools (value of 6 for the generic tool ‘Cumulative impact spatial mapping’), is reported in Table 7.

Table 7. Unique tools assessed (including generic tool groups and specific tools within) and the level of familiarity of respondents (indicator of confidence). Values in the table are number of responses received by familiarity level and in total. The confidence score (as % of the maximum confidence recorded across the tools) is also provided in the last column, accounting for both the number of responses received and the familiarity level of the respondents.

	Tool unique # and Name	Expert	Very familiar	Familiar	Low	Total	Confid. %
1.0	Conceptual models (generic)	1				1	17%
1.1	Conceptual models: MAMBO	1				1	17%
2.1	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping: Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler		3			3	25%
3.0	Knowledge Graphs (generic)		1		1	2	8%
3.1	Knowledge Graphs (KG): EAD DAPSI(W)R(M) KG	1				1	17%
4.0	BBN probabilistic models (generic)	1				1	17%
5.0	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic)	1				1	17%
5.1	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability: Bow tie analysis	2				2	33%
6.0	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (e.g., Halpern et al., 2008) (generic)	5	2			7	100%
6.1	Cumulative impact spatial: CIMPAL - cumulative impact of invasive alien species	1				1	17%
6.2	Cumulative impact spatial mapping: PlanWise4Blue		1			1	8%

	Tool unique # and Name	Expert	Very familiar	Familiar	Low	Total	Confid. %
7.0	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic)	2		1		3	35%
7.1	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: SCAIRM	1				1	17%
7.2	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: ODEMM	1	1			2	25%
7.3	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: Aquacross		1			1	8%
7.4	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: ICES/Mission Atlantic variation	1				1	17%
8.0	Single species models (e.g., life cycle, stock assessment) (generic)			2	1	3	3%
9.0	Biogeochemical models (generic)	1				1	17%
9.1	Biogeochemical models: DCPM box model, and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR			1		1	2%
10.1	Food web models: Ecopath with Ecosim		1	2		3	12%
11.0	Ecosystem models (e.g., End2End) (generic)	1				1	17%
12.0	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution) (generic)	1	1			2	25%
13.0	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic)		1	1		2	10%
13.1	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation: Ocean Accounts	1				1	17%
14.0	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic)		1			1	8%
15.0	Spatial planning models and tools (e.g., GIS, VAPEM, related to use) (generic)		1			1	8%
15.1	Spatial planning models and tools: GIS		1			1	8%
16.0	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic)		1			1	8%
16.1	Systematic conservation planning tools: MARXAN family tools		2			2	17%
17.0	Simple assessment index (e.g., M-AMBI) (generic)	2	1		1	4	42%
18.0	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (e.g., HEAT, BEAT, CHASE) (generic)	1	1			2	25%
19.0	Overarching assessment tools (e.g., NEAT, OHI) (generic)	2	2			4	50%
19.1	Overarching assessment tools: NEAT	2		1		3	35%
20.0	Size spectrum models (generic)	1				1	17%
	Grand Total	30	22	8	3	63	

The detailed data obtained for each tool from the questionnaire returns are given in the tool-specific factsheets produced as part of the DST (Appendix 1). The main patterns in the data were explored in relation to the key questions of interest (see Section 5.2.2) through a frequency analysis. The results are outlined below.

It is emphasised that the results below reflect the experts' views as represented by their responses in the online survey. In addition, not all tools were assessed at the expert level, and, therefore, the results for some tools are to be considered with a lower level of confidence, including single species models (#8) and specific biogeochemical models (#9.1) (only familiar respondents), followed by food web models (#10.1) and generic natural capital accounting and ecosystem services valuation (#13) (mix of familiar and very familiar respondents), and by fuzzy cognitive models (#2.1), generic knowledge graphs (#3), specific cumulative impact spatial mapping (PlanWise4Blue #6.2) and impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (Aquacross #7.3), bio- and socio-economic models (#14), spatial planning tools (generic #15 and GIS #15.1), and systematic conservation planning tools (generic #16 and MARXAN #16.1) (only very familiar respondents but no experts) (Table 7).

5.3.1 Tool ability to address EBM elements

The list of EBM elements (and their respective identification code) considered in this study is given in Table 8.

The assessment of activities-pressures footprints (EBM7), of single MSFD Descriptors or single issues (EBM10; e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs), of the state change of single species or ecosystem components (EBM11), and of threatened habitats and species (EBM12), also in the context of the Birds and Habitats Directives (EBM18.2) are the EBM elements and applications most frequently addressed by the tools assessed here (28 out of 34 unique tools, 82%) (Figure 14). In turn, fewer tools (21-22 out of 34) are able to address whole ecosystem assessments (EBM3), special biotic effects/impacts (EBM5), climate change (EBM13) and uncertainty (EBM16).

A total of 8 tools have been reported to currently be able to address all the 20 EBM elements and applications considered (Figure 14). These are: Conceptual models (generic, unique tool #1), Risk-based approaches assessing exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic, #5), Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic, #6), Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic, #7), Food web models (EwE, #10.1), Overarching assessment tools (generically, #19 and specifically as NEAT, #19.1). Single species models (generic, #8) were also reported as able to address all 20 EBM

elements, although lower confidence is assigned to this result. However, most of these tools are not able to fully deliver the EBM elements.

Table 8. Identification (ID#) and name of Ecosystem-Based Management elements considered in this study.

ID#	Ecosystem-Based Management element Name
EBM1	Cumulative effects assessments - CEA
EBM2	Good Environmental Status Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) assessments
EBM3	Whole ecosystem assessments
EBM4	Ecosystem Services (delivery, impacts, valuation)
EBM5	Special biotic effects/impacts
EBM6	Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions)
EBM7	Activities-Pressures footprint
EBM8	Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints)
EBM9	Links activities pressures impacts
EBM10	Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs)
EBM11	Single species, ecosystem Components State change
EBM12	Threatened habitats and species
EBM13	Climate change
EBM14	Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation
EBM15	Spatial and other measures
EBM16	Uncertainty
EBM17	Risks
EBM18.1	Other policy requirements – Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
EBM18.2	Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives
EBM18.3	Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy

Figure 14. Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) elements addressed by the tools assessed, currently (block colour) and potentially (after further development and adaptation; patterned colours). See text, Tables 7 and 8 for the names of the tools and EBM elements corresponding to the ID# in the figure.

Here below are some examples of the reasons provided by the respondents of the survey (paraphrased):

- Conceptual models (#1) are the starting point for most other tools, but they only provide a conceptual mapping of the problem (e.g., cause-effect relationships), but other tools are needed for quantifying the concepts represented.
- Cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6) assesses potential activity-pressure effects, but it does not allow to determine the status and distance-to-target or confidence, nor to identify tipping points and set up thresholds of pressures resulting from multiple activities. This tool also relies on other tools to provide spatial information and incorporate a risk-based approach (e.g., GIS, Species Distribution Modelling, Statistical Modelling; see Stelzenmüller et al. (2018) for a

review of used tools), and on monitored state/impact data to assess the accuracy of the predicted impact maps.

- The NEAT tool (#19.1) does not establish explicit activity-pressure, pressure-impacts, impacts-Ecosystem Services links, so “conclusions can be reached, but not explicitly”.
- Impact risk ranking (#7) through linkage-chain-frameworks are tools for gross risk identification (e.g., hot spots of risk through the overlap of components' presence with activities/pressures). Several tools in this group (e.g., ODEMM, Aquacross) are based on a semi-quantitative approach that can then be used with specific modelling tools in context. However, recent developments (e.g., SCAIRM; Piet et al., 2021, submitted; Coll et al., 2023 (GES4SEAS Deliverable 3.1)) have made it possible to express impact risk as a quantifiable concept representing a state change expressed as a relative change in equilibrium abundance of the ecosystem component (e.g., species or, in the case of habitats, the associated biota) compared to an undisturbed situation. This can be assessed using expert judgement, semi-quantitative and/or quantitative information (#7.1).
- Food web models (#10.1), and other marine ecosystem models (MEMs), have been historically mostly used to address fishery-related issues in EBM (e.g., fishing activity - pressure - state links, individual fish stock assessment), but their applications with a spatial perspective have extended their applications to the evaluation of marine protected areas and spatial management measures in general (de Mutser et al., 2023) and the impacts of cumulative impacts including human induced climate change (Stock et al., 2023). Depending on the link between the driver and the ecosystem element, functional relationships are inputs of the EwE models (e.g., climate change effect on recruitment). An example in such a direction is provided by Scotti et al. (2022) where the authors consider the impact of warming on the recruitment of western Baltic cod, western Baltic Spring-spawning herring and sprat in the western Baltic Sea.

The only tool of the eight listed above that was consistently reported to be able to deliver all the EBM elements in full was marine ecosystem modelling, with the example of food web models using EwE as the main application, albeit with the caveat that these are models that can need important amounts of data if applied in their full spatial-temporal capacity.

Bow-tie analysis (a specific tool within the group of risk-based approaches assessing exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability, #5.1), MARXAN family tools (as part of systematic conservation planning tools, #16.1) and ecosystem models (generic, #11) were also identified as potentially being able to address the full set of EBM elements in the future, although they already address 19 out of the 20 EBM elements currently. The improvements would allow uncertainty (EBM16) to be also addressed by tool #5.1, risks (EBM17) by tool #16.1 and requirements of the MSPD (EBM18.1) by tool #11 (Figure 14). The PlanWise4Blue tool for cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6.1), currently addressing 16 EBM elements, was also indicated as potentially addressing all EBM elements after further development,

with the future addition of whole ecosystem assessments (EBM3), climate change (EBM13), and additional policy requirements such as Birds and Habitat Directives (EBM18.2) and Biodiversity Strategy (EBM18.3).

Several other tools were reported to currently address a variable proportion of the EBM elements considered (see Figure 14). Only the MAMBO conceptual model (Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms, #1.1), BBN probabilistic models (generic, #4) and Size spectrum models (generic, #20) were not considered to be able to deliver any of the EBM elements in their current status. However, with further development and adaptation, they might address 7-8 EBM elements, e.g., GES MSFD assessments (EBM2) and Links activities pressures impacts (EBM9) by all three tools; Cumulative effects assessments by BBN models, the assessment of single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) by MAMBO and BBN models) (Figure 14). Considering the additional comments provided by the respondents, it is believed that the results on the current capability of these tools are just a reflection of the fact that these models are either under development/testing (MAMBO) or need to be tailored to the specific analysis (e.g., complex relationships in BBN) and this would affect which EBM elements the tool may address.

The EBM elements at the core of GES4SEAS, namely the MSFD GES assessment (EBM2) and the cumulative effects assessment (EBM1), are delivered by 27 tools out of the 34 unique tools assessed (Figure 14). Among the tools that were reported not to currently address EBM1, there are the conceptual model MAMBO (#1.1) and specific knowledge graphs (#3.1), species distribution models (#12), natural capital accounting and ecosystem services valuation (#13 and #13.1), bio- and socio-economic models (#14), size spectrum models (#20), as well as BBN probabilistic models (#4) and specific biogeochemical models (DCPM box model, also biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR; #9.1). However, the latter two tools were considered to be potentially able to address cumulative effects assessment after further development in the future. Most of the tools mentioned above (#1.1, #3.1, #4, #12, #13, #14, #20) were also reported not to currently address EBM2, with the addition of generic knowledge graphs (#3) and systematic conservation planning tools (#16). However, the potential to address MSFD GES assessments in the future, after further development, was indicated for MAMBO (#1.1), BBN models (#4) and size spectrum models (#20). Of the tools reported to address both MSFD GES assessment (EBM2) and the cumulative effects assessment (EBM1), the PlanWise4Blue tool for cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6.2), descriptors or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic, including, e.g., HEAT, BEAT, CHASE, #18), overarching assessment tools (generic, including, e.g., NEAT, OHI; #19), ecosystem models (generic; #11) and spatial planning tools (generic, including e.g., GIS,

VAPEM; #15) were amongst the tools reported to be able to fully deliver against the EBM elements selected for them.

5.3.2 Data requirements for DAPSI(W)R(M) components

The tools were assessed in relation to the DAPSI(W)R(M) components they use as input or output variables. In this assessment, Drivers were not considered (unless specified by the respondent) and therefore, when “all DAPSI(W)R(M) components” are mentioned in the results below, this only refers to Activities, Pressures, the State of eco-components (e.g., species or species groups, habitat) and ecosystem services provision, the Impacts on welfare (as supply of societal goods and services) and Responses and management measures.

Overall, all the DAPSI(W)R(M) components are included in the assessments undertaken by the tools, either as inputs and/or outputs and most often represented by multiple variables in a tool (Figure 15). Activities, pressures and their effect on the state of eco-components are most often used as input by the tools, while the effects on ecosystem services and responses as management measures are most frequently provided as outputs (Figure 15). In addition, some tools (e.g., specific applications of Knowledge Graphs (tool #3.1), Natural capital accounting (#13, #13.1), bioeconomic/socioeconomic models (#14)) may also require evidence on the Drivers (human needs and wants) that lead to the activities.

Figure 15. DAPSI(W)R(M) components used by the assessed tools as input (left) or output (right), as single or multiple variables (ES = ecosystem services; SG&B = societal goods & benefits). The % represents the overall relative frequency of use of a DAPSI(W)R(M) component across all 34 tools.

Only 38% of the assessed tools (13 out of the 34) individually use input data for all the DAPSI(W)R(M) components, but this percentage increases to 76% (26 tools) when input data for only activities,

pressures and their effect on the state of eco-components are considered (Table 9). In general, conceptual models (tool #1) can use input on any DAPSI(W)R(M) component, although this may vary with the specific application (e.g., MAMBO (#1.1) only uses input data on activities and species state). Other tools that can use all DAPSI(W)R(M) components as input include fuzzy cognitive models (#2.1), knowledge graphs (#3 and #3.1), risk-based approaches assessing exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic #5 and Bow-tie #5.1), food web models (EwE #10.1), natural capital accounting and ecosystem services valuation (generic #13). Cumulative impact spatial mapping, impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks and overarching assessment tools also include all DAPSI(W)R(M) components as input, in general (tools #6, #7 and #18, respectively) and for some of their specific applications (PlanWise4Blue #6.2 and Aquacross #7.3), but not for all (Table 9). CIMPAL (cumulative impact of invasive alien species, #6.1) does not use input data on ecosystem services, societal goods & benefits and response measures (but it provides outputs on response measures). NEAT (a specific application of overarching assessment tools, #19.1) does not use input data on societal goods & benefits, nor SCAIRM, ODEMM and the ICES/Mission Atlantic variation tools do (#7.1, #7.2 and #7.3). The latter tool also does not use data on ecosystem services and response measures. In turn, tools like generic bio-/socio-economic and societal goods and benefits valuation (#14) only require input data for societal goods and benefits, while biogeochemical models (#9 and #9.1) only for pressures and the effects on the state of eco-components (species or species groups) (Table 9).

Table 9. DAPSI(W)R(M) components used as input by the individual tools. Column headings: A= activities; P = Pressures, S = effects on the state of species (spp), habitats (hab) or ecosystem services (ES); I = Impact on welfare (societal goods & benefits, SG&B); R = response and management measures. Values in the table indicate use as single (1) or multiple variables (2). No use is marked by dark grey cells.

Tool Unique Name	Tool unique#	A	P	S spp	S hab	S ES	I G&B	R
Conceptual models (generic)	1.0	2	2	1	2	2	2	2
Conceptual models: MAMBO	1.1	1		1				
Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping: Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM)	2.1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Knowledge Graphs (generic)	3.0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Knowledge Graphs: proprietary system built for EAD	3.1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
BBN probabilistic models (generic)	4.0	2	2	2	2			
Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic)	5.0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability: Bow-tie analysis	5.1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Cumulative impact spatial mapping (e.g., Halpern et al. 2008) (generic)	6.0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Tool Unique Name	Tool unique#	A	P	S spp	S hab	S ES	I G&B	R
Cumulative impact spatial: CIMPAL - cumulative impact of invasive alien species	6.1	2	1	2	2			
Cumulative impact spatial mapping: PlanWise4Blue	6.2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1
Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic)	7.0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: SCAIRM	7.1	2	2	2	2	2		2
Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: ODEMM	7.2	2	2	2	2	2		2
Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: Aquacross	7.3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks: ICES/Mission Atlantic variation	7.4	2	2	2	2			
Single species models (e.g., life cycle, stock assessment) (generic)	8.0	2	2	2		2	2	2
Biogeochemical models (generic)	9.0		2	2				
Biogeochemical models: DCPM box model, and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR	9.1		1	2				
Food web models: Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE)	10.1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Ecosystem models (e.g., End2End) (generic)	11.0	2	2	2	2			2
Habitat suitability / species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution) (generic)	12.0	2	2	1	2			
Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic)	13.0	1	2	1	1	2	2	2
Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation: Ocean Accounts	13.1	1		1	1			
Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic)	14.0						2	
Spatial planning models (e.g., GIS, VAPEM, related to use) (generic)	15.0	2	2	2	2			2
Spatial planning models: GIS	15.1	2	2	2	2			2
Systematic conservation planning tools (generic)	16.0	2	2	2	2	2	2	
Systematic conservation planning tools: MARXAN family tools	16.1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
Simple assessment index (e.g., M-AMBI) (generic)	17.0	2	2	2	2			2
Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (e.g., HEAT, BEAT, CHASE) (generic)	18.0		1	2	2	2		2
Overarching assessment tools (e.g., NEAT, OHI) (generic)	19.0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Overarching assessment tools: NEAT	19.1	2	2	2	2	1		2
Size spectrum models (generic)	20.0		1					

Information was gathered from the online survey to provide guidance on the data requirements for the different DAPSI(W)R(M) components. This is summarised in Table 10, with an indication of what data are required across the different tools and their type (as quantitative, semi-quantitative, or qualitative), as per respondents' input, and the DAPSI(W)R(M) components they characterise.

There are only a few tools that have strict requirements for quantitative data, namely biogeochemical models (#9 and #9.1), specific applications of natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (Ocean Accounts #13.1) and size spectrum models (#20). Quantitative data may potentially inform any tool, even when they are used to derive qualitative or semi-quantitative variables as needed by the model (e.g., conceptual models (#1), fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1), the ICES/Mission Atlantic variation of impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7.4)). Indeed, most tools may use a combination of quantitative, semi-quantitative or qualitative input data to characterise the different DAPSI(W)R(M) components (Table 10). In some cases, although quantitative data may be preferred (e.g., for cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6)), they are not essential, and, where not available, semi-quantitative or qualitative data may be used instead (e.g., all quantitative inputs in cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6) may be replaced by the use of indices or scores on a Likert scaling; the quantitative valuation of specific Activity-Pressure-Ecosystem component chain or ecosystem services in impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7, #7.1) may be replaced by the use of semi-quantitative data (scores, categories) from expert-based assessment; habitat distribution models (#12) may be calibrated based on species presence/absence, if abundance data are not available). This, however, may be at the expense of the detail/quality of the resulting outputs. Many tools are also able to use expert judgment in place of data, the exceptions being: CIMPAL (cumulative impact of invasive alien species, #6.1), single species models (#8), biogeochemical models (#9 and #9.1), species distribution models (#12), simple assessment index (#17), descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (#18), overarching assessment tools (#19 and 19.1) and size spectrum models (#20).

Table 10. Data requirements for DAPSI(W)R(M) components to be used as input by the assessed tools. Column headings: DAPSI(W)R(M): A= activities; P = Pressures, S =effects on the state of eco-components (eco) or ecosystem services (ES); I = Impact on welfare (societal goods & benefits, SG&B); R = response and management measures. Data type: Quant = quantitative; semi-quant = semi-quantitative; qual = qualitative. The tools for which each variable was reported by respondents are indicated by their unique #.

Data requirements (variables indicated by respondents)	DAPSI(W)R(M)						Data type			Tool unique #
	A	P	S eco	S ES	I	R	quant	semi-quant	qual	
Distribution (presence/absence) of activities (e.g., port).	x						(x)	(x)	x	#1 #3 #3.1 #5.1 #7.1 #7.2 #7.3 #7.4 #15.1 #16 #16.1

Data requirements (variables indicated by respondents)	DAPSI(W)R(M)						Data type			Tool unique #
	A	P	S eco	S ES	I	R	quant	semi-quant	qual	
Frequencies of activities.	x						x	x	x	#5 #5.1 #7.4
Indices of the intensity of human activities, e.g., in a Likert scale (e.g., low/medium/high fishing effort).	x							x	x	#5.1 #16
Maps and temporal data (occurrence, frequency, effort).	x	x	x				(x)	x	x	#5.1 #7.4
Distribution (presence/absence) of pressures.		x					(x)	(x)	x	#1 #3 #3.1 #5.1 #6.2 #7.1 #7.2 #7.3
Pressure intensity in space (and time) (as quantitative data).		x					x	x	x	#5 #5.1 #6 #6.2 #7.1 #7.3
Pressure data in terms of concentrations of chemicals or abundance of species. For indicators, annual means plus target values are usually needed.		x	x				x			#18
Pressure data in terms of categorised pressure levels of chemicals or abundance of species (semi-quant.) or presence/absence (qual.).		x	x					x	x	#18
Nutrient concentration.		x					x			#1.1 #9 #9.1
Area coverage of the algal bloom.		x						x		#1.1
Species pathways of introduction.		x							x	#6.1
Fishery landings and catches (by metier, season).		x					x			#8
Fishery survey indices (in the absence of catch data).		x						x		#8
Biota mortality, pollutant concentrations, nutrient concentrations. Indicator values and standard errors, e.g., temporal data; spatial area. Preferably long-time data series.		x					x			#19.1
Pressures on populations in the form of changes in mortality or respiration rate.		x					x			#20
Activity/Pressure footprint.	x	x						x		#7.2
Distribution of activities and pressures, and potentially their intensity, risk.	x	x					(x)	(x)	x	#7.1 #7.3 #15 #15.1
Metrics of activities/pressures (e.g., actual fishing effort per grid cell, level of disturbance by towed gears).	x	x					x			#16
Time series of fishing effort, mortality.	x	x								#10.1
Maps and temporal data (occurrence, frequency, effort).	x	x	x				(x)	x	x	#7.4
Distribution (presence/absence) of eco-components (species or habitats); Geo-referenced species occurrence.			x				(x)	(x)	x	#1 #1.1 #3 #3.1 #5.1 #6 #6.1 #7.1 #7.2 #7.3 #15.1
Species presence-absence.			x						x	#5.1 #17

Data requirements (variables indicated by respondents)	DAPSI(W)R(M)						Data type			Tool unique #
	A	P	S eco	S ES	I	R	quant	semi-quant	qual	
Occurrence of habitats and threatened species from surveys and observation notes.			x						x	#5.1 #19.1
Ecosystem components - semi-quantitative estimates, e.g., indices of species abundance, Likert scale (e.g., low/medium/high abundance).			x					x	(x)	#5.1 #6 #15.1 #16
Species and seagrass distribution as approximate measurements assigned to data using a biotic index.			x					x		#19.1
Ecosystem components (quantitative estimates, e.g., species densities, abundance).			x				x	x	x	#5.1 #6 #16
Numbers or biomass of each biological component of the model (typically biomass pools for invertebrates and abundance at age for vertebrates) - which might be species or functional group of taxonomic resolution.			x				x	(x)		#11
Species abundance distribution data (density, catches, sightings, etc.) from monitoring. Species abundance could be represented in a semiquantitative way (e.g., on a discrete scale/score), but it is unusual. Species distribution (presence/absence) from monitoring, if no abundance data are available.			x				x	(x)	x	#7.1 #7.3 #12
Species abundance, species potential distribution (from models).			x				x			#7.1 #7.3 #15.1
Species abundance, biomass, biovolume, age distribution, species count, body size, arrivals.			x				x			#17
Biota biomass (mean and standard errors for, e.g., temporal data, spatial area, preferably long time data series).			x				x			#19.1
Phytoplankton counts.			x				x			#1.1
Species-specific dispersion radius.			x				x			#6.1
Species abundance in the initial year.			x				x			#10.1
Fishery-independent data (abundance, biomass, size, maturity).			x				x			#8
Time series of fish abundance.			x							#10.1
Biological data (growth, asymptotic length, etc.).			x				x			#8
Species diet matrices.			x				x	x		#10.1
Map of [seabed] bottom type.			x				x	(x)		#11
Habitat area/extent/coverage.			x				x			#7.1 #7.3 #15.1 #16
Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions.			x				x	x	x	#6.2
Environmental data layers (oceanographic, topographic, geomorphologic, etc., variables).			x				x			#12

Data requirements (variables indicated by respondents)	DAPSI(W)R(M)						Data type			Tool unique #
	A	P	S eco	S ES	I	R	quant	semi-quant	qual	
Environmental data - e.g., tides, residence time, riverine flows, Chlorophyll a, opportunistic algae, catchment size or area.			x				x			#9 #9.1
Environmental data - salinity; salinity gradients.			x				x			#1.1 #9.1
Time series of hydrodynamic flows and physical environmental state (temperature, salinity, etc.).			x				x	(x)		#11
Time series of oceanographic conditions.			x							#10.1
Sensitivity of eco-components to pressures (e.g., minimal/minor/moderate/major/massive vulnerability, presence/absence).		x	x				(x)	x	x	#6
Species-habitat specific impacts weights (sensitivity to pressures).		x	x				(x)	x		#6.1
Dose-effect relations, specific recovery durations, etc., to assess the effect potential.		x	x				x	x	x	#7.1
Semi-quantitative data for indicators (e.g., nutrients) defined based on Risk-based approaches.		x	x					x		#19
Observation Notes, Semi-structured interviews, Concept Maps, Case Studies. Qualitative data are typically transferred to a quantitative scale using some assumptions.		x	x						(x)	#19
Delivery (presence/absence) of ES.				x			(x)	(x)	x	#1 #3 #3.1
Habitat extent, geography and condition. Where possible, both spatial and temporal data to provide the best outputs.			x	x			x			#13.1 #14
Full distribution of features (e.g., species, habitat, process, cultural site, etc.) targeted for protection expressed as continuous values (e.g., species population, model outputs, indicators, proxies) based on field data or derived from expert judgment where data are not available.			x	x			x	x	x	#16.1
Spatio-temporal data of GES criteria, activities or pressures are needed for spatial explicit assessments of effects and future change.	x	x	x				x			#4
Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually by informing a scale, risk, impact or condition score).	x	x	x				(x)	x	x	#7.4
Delivery (presence/absence) of SG&B.					x		(x)	(x)	x	#1 #3 #3.1
Prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services (or semi-quantitative or qualitative value for some of the societal benefits that are not amenable to monetary valuation). Where possible, both spatial and temporal data to provide the best outputs.					x		x	x	x	#13 #13.1 #14

Data requirements (variables indicated by respondents)	DAPSI(W)R(M)						Data type			Tool unique #
	A	P	S eco	S ES	I	R	quant	semi-quant	qual	
Contribution of human activities to GDP.					x		x			#16
Presence/absence of response/management measures.						x	(x)	(x)	x	#1 #3 #3.1 #5.1
Number of response measures that are available and any quantitative conditions for those responses.						x	x	x		#5.1
Numerical conservation targets for each feature targeted for protection.						x	x			#16.1
Opportunity cost or action-based cost.					x	x	x			#16.1
Pressures and management costs expressed in relevant units (e.g., fishing effort) or as distance/area-based costs.		x			x	x	x	x		#16.1
Cause-effect relationships - probabilities of effects.	x	x	x				x	x	x	#5
Any quantitative data available for any activity, pressure and state/impact, although not strictly required (gross estimates will work).	x	x	x	x			(x)	x	x	#7
Importance of component (Likert scaling).	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	(x)	x	#2.1
Relationships between factors (Likert scaling).	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	(x)	x	#2.1
Probability distribution.	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	#4
Interaction effects and impacts.	x	x	x						x	#7.2
The specific Activity-Pressure-Ecosystem component chain characterisation, or Ecosystem services expert-based valuation.	x	x	x	x	x	x		x		#7
Links between components - identification, occurrence.	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)		x	#5.1 #7
Links between components - indicators of importance, e.g., resulting pressures, state change, etc.	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			#5.1 #7

5.3.3 Spatial and temporal scales

As seen in Table 10, the assessed tools may use spatial and/or temporal data (e.g., spatial distribution maps, time series). Some tools undertake spatial or temporal assessments, and therefore, they require this type of data, while others can use them, but they are not necessary.

Tools that perform spatial assessments providing spatially resolved outputs require spatially explicit data (e.g., the spatial distribution of the ecological features of interest, environment data, and pressures). These tools include, for example, species distribution models (#12), spatial planning models (#15), systematic conservation planning tools (#16, including MARXAN 16), cumulative impact spatial mapping tools (#6, #6.1 and #6.2), food web models (#10.1, when EwE is implemented with its spatial-temporal module Ecospace), marine ecosystem models in general (#11), and overarching

assessment tools (#19, but depending on the specific tool; e.g., OHI does require spatial input, while NEAT needs data that are referred to a spatial assessment unit for which the tool is applied but it does not need these data to be spatially resolved within the area).

Some of the tools above also provide temporal assessments, and, as such, also require the input of time series data. For example, the output of ecosystem (end-to-end) models (#11) is a 3D spatially resolved time series for each model variable. Food web models (#10.1, where Ecopath is used with Ecosim) explicitly use time series as inputs (e.g., catch rates, biomass of components, etc.) and can then output modelled trends. NEAT (#19.1) requires temporal data to produce indicators with associated standard error, and, although they do not produce time series as outputs, the combination of multiple outputs (referred to different specific time periods, e.g., years) may be used for temporal assessment. The same is valid for species distribution models (#12).

Some tools only provide temporal assessments, such as single species models (#8; the tool may use spatially explicit information, but the assessment is not spatial and only temporal outputs are provided) and size spectrum models (#20).

Some tools do not require or produce spatially or temporally resolved inputs/outputs (e.g., conceptual models (#1), fuzzy cognitive models (#2.1), knowledge graphs (#3, #3.1), BBN probabilistic models (#4), risk-based approaches such as Bow-tie analysis (#5.1)), even though spatial or temporal input data may be used (e.g., #4, #5.1, Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks #7). For example, impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks such as ODEMM (#7.2) may consider some spatial or temporal distributions of data to inform the reasoning behind the assessment. However, the assessment is for the whole area and period of time as a unit, although the tool is apparently being developed to address quantitative spatial and temporal aspects (Defra-funded ASPri programme).

Where spatial assessments are undertaken, most of the tools are able to assess at multiple scales, the ones most frequently represented being between site level and regional scale (up to 100,000 km²), whereas assessments at the larger European scales are less frequent (Figure 16). Generic risk-based approaches (#5), specific biogeochemical models (#9.1) and ecosystem models (#11) are the only tools for which assessments were reported to focus only on a few of the smaller spatial scales (#5: site, local and national; #9.1: local and regional; #11: local and national).

As for temporal scales, most of the tools are able to assess at multiple scales; the ones most frequently represented being short-medium and medium-long term (i.e., between one individual year and multiple years within a decade), whereas assessment on short and long terms are less frequent (Figure 16). The only tools for which assessments were reported to focus only on a few of the temporal scales

were the generic simple assessment indices (#7: short to short-medium term), specific biogeochemical models (#9.1) and descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (#18) (both: short-medium to medium-long term) and single species models (#8) and size spectrum models (#20) (both: medium-long to long term).

Figure 16. Frequency of spatial scales (left) and temporal scales (right) of the assessments undertaken by the tools. Whether the individual scale is assessed on its own by a tool, or in combination with 1, 2 or more other scales is also shown. Spatial scales: Site level (e.g., < 10 km²), Local (e.g., 10-100 km²), National (e.g., 100-10,000 km²), Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 km²), European (e.g., > 100,000 km²). Temporal scales: Short-term (e.g., seasonal), Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year), Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years), Long-term (e.g., > 10 years).

5.3.4 Tool uses

The assessed tools are most frequently used within national governments (for national reporting, e.g., of Fisheries Management Plans, and relevant competent authorities) and for EU project work, followed by the use within Regional Sea Conventions, ICES Working Groups and EU Technical Expert Groups (Figure 17). An individual tool is most often used for a combination of these different uses. The use for official MSFD reporting, often associated with EEA assessments, is limited to fewer tools, namely cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic (#6) and as specific tool PlanWise4Blue (#6.2)), single species models (#8), species distribution models (#12), spatial planning models (#15 and #15.1), simple assessment indices (#17), descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (e.g., HEAT, BEAT, CHASE; #18) and overarching assessment tools (e.g., NEAT, OHI; #19).

Figure 17. Frequency of uses for the assessed tools. Blue lines at the bottom indicate the most frequent (from top to bottom) combinations of uses for an individual tool.

Almost all tools have been reported as relevant to marine governance, the only exception being BBN probabilistic models (#4). However, it might be argued that, where developed to address environmental management problems, the probabilistic representation of correlative and causal relationships that BBNs provide is likely to constitute valuable supporting evidence for policy development and decision-making (even if this was not the direct experience of the expert who provided the response for this tool).

Considering their role in marine governance, the tools are most frequently used to inform decision-making and to track progress (e.g., against action plans), followed by the design of remediation and management measures (in some cases being specifically used to analyse, evaluate and implement the most appropriate measures, as for risk-based approaches such as Bow-tie (#5.1)) (Figure 18). Less frequent roles are in the design of monitoring programmes, the development or setting of targets or MSFD thresholds, and policy development (including providing supporting evidence). Additional roles were identified in assessing the effectiveness of PoM or the development of pressure indicators for cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6) or assessing the achievement of overarching policy goals (in particular in the Common Fisheries Policy and as elements of the MSFD D3 (commercial species) assessment for criteria D3C1 (fishing mortality rates) and D3C2 (spawning stock biomass)) for single species models (#8).

Figure 18. Frequency of roles of the assessed tools in marine governance. Blue lines at the bottom indicate the most frequent (from top to bottom) combinations of roles for an individual tool.

5.3.5 Resources required

Most (> 90%) of the tools require some ecological knowledge to be implemented (Figure 19). Only PlanWise4Blue (a specific tool for cumulative impact spatial mapping; #6.2) and GIS spatial planning models (#15.1) do not have this specific requirement, according to the respondents (single species models (#8) were also indicated as not requiring ecological knowledge, but low confidence is ascribed to this response, considering the low level of familiarity of the respondents). Analytical, statistical and modelling expertise, as well as programming and GIS skills, are also a common requirement across the tools. Some respondents also indicated the need for additional knowledge of the social, economic and governance system, often associated with expertise in stakeholder engagement (e.g., through running workshops) (Figure 19). This was the case, for example, of fuzzy cognitive modelling (#2.1) or impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (e.g., the ICES/Mission Atlantic variation, #7.4). PlanWise4Blue (#15.1) and the most basic (qualitative/semi-quantitative) application of SCAIRM (a specific impact risk ranking tool through linkage-chain-frameworks, #7.1) were the only tools for which no specific expertise requirement was indicated. However, where quantitative data are used in SCAIRM, the need for some expertise with GIS and/or R, and some ecological knowledge to quantify effects was indicated.

Figure 19. Frequency of types of expertise required by the assessed tools.

Most (70%) of the tools use publicly available software (e.g., MS Office (Excel, Access, etc.); R or Python-based codes; GIS-based software (e.g., ArcGIS, QGIS)), some of which available through tool-specific applications (Mental Modeller, EwE a, MARXAN, ZONATION, M-AMBI). Some may involve purchase and/or licence costs (e.g., MS office, some GIS software, Bow tie XP proprietary software). Only some specific tools require software that is not yet publicly available because of its specificity (the proprietary knowledge graph system custom-built for the DAPSI(W)R(M) for the Abu Dhabi Environment Agency, #3.1), or because the tool is still under development (e.g., SCAIRM (#7.1), running on R code and associated databases; Ocean accounts (#13.1) for which the ARIES tool is still being developed for application to the marine environment). Some tools do not necessarily require any specialist (tool-specific) applications (i.e., they can be implemented using common software as MS Office Excel, or in GIS), namely conceptual models (#1 and MAMBO #1.1), fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1), risk-based approaches (#5 and Bow-tie #5.1), cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6 and PlanWise4Blue #6.2), Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks Aquacross (#7.3) and ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (#7.4) and some simple assessment indices (#17). However, in some cases, the use of specialist software may make the tool implementation easier (e.g., using Mental Modeller for conceptual and fuzzy cognitive mapping (#1, #2.1)) or be required for specific implementations of the tool (e.g., M-AMBI simple assessment index in #17). Some tools may also require special equipment, e.g., biogeochemical modelling (#9), which may require high-performance computers where large-scale 3D models are applied (but for 1D modelling, a PC-based approach is possible).

In general, all tools are expected to perform when in data- and skill-rich situations. Some tools are particularly data-/skill-hungry and are considered not suitable for implementation in data- and/or skill-poor situations. For example, the use of food web models (#10.1), species distribution models (#12) and natural capital accounting & ecosystem services valuation (#13) seems to be limited, especially by data availability (i.e., they are poorly suited to data-poor situations even when skills are available). In turn, skills availability appears to be a limiting factor, e.g., for systematic conservation planning tools (#16 and #16.1), ecosystem models (#11) and BBN probabilistic models (#4), which all require, as a minimum, ecological knowledge and programming skills, with the addition of statistical, analytical or modelling skills (and GIS expertise for #4, #16 and #16.1). Some tools are well suited for implementation even in data- and skill-poor situations, even though this may lead to higher uncertainty and lower confidence associated with the outputs (see section 5.3.6 - Weaknesses). These include conceptual models (#1), fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1), risk-based approaches assessing exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (#5), and impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7, #7.1, #7.3 and 7.4).

5.3.6 Strengths and weaknesses

The participants in the survey were asked about the strengths and weaknesses of the tools, including barriers and limitations in applicability. Each tool has its own combination of specific strengths and weaknesses (see factsheets, Appendix 1). The most frequent results across the tools are reported below. As the information on strengths and weaknesses was derived from an open-ended question (i.e., the respondents could add their own comments), emphasis is given to the positive identification of a strength or weakness for a tool, whereas the absence of it in the response should not be necessarily interpreted as the fact that a strength or weakness does not apply to that tool.

Strengths

Some of the strengths identified for the tools characterised what the tool can do (e.g., cumulative impacts assessment, spatial assessment, coverage of multiple DAPSI(W)R(M) components, work in data-poor situations), reflecting the results outlined in the sections above.

The **ease of use** was indicated as a strength for several tools, including, e.g., conceptual models (#1), fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1), risk-based approaches such as the Bow-tie tool (#5.1), impact risk ranking tools (#7.1, #7.2, #7.3), simple assessment indices (#17) and descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (#18). Food web models with EwE (#10.1) and overarching assessment tools such as NEAT (#19.1) were also considered easy to use, although expert user

guidance or training was suggested. For several of these tools (#1, #2.1, #5.1, #7.2, #7.3, #10.1), its use in **stakeholder engagement** activities was also regarded as a strength, often associated with its **ease of communication** (#1, #2.1 and #5.1, #17, #18). Other tools, such as cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6) and single species models (#8), were indicated as easy to understand by policy makers and other stakeholders.

The strength of several tools was identified in their ability to **allow prioritisation** (e.g., of locations, pressures, species) for further research, monitoring and/or management actions (cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6 and #6.1), impact risk ranking (#7.1 and #7.4), biogeochemical models (#9.1), species distribution models (#12), bio- and socio-economic models (#14), systematic conservation planning tools (#16 and #16.1) and the NEAT overarching assessment tool (#19.1)).

The ability of a tool to provide a **holistic view** of the ecosystem (including both natural and human domains) was regarded as a strength, e.g., for knowledge graphs (#3 and 3.1), impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7 and #7.4) and natural capital accounting and ecosystem services valuation (#13 and #13.1).

The use of some tools as **screening tools** for **hypothesis generation** and **scoping complex questions** (including identification of key risks) was also seen as a strength, e.g., for conceptual models (#1), fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1) and impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7). This strength was often associated with the **identification of knowledge gaps** (hence to direct research effort) and the use for **scenario development** to support EBM (the latter being also a strength of biogeochemical models (#9) and food web models (#10.1)).

Weaknesses (including barriers and limitations)

Issues about **data requirements (and availability)** and how they may affect **uncertainty and confidence in the outputs** of the tool were the most commonly identified weaknesses for the tools. The availability of input data from specific, extensive **monitoring** programmes was a common limitation (for 20 tools out of 34). Data and knowledge gaps may be a limiting factor to the application of some tools, e.g.: the amount and diversity of the types of data required for cumulative impact spatial mapping as CIMPAL (#6.1); the knowledge gaps in impacts of human activities for impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7); the amount of data needed for overarching assessment tools (#19)). Data requirements may be a weakness also for those tools that may be applied with limited or lower quality data or may use expert judgment instead, as it would affect the uncertainty and confidence associated with the outputs (e.g., for fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1),

cumulative impact spatial mapping PlanWise4Blue (#6.2), impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7-#7.4) species distribution models (#12), spatial planning models (#15)).

Current **uncertainty in the tool parametrisation** was also identified as a weakness affecting confidence in tool outputs. This is often due to poor knowledge, leading to **simplifications** being made and **assumptions** being applied in tools like, e.g.: cumulative impact spatial mapping (#6), relying on assumptions of additive effects and linear relationship between pressures and impacts, hence with no interactions between the cause-effect relationships; impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (ICES/Mission Atlantic variation, #7.4), not accounting for cumulative and or interactive effects; biogeochemical models (#9), making some possibly simplistic assumptions on parameters' constraints due to incomplete knowledge of biogeochemical interactions; overarching assessment tools (#19), not taking ecological interactions into account in the tool parametrisation.

The stakeholder engagement, seen as a strength by some, may be also perceived as a barrier, especially where the tool requires (or may rely on) **focus/expert groups** (e.g., fuzzy cognitive mapping (#2.1), BBN probabilistic models (#4), impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (#7, #7.2, #7.4), natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (#13), bio- and socio-economic models (#14), systematic conservation planning tools (#16 and #16.1)). This may be due to challenges associated with stakeholder engagement (identified, for example, as motivating stakeholders to thoroughly verify the accuracy of their models).

Not having any associated thresholds or targets was also indicated as barrier for 15 tools (including for example: cumulative impact spatial mapping generic tools #6 and CIMPAL #6.1; impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-framework generic tools #7, ODEMM #7.2, Aquacross #7.3, and ICES/Mission Atlantic variation #7.4; food web EwE models #10.1; spatial planning tools in general #15 and GIS #15.1; overarching assessment tools as NEAT #19.1, natural capital accounting and ecosystem services valuation #13, bio- and socio-economic models), along with **non-full compatibility with policy requirements** (8 tools, e.g., tools #6, #7, #7.2, #7.3, #13, #14 mentioned above).

Barriers were also related to **costs** associated with the tool implementation. The latter may be due to expensive software (e.g., Bow tie XP for #5.1), costly monitoring requirements (e.g., benthic sampling with good coverage for M-AMBI, #17), or time-consuming operations (e.g., model building for #10.1 or #5.1 (using alternative software than Bow tie XP; compiling data manually into possibly very large spreadsheets for ODEMM #7.2 or overarching tools #19 in its current version but GES4SEAS is resolving this for #19.1 in the newer version).

5.3.7 Decision Support System – the SEAS4GES tool

Background

The SEAS4GES tool (currently available as a beta version) allows the user: (1) to specify their requirements; and (2) to outline what information (data) and skills/experience they are able to provide.

Information both on user requirements and on information (data) availability is provided by the user through two sets of six closed questions, with responses being recorded by simple check-box selections.

The assessment algorithms built into the tool compare these user inputs with a reference dataset (derived from the responses to the online survey questionnaire), which defines the range of potential ecosystem approaches both in terms of the capabilities and the data requirements of each approach.

At this stage, the tool has been produced as a proof-of-concept, and, whilst there are several areas that might be improved with further focussed development, it is anticipated that it will form part of the guidance and support provided to each LS. Functionality has been deliberately restricted to allow the tool to run without the need for macros or other VBA coding.

Tool layout

The tool opens with four visible worksheets (tabs): 'ReadMe' (coloured green); 'User input page' (coloured red); and two results tabs, 'Results (matrix)' and 'Results list & factsheets' - both coloured purple). User interaction with the SEAS4GES tool is exclusively through the 'User input page', whilst outputs can be viewed and printed from the two 'Results ...' tabs.

The SEAS4GES tool has been structured to allow modifications/corrections to the current underlying dataset to be made relatively easily. This also allows new approaches to be added at a later date, requiring only minor modifications to the tool front-end to be made.

Operation - Part 1: Filtering by user needs - what do you want to do?

This first section contains six 'filters' which, together, outline the user's needs. The tool takes the user's responses and compares them against the functionality of each of the range of 34 possible ecosystem-based approaches under consideration. These six filters identify:

- the particular elements or applications of EBM that you need to address;
- whether there are particular aspects of marine management that you are interested in;

- whether there are particular GES Descriptors that you are interested in;
- whether you need the tool to produce spatial outputs (e.g., maps) and, if so, at what scale(s);
- whether you need the tool to produce temporal outputs (e.g., future projections/forecasting) and, if so, at what scale(s); and
- whether you require a measure of the level of confidence in the outputs from the tool.

As the user selects/deselects the checkboxes against each filter, the SEAS4GES tool will calculate how many of the options that are selected by the user are satisfied by each approach (with reference to the first filter indicated above, it is highlighted that the tools selected may only partially address the EBM element, as reported in section 5.3.1). These assessments are expressed as a percentage 'compliance' score, based on relevant characteristics. For example, if a user wanted outputs at only one of the possible four spatial scales that are considered, and a tool caters for just two spatial scales, of which one is the scale required by the user - then that tool would score 100%; that is, it completely satisfies the user's needs. Equally, if the user wanted outputs at three spatial scales, with two being matched by those considered by the tool, then it would have a compliance score of 66% (i.e., 2/3).

Part 2 - Filtering by available information and skills - what are you able to provide?

This second section contains a further six 'filters' which, together, outline the range and nature of data and skills that the user and their organisation are able to provide. Again, the tool takes the user's responses and compares them against the requirements of each of the 34 possible ecosystem-based approaches under consideration. This second block of filters identifies the following:

- Whether quantitative data are available for specific DAPSI(W)R(M) components: A (Activities), P (Pressures, Spp (Species), Hab (Habitats), ES (Ecosystem Services), & SGB (Societal Goods and Benefits);
- Whether semi-quantitative data available for specific DAPSI(W)R(M) components: A (Activities), P (Pressures, Spp (Species), Hab (Habitats), ES (Ecosystem Services), & SGB (Societal Goods and Benefits);
- Whether qualitative data available for specific DAPSI(W)R(M) components: A (Activities), P (Pressures, Spp (Species), Hab (Habitats), ES (Ecosystem Services), & SGB (Societal Goods and Benefits);
- Whether empirical data are not available, expert judgment might be used as a potential alternative source of data;
- What specific expertise is the user or their wider organisation able to apply to their use of the approach; and

- Whether the data the user has available includes associated confidence/uncertainty information.

Again, as the user selects/deselects the checkboxes against each filter, the SEAS4GES tool will assess how many of the needs of each tool are met (based on the information provided by experts through the questionnaires), expressing this as a percentage 'compliance' score that represents the extent to which the requirements of each approach are satisfied by the data and skills that the user has at their disposal.

Outputs

Two forms of output are produced by the tool. These are presented on their own tabs but are also reproduced in miniature at the top of the input page, providing the user with dynamic feedback on the implications of their selection choices as they move through the 12 filters.

The first output is a simple matrix (presented on the 'Results - matrix' tab) that shows the percentage compliance scores for each approach against each of the 12 filters (filters 1-6 representing the user's needs, and filters 7-12 representing the approaches' requirements). Across the matrix, higher values indicate where an approach represents a 'better' option given the assessment needs of the user, or the ability of the user to satisfy the requirements of an approach. Conversely, lower scores indicate where an approach is less suitable.

When the SEAS4GES tool is first opened, all cells in the matrix are blank (reflecting that no comparisons have yet been made between the user's needs and the approaches' capabilities, or between the available data & skills and the approaches' operational requirements). Subsequently, as the user provides responses to each of the 12 filters, the matrix is populated (and colour-coded) row by row.

The cells in the matrix are colour-coded to aid interpretation: approaches that have compliance for a given (user) need or (approach) requirement in excess of 66% are shaded green; those in the 33-66% range are shaded orange; and those < 33% are shaded red. Given the vast number of potential combinations of user needs and tool requirements that are assessed against the 34 possible approaches it was not feasible to generate category breaks based on a formal frequency assessment of the full potential set of assessment outputs. In lieu of such an objective approach a simple pragmatic approach was instead adopted to aid interpretation. For this, values of 33% and 66% were selected to represent the boundaries between nominally low, medium, and high levels of compliance, and are primarily intended simply to allow colour-coding to be used in the graphical (matrix) output to help support the rapid visual interpretation of the derived data. For a better understanding of the

compliance of a tool with the user's requirements, the user (LSs) should consult the detailed information in the tool factsheet (Appendix 1).

The second output is a prioritised listing of the 34 approaches. This list is dynamically sorted using the average compliance score across filters 2-12 for each approach, weighted by the compliance score of filter 1. This weighting effectively increases the importance of filter 1 – if a tool performs poorly in terms of satisfying the user's needs with regard to addressing selected EBM elements, its overall performance will be down-weighted. Consequently, even if a tool satisfies all of the user's other needs, its estimated value will be downgraded if it does not address the EBM element the user is interested in. The likely optimal approach(es) are at the top of the list, and the less appropriate approaches are towards the bottom.

Again, the graphical (prioritised list) output is colour-coded to aid interpretation: currently, those approaches that have an average compliance for a given (user) need or (approach) requirement in excess of 66% are shaded green; those in the 33-66% range are shaded orange; and those < 33% are shaded red and presented in a 'strikethrough' typeface. The threshold values for the boundaries between nominally low, medium, and high levels of compliance were selected as described above (for the first output).

Both the matrix and list output tabs are set up to print to A4; the user should use the print short-cut command (Ctrl+P) to open the standard Excel print dialogue.

Interpretation

As the SEAS4GES tool is dynamic, the outputs will instantly reflect changes made to the input selections.

The interactive nature of the SEAS4GES tool enables the user to identify the filter(s) for which their responses are responsible for improving or reducing the selection of suitable approaches, and so indicate the likely limiting factors. By varying their responses to the 12 filters and observing the resultant changes in the compliance scores, the user can identify where potential restrictions arise.

Caution!

In the interests of transparency, the SEAS4GES tool is currently UNPROTECTED. However, editing any of the cells on the spreadsheet or accessing any hidden columns or tabs may impact the underlying formulae and algorithms, resulting in unpredictable and unintended tool behaviour/outcomes - please, **make a copy before you start, so to have a reference file of the tool!**

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The Discussion has been structured according to the three main objectives (subtasks) of Task 2.3, with final conclusions and the way forward also provided.

It is highlighted that the results and guidance provided in this report are derived mostly from the information provided by experts on ecosystem-based approaches. This reflects the expertise represented in the stakeholder group; therefore, as any evidence obtained from stakeholder consultation, may not be exhaustive. However, as most (82%) of the experts were members of the GES4SEAS project team, the information obtained is most likely to reflect the project focus and, therefore, is considered most relevant for this task.

6.1 Risk and opportunity assessment and management

This report has indicated the list of hazards created by natural or anthropogenic means in the marine environment and how those hazards become risks when there is the danger of the hazards affecting human wellbeing and livelihoods. Again, it is emphasised that determining any causes of change is at the centre of marine management and, hence, the *raison d'être* for creating the EU MSFD, its descriptors, criteria, indicators and PoM to prevent or alleviate adverse conditions.

Determining those risks, their causes, consequences and responses requires a rigorous and defensible approach, often involving quality-assured and widely accepted tools, as demonstrated here. Arguably, the starting point of using any of the tools mentioned and interrogated in the present report should be a conceptual model that lays down the basic framework and approach. Hence, while a conceptual model will not enable the carrying out of the assessment and management, it is the starting point for using tools to achieve these aspects.

Given the above, the EBM approach requires the Drivers, Activities, and their Pressures in the marine environment to be controlled by prevention, mitigation and compensation measures, which constitute the PoM required by the MSFD (see Smith et al., 2022 for terminology and relevant MSFD lists). These actions should then prevent State changes on the natural system and its ecosystem services and Impacts on human welfare and wellbeing and hence the goods and benefits required by society (Elliott, 2023). That PoM then constitutes the Responses using management Measures of the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework used here.

As shown here, the LSs employed in the GES4SEAS are being used to test the methods for the EBA and the inherent assessment and management relevant to GES. Hence, it is emphasised that there is the

need by those Learning Sites to start with a rigorous risk assessment and management procedure, and, if possible, extend this to an opportunity assessment and management approach as the conceptual model before using more detailed EBM tools such as those described here. Therefore, this report gives the background to and operationalisation of the ISO-accredited and industry-assured Bow-tie technique for use by the LSs.

6.2 Data requirements on activities, pressures, eco-components, impacts and ecosystem goods and services

EBM operates within the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework, where activities undertaken to satisfy basic human needs and wants (drivers) generate pressures on the environment which result in changes in the state of the ecosystem components (structure and functions) and of the ecosystem services they provide, resulting in impacts on human welfare (through effects on the supply of societal goods and services), which require appropriate response (as management measures) (Elliott et al., 2017). The goal of EBM is to maintain ecosystems in a healthy, clean, productive and resilient condition, so that they can provide humans with the services and goods we depend on (Smith et al., 2022). As such, an ecosystem approach to management recognises the full array of cause-effect interactions between the components of the marine ecosystem, integrating the natural and human domains (Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

As a result, the EBAs that may be used to support EBM may incorporate multiple components of the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework (and their inter-relationships) into the assessment, thus determining the data requirements for the implementation of such tools. Different tools may incorporate different combinations of DAPSI(W)R(M) components, and therefore, the specific data requirements will depend on the tool being applied (see factsheets in Appendix 1 for a detailed characterisation of the data requirements of each tool). LSs can be informed and benefit from the use of the SEAS4GES DST provided with this report (Appendix 1) to select the most appropriate tool(s) that fit with their specific assessment needs to support EBM in their case study area (see section 5.3.7 for instructions on how to use the DST).

The overall analysis in section 5.3.2 of this report has provided general guidance for the learning sites on the type of data that may be required by the tools for the different DAPSI(W)R(M) components (see Table 10 for a detailed overview). Whatever tool is used, it is most likely that LSs will need to collect data on activities and/or pressures in their case study area and on the state of the ecosystem components ('eco-components').

As a minimum, activities and pressures may be qualified based on their presence or, where a spatial assessment is undertaken, their distribution in the study area, although some assessments may benefit from the quantification of such components in terms of their frequency or intensity (e.g., the concentration of chemicals for contamination pressure, the concentration of nutrients for eutrophication, catch or by-catch mortality pressure for certain biota). However, the latter may be expressed as a semi-quantitative score (e.g., on a Likert scale) in some cases (for example when using risk-based approaches on exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability or cumulative impact spatial mapping). Input data on activity or pressure intensity and distribution may also be used by some tools to generate and assess the implications of management scenarios (e.g., exploring spatio-temporal changes in fishing pressure (as mortality to key stocks) to predict changes in the food web, with EWE food web models; or exploring the sensitivity of cumulative impact distributions to changes in pressures over space and time with cumulative impact spatial mapping).

Data on individual species or species groups (e.g., identified by taxonomy, function, size or a combination of them) are most commonly required by ecosystem-based assessment tools to characterise the state (and changes) of eco-components. However, several tools also use data on habitats as eco-components (see Table 9). Some tools may require evidence for one or few specific species or species groups (e.g., MAMBO, single species models, simple assessment indices focusing on a particular eco-component as M-AMBI (macrobenthos)), while others may be able to integrate data from multiple eco-components for a wider representation of the ecosystem (e.g., food web models, ecosystem models, cumulative impact spatial mapping). As before, several tools may accommodate data on eco-components in a qualitative (species or habitat occurrence in an area, spatial distribution) or semi-quantitative way (e.g., abundance score), but quantitative data (e.g., counts/abundance, density, sightings, biomass) are required to provide more robust assessments.

Most of the basic data required for eco-components concern the distribution and/or quantity (abundance or extent) of these natural assets, and these data are commonly obtained from standard monitoring programs, which are likely to be available in most countries and locations, albeit with variable coverage in space/time or eco-component (e.g., Katsanevakis et al., 2023 (Deliverable 2.2) highlighted the lack of specific/standardised monitoring programs for marine invasive alien species in most countries). However, some models may require further characterisation of these components, e.g., in terms of size, age-distribution, growth, and maturity (e.g., food web models, single species models, some simple assessment indices) or to parametrise their relationships with other eco-components (e.g., species diet matrices in food web models) or with other DAPSI(W)R(M) components (e.g., dose-effect relations, specific recovery durations, sensitivity to pressures). In most cases, the

latter may be characterised in a semi-quantitative way (e.g., using species-habitat specific impact weights), as in cumulative impact spatial mapping (e.g., CIMPAL) or in impact risk ranking approaches (e.g., ODEMM, SCAIRM). Such evidence may be derived from literature review or expert judgement, although assumptions may be made that may not accurately represent reality (e.g., additive impacts and linear response model in cumulative impact assessment). The work being undertaken on cumulative impact spatial mapping in GES4SEAS (WP4) aims at bridging these weaknesses. Additionally, through the use of the SCAIRM tool (for impact risk ranking), linkages with the ecosystem services delivery are investigated, i.e., how multiple pressures and impact risk affect the capacity of ecosystem services delivery, as addressed in WP3.1 (see Deliverable 3.1, Coll et al., 2023).

Data on the societal goods and benefits (SG&B) supplied by the ecosystem are less frequently required as inputs by the tools (Table 9). These may be included as qualitative information on the occurrence (delivery) of the SG&B in the studied system, e.g., where tools are used to map a problem (conceptual models, knowledge graphs, fuzzy cognitive modelling), while their quantification in monetary terms (e.g., market prices, exchange values) may be required for socio-economic valuations in natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation, bio- and socio-economic models (Vallecillo et al., 2022). However, some societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation (e.g., because they are not directly associated with an economic activity, for example cultural benefits), and semi-quantitative or qualitative values may be used to characterise them (e.g., wellbeing indices, welfare values assigned to SG&B based on stated preference methods). Further guidance on these approaches has been developed in the sister Horizon Europe project MARBEFES (Luisetti and Turner, 2023; Turner et al., 2023).

Some tools may also require temporal series for the data mentioned above to allow the hindcasting and forecasting of the effects of activities/pressures on the eco-components (e.g., food web models, BBN models) to allow integrated assessments over a period of time while accounting for uncertainty (e.g., as standard deviation around mean values over the study period, as in overarching assessment tools as NEAT), or to allow the full assessment of natural capital accounts (to be opened and closed over a defined time period, Turner et al., 2023).

The flexibility in data requirements mentioned above (i.e., the ability to accommodate qualitative or semi-quantitative data where quantitative data are not available) is an advantage as it widens the applicability of the approach to cases where data availability may be poor. However, the user should be aware that using lessened quality data may lead to less informative outputs (i.e., less detailed in the type of information they provide) and less trustworthy (i.e., characterised by a higher uncertainty or lower confidence).

6.3 Methods available and scales in operationalizing the approach

Twenty types of ecosystem-based approaches were identified as available to undertake assessment in support of EBM. These include the 19 tool groups identified in Deliverable 2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023), some of which are also being used to address specific issues regarding HABs, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and the decline of top predators (Deliverable 2.2, Katsanevakis et al., 2023), and an additional tool group identified by a respondent and that could not fit in the pre-defined groups (size spectrum models). The respondents of the online survey that was used to gather information on the methods also identified 14 specific tools within the existing tool groups. It is emphasised that these are just examples and not an exhaustive representation of all the specific methods available for ecosystem-based assessment. These reflect the knowledge and expertise of the respondents who provided the information. As these were mostly (but not exclusively) experts within the GES4SEAS partners team, the methods identified in this task are considered the most relevant to this project.

As seen from the respondents' input on the tools (see results in section 5.3 and detailed tool characteristics in the factsheets in Appendix 1), even though different tools may show similarities in their characteristics (e.g., they can be used to address the same EBM element(s) or require similar type of data), each tool has a specific combination of characteristics (what it can do, how it is used, what data it needs, what skills, what limitations, etc.). Therefore, the suitability of a tool for practical use in support of EBM is determined by matching these characteristics with the user's needs and abilities. Each LS likely has different priorities regarding the specific issue to address in the context of EBM, the type of output they require to support it and the availability of data and expertise they can use for this purpose. Amongst all the available EBAs, only those with characteristics that match the requirements on the user's end will be their best options to apply in the specific situation. The DST provided in Appendix 1, including the SEAS4GES DST and the tool factsheets, has been designed to guide the LSs to identify this matching and, therefore, support the selection of the tool(s) that best suit their case study. LSs should follow the instructions in section 5.3.7 on how to do this. The SEAS4GES DST is currently based on an Excel application, but discussions are ongoing to possibly integrate it into the GES4SEAS toolbox being developed in WP4.

Key to this process is that the LSs identify the EBM problem(s) to focus on (i.e., the priorities for EBM in the case study area). The PAB consultation in WP1 and the stocktaking of pressures and impacts in WP5 will likely provide this information. Organising this information conceptually is essential to frame the main problem at the centre of the EBM in the LS, its causes and consequences (not only for the natural components of the ecosystem but also for the human ones, namely the social, economic and cultural aspects) and the management actions that may be required to prevent or mitigate the

impacts. As seen before, a risk assessment and management approach is a standardised method that is particularly suited for this and can be easily implemented by the LSs, for example through Bow-tie analysis (see section 6.1 and specific guidance on how to operationalise it in section 4).

The assessment process that a LS will need to undertake to support EBM for the specific problem in their case study area may be deconstructed into separate elements of EBM, which constitute specific tasks or objectives to be delivered (to assess cumulative effects, to undertake MSFD GES assessments, to determine the footprint of pressure, activities or impacts, to establish cause-effect links between these components, to identify measures to reduce pressures or mitigate impacts, to take into account climate change, etc.; see Deliverable 2.1 for a detailed description of the 18 EBM elements identified as relevant to this project; Papadopoulou et al., 2023). The EBAs analysed in this report have been characterised based on the elements of EBM they may address. For the sake of efficiency (and economy of effort), tools that are able to address multiple EBM elements are possibly the best options available. For example, generic conceptual models, risk-based approaches assessing exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability, cumulative impact spatial mapping, impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks, food web models, and overarching assessment tools (e.g., NEAT) have been identified as currently being able to address all the elements of EBM considered in this task. However, as also seen in Deliverable 2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023), the fact that a tool may address an EBM element does not necessarily mean that it is able to fully deliver on that EBM element. In fact, a tool might provide outputs that are only relevant to specific aspects or applications of the EBM element, or that need to be used in combination with other outputs (from other tools) to fully deliver the EBM element.

When considering the need to assess cumulative effects/impacts, for example, tools designed for this purpose (namely cumulative impact spatial mapping) are the best option to deliver this element of EBM (Papadopoulou et al., 2023). This tool spatially assesses the potential effects of combined activities and pressures on ecological components (receptors), and the Halpern approach (Halpern et al., 2008) is currently being further developed in GES4SEAS (WP4) to also account for links with (hence effects on) ecosystem services and with MSFD GES assessment (through integration with NEAT) and to improve on current limitations of the method (e.g., additional impacts not accounting for interactions, linear pressure-response relationships, sensitivity scores largely relying on expert assessment), where possible.

In general, cumulative impact spatial mapping is flexible enough to accommodate any activity, pressure or receptor (for which evidence exists). Although it may use evidence of variable quality (e.g., all quantitative inputs may be replaced by the use of indices or scores on a Likert scaling, or by presence/absence records), the most robust outputs are obtained when supported by quantitative

data (e.g., from monitoring of the distribution and intensity of pressures/activities or abundance of receptors), thus increasing its ability to confidently deliver the assessment of cumulative effects/impacts. It is a spatial tool which may operate at a range of spatial scales, from site level (< 10 km²) up to broader European scale (> 100,000 km²). It does not require temporal data, but a current research direction is towards the production of temporal outputs, from short-term (seasonal variability within a year) to long-term scale (> 10 years).

There are specific applications of this type of tool that are sufficiently flexible to use expert judgment where data are unavailable. However, they deliver the EBM element only partially by focusing on a specific issue, and do not account for ecosystem services (e.g., CIMPAL - cumulative impact of invasive alien species).

Despite its highest suitability to deliver the assessment of cumulative impacts/effects, cumulative impact spatial mapping still needs to be used in combination with other tools to provide spatial information and incorporate a risk-based approach (e.g., GIS, Species Distribution Modelling, Statistical Modelling; see Stelzenmüller et al. (2018) for a review of used tools), and on monitored state/impact data to assess the accuracy of the predicted impact maps.

Several other tools may be used to account for cumulative effects/impacts (see Figure 14). Papadopoulou et al. (2023) identified impact risk-linkage-chain-frameworks (e.g., ODEMM) and risk-based approaches (e.g., Bow-tie) as the next best options (after cumulative impact spatial mapping) to deliver this element of EBM. However, these are tools for gross risk identification, and they operate in a semi-quantitative way at best (even when quantitative data are available, they are used to derive qualitative or semi-quantitative variables as needed by the model). This leads to their suitability for implementation even in data- and skill-poor situations, although it limits the use of their outputs compared to where quantitative outputs may be obtained. In addition, these tools do not produce spatially or temporally resolved outputs, only providing an assessment for the whole study area and period of time as a unit (although ODEMM is currently being developed to address quantitative spatial and temporal aspects in a Defra-funded ASPri programme). Hence, they have a reduced ability to fully deliver the element of EBM compared to cumulative impact spatial mapping. The semi-quantitative impact risk-linkage-chain-framework approach is taken forward with the quantitative method by Piet et al. (2021) that results in spatial and temporal mapping of impact risk and more recently incorporating ecosystem services and EwE modelling (SCAIRM; Coll et al., 2023; Piet et al., 2023). This and other methods currently under development may be used to address this limitation.

Another example of tools that may address cumulative impacts/effects is food web models (specifically those undertaken using EwE). However, it is not as highly ranked as the ones mentioned above when considering its ability to deliver this element of EBM (Papadopoulou et al., 2023). This is a quantitative approach that potentially gives a complete ecosystem perspective. The extent of the impact assessment, in terms of eco-components covered, depends on the formulation of the individual model being applied (i.e., which groups and functions are included/highlighted). When used in full (EwE, the tool provides spatially and temporally explicit outputs, thus allowing to forecast cumulative impacts of key components over time, from short-term to long-term predictions, and over space, from site level to broader European scale. However, it may be limited in the types of pressures that can be currently included in the model to generate the combined impact (it started as a fisheries assessment tool, but has subsequently been applied to contaminants and HABs, and it may also account for climate change; see for example Stock et al., 2023).

6.4 Conclusions (way forward)

This report provides higher level guidance, but the specific instruction for LSs to support the identification of the best options for implementing EBA in their areas (WP5) according to their needs are provided through the DST developed in Task 2.3.

At the higher level, general guidelines include the following:

- The starting point of using any of the tools mentioned and interrogated in the present report should be a conceptual model that lays down the basic framework and approach relating to the main problem to be addressed by EBM in the specific case.
- A rigorous and defensible approach is important to determine the risks created by natural or anthropogenic pressures for the marine environment and the human wellbeing and livelihoods depending on it, their causes, consequences and responses. This involves using quality-assured and widely accepted tools, such as the ISO-accredited and industry-assured Bow-tie technique (see detailed guide for operationalisation in section 4.3 of this report).
- There are multiple tools available to undertake assessment in support of EBM (34 EBA tools were considered in this study). Each tool has a specific combination of characteristics (functionality and requirements) which may make it more or less suitable for practical use, depending on the EBM context in which it is applied (i.e., one-size-fits-all does not apply). The SEAS4GES DST developed in this project allows a user to identify the best practical option(s)

(methodological tools) available depending on the particular combination of (resource) requirements and (user) capabilities in the specific proposed application.

- As tool selection will be case-specific, general guidance cannot be given except by way of an example of application. Where cumulative effects/impacts are to be assessed, the specialised tools developed for this purpose (namely cumulative impact spatial mapping in general, and as specific examples the improved 'Halpern' version being developed by GES4SEAS along with the 'Halpern' based CIMPAL+ also being developed in GES4SEAS to account for NIS, HABS and jellyfish cumulative impacts and interactions) are most suited, although they need to be used in combination with other tools (e.g., GIS, species distribution models) to provide spatial information and incorporate a risk-based approach. These spatial tools are sufficiently flexible to accommodate evidence of variable quality on any activity, pressure or receptor. They may operate at a range of spatial scales, from site level (< 10 km²) up to broader European scale (> 100,000 km²), but do not require temporal data (although research is being undertaken towards the production of temporal outputs). Impact risk-linkage-chain-frameworks (e.g., ODEMM) and risk-based approaches (e.g., Bow-tie) are the next best option to assess cumulative effects/impacts, although these are tools for broad scale risk identification, as they operate in a semi-quantitative way at best; in addition, they do not (or need further work to) produce spatially or temporally resolved outputs (recent developments in the impact risk-linkage-chain-framework approach address these limitations).
- Data requirements may vary depending on the specific EBM problem to be addressed and the methodological approach being applied. Whatever approach is used, it is most likely that data on activities and/or pressures, and on the state of the ecosystem components ('eco-components'), in the specific case will be needed. These data may be qualitative (e.g., occurrence), semi-quantitative (e.g., measured on a Likert scale) or quantitative (e.g., counts/abundance of an eco-component, intensity of a pressure), and some tools may also accommodate expert judgment. Spatial distribution and/or temporal series for the data may be required in some cases. The flexibility of a tool with regard to its data requirements (i.e., the ability to accommodate qualitative or semi-quantitative data where quantitative data are not available) widens the applicability of the approach to cases where data availability may be poor. However, the use of quantitative data would provide more robust assessments (i.e., characterised by a lower uncertainty or higher confidence) and more informative outputs (i.e., more detail regarding the type of information they provide).

Based on the work undertaken in Task 2.3, our recommendations for the LSs to move towards the practical implementation of EBM can be summarised as follows (with a proposed tentative timeline to be discussed and agreed with WP5 and the LSs):

- Each LS should first identify the specific issues (scoping questions) relevant to EBM in their case study area. As local stakeholder consultation (undertaken and ongoing in WP1 and WP5) would likely provide information on this, this step could be undertaken by project month 20.
- Risk and opportunity assessment and management is an integral part of EBM (and indeed any management). As it is one of the tools, we recommend that the LSs use Bow-tie analysis to frame their specific issue/scoping question and map the relevant cause-consequences linkages (see guidance in section 4.3). Activities undertaken in WP1 (local stakeholder consultation) and WP5 (stocktaking of pressures and impacts, identification of information gaps for the LSs) will inform the building of the Bow-tie. This will also allow identifying what elements (pressures, impacts, responses, etc.) are key to the specific issue, and which EBM elements (as defined in WP2, Deliverable 2.2 and this report) need to be addressed, thus focussing further assessment efforts. This step could be completed by project month 24.
- We recommend that LSs use the DST (the SEAS4GES tool) provided with this report (Appendix 1) to assess the applicability of the available ecosystem-based approaches and identify those that constitute the best option(s) for implementation in the LSs to address the EBM element(s) of interest. This may also help the LSs in selecting the most suitable methods to test in the assessment of HABs, IAS and jellyfish as required by Task 5.2. This step could be completed by project month 28.
- Once a shortlist of tools (best practical options) is obtained from the SEAS4GES tool, it is essential that LSs read carefully the factsheets of the selected tools (Appendix 1), as these provide more detailed info on how the tool works, also considering their limitations, barriers and weaknesses. As this step is integral to the application of the SEAS4GES DST, the timescale for it would be as indicated above for the use of the DST.
- Guided by the combined information from the DST (prioritised shortlist) and the insights and factsheets from D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) and this report, the LSs will be able to make a judgment call based on which tool(s) they may test within the GES4SEAS project timescale. Most tools are relatively easy to use, but some may require training/expert guidance. There is already interest from some LSs for some tools and resources allocated in WP3 for capacity building and support on some tools (biogeochemical models, EwE food web models, BBN models, etc.) (Deliverable 3.1, Coll et al., 2023). The use of the DST will also help the LSs to identify evidence gaps (e.g., where data are lacking for the implementation of a specific tool), and this may inform data collation needs for future assessments (outside the GES4SEAS timescale). This step would coincide with Tasks 5.2 and 5.3 (testing of methods in the LSs and identification of information gaps), to be completed by project month 42.

The flow of information from Task 2.3 (and other tasks delivered so far in WP2) into other tasks and WPs in GES4SEAS is summarised in Figure 20. Building on the work of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, Task 2.3 provides guidance for the LSs to implement ecosystem-based approaches according to their specific needs and to support EBM in these case studies (WP5). Task 2.4 will use the outputs of Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 to ‘design a practical EBA for management using risk-based and opportunity assessment management’. This will be undertaken through consultation, co-creation and iterative processes with WP1 and WP5. The results of the implementation at the LSs will be reported in deliverables D5.3 and D5.4 early in 2026, with the lessons learnt in the application of the guidelines from WP2 being summarised in Deliverable 2.4 at the end of the project. All this work will contribute to the provision of the final toolbox, and the final guidance and recommendations for practitioners to be delivered at the end of the project (Deliverables D1.1, D1.2).

Figure 20. Flow of information among tasks in WP2 and to other WPs in GES4SEAS. EBM: Ecosystem-Based Management.

7. References

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8. Appendices

8.1 Appendix 1. SEAS4GES Decision-Support System tool and factsheets

8.1.1 SEAS4GES Decision Support System

The **SEAS4GES (Selecting Ecosystem-based Approaches for GES) Decision Support Tool (DST)** is available as an Excel workbook file attached to this report (*SEAS4GES - v. Beta 2.01.xlsx*). This version of the DST was checked using the McAfee 'Total Protection' antivirus suite (version 1.11.279, release 16.0 R111) and no threats were found. SEAS4GES was produced using the Microsoft 365 Excel tool, running under Microsoft Windows 11; functionality may be limited if used on other platforms. No liabilities for the tool's use are assumed.

8.1.2 Factsheets

The **Factsheets** of the EBA tools have been included below, providing the LSs with supplementary information about the tool(s) selected when using the SEAS4GES DST. This information is intended to assist the LSs in making decisions on how best to proceed with the application, while considering the strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of the tools.

The factsheets are reported in tabular form, with the topic addressed in the online survey given in the first column of the table and the summary of the information obtained from the respondents in the second column. Tool identification numbers (#) are given as per main report. References cited in the factsheets are given at the end of this appendix.

The factsheets originate from the responses collected through the online questionnaire from experts on ecosystem-based approaches. Replicate responses were merged to compile all captured information about each tool. The information provided by the respondents on the elements of EBM addressed by a tool has been integrated with similar information from D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) for completeness. The latter also includes a score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver each addressed EBM element.

Conceptual models

Conceptual models (including mental models, mind maps, argument mapping, horrendograms, organograms, etc.) are regarded as an integral part of summarizing complex relationships within a system (e.g., natural ecosystem, socio-economic system, socio-ecological system). They aim to present graphically (visually) the main components (nodes) of a system, the pathways (vectors) linking those components and thus the nature of changes in one part of the system having repercussions for other parts of the system. They usually play an important role in communication and common understanding between developers and users. While these are often qualitative diagrams, they may form the basis of a quantitative assessment and, thus, future mathematical descriptions and predictive models. They can also draw the methodological procedures to be followed on the basis of homogenised criteria (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Conceptual models (generic tool, #1) [1 response, Expert].
- MAMBO (specific/particular tool, #1.1) [1 response, Expert].
- GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool) [NOTE: information about this tool was obtained at a later stage of the Deliverable 2.3 reporting, and, therefore, it could not be included as a standalone tool in the analysis or in the current version of SEAS4GES DST. However, the information provided for this specific tool has been included as a factsheet for completeness, and it will be fully integrated in the SEAS4GES DST at a later stage].

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.6) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*2.5) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2.6) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.6)

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.3) ● EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.2) ● EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.6) ● EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.2) ● EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) ● EBM13 - Climate change (*2.9) ● EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.8) ● EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2) ● EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.8) ● EBM17 – Risks (*1.9) ● EBM18 – Other policy requirements: (*2.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan ● Act ● Check <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Conceptual models can build in the relevant concepts for the analysis and show the direction of changes, but other tools are required for quantification. They are, therefore, a starting point for most other tools and are useful in stakeholder discussions.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For EU project work ● Within EU Technical Expert Groups ● Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups ● Within ICES Working Groups ● Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG ● Delivery of monitoring programmes ● Tracking progress against action plans, etc. ● Design of remediation/management measures ● Informing decision-making ● Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development ● Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>Overall, the tool is not used to assess GES Descriptors and/or Criteria.</p>

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Feedback mechanisms and causal loop analysis between the elements - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Feedback mechanisms and causal loop analysis between the elements - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool generally does not require quantitative data. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool generally does not require semi-quantitative data. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence or absence of all components could be added to the models. <p>Being a conceptual tool, there is no need for quantitative aspects, although they can be given, even using HML scoring.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/ Uncertainty	The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. This confidence is associated with the knowledge and confidence of the user in the links between nodes and pathways.

Tool name	Conceptual models (generic tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
	<p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological knowledge • Wide ability to think out of the box and bring together features, pathways and interactions <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avison D.E., Golder P.A., Shah H.U., 1992. Towards an SSM toolkit: rich picture diagramming. <i>European Journal of Information Systems</i> 1: 397-408. • Davies M., 2010. Concept mapping, mind mapping and argument mapping: what are the differences, and do they matter? <i>Higher Education</i>, 62(3), 279-301.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The only barrier to the tool is its limited ability to consider and link the features; hence, it should be used for both brainstorming situations and climate events.
Overall Strengths	<p>The main strength lies in its role as a foundational tool—a starting point for any other tool. It serves to indicate the direction and application of other tools, facilitating hypothesis generation prior to hypothesis testing through alternative methods. It can be stakeholder-led, making it the initial step in scenario development and interrogation.</p> <p>The tool not only aims to consolidate existing knowledge but also highlights areas of information gaps. Its effectiveness extends to communication with lay audiences, making it a valuable instrument for conveying complex information in an accessible manner.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>It is not designed for quantitative analysis, even if it is the starting point as such; it is not amendable to statistical testing.</p>

Tool name	MAMBO - Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>The tool is not considered to address any EBM elements (and consequently any PACE management phases) in its current state because it was still under development at the time the online survey was being undertaken.</p> <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address the following EBM elements: (7, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM17 – Risks <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Once the tool is developed and in use, other tools will be required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is new and is not currently being used.</p> <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess GES descriptors, namely D5 (Eutrophication).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited to use in data-rich, skills-rich situations and not suitable for data-poor, skills-poor situations. It is moderately suited to use in data-rich, but skills-poor situations or data-poor, but skills-rich situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables

Tool name	MAMBO - Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrients, phytoplankton counts, salinity. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area coverage of the bloom. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxonomic expertise (species ID). <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. This confidence is associated with the confidence of the user in the taxonomic expertise used.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Ecological knowledge <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<p>Links to GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAMBO was developed under GES4SEAS Task 2.2 to address different Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and their interaction with human and environmental pressures. MAMBO is embedded in a decision tree called GES4HABs. See Katsanevakis et al., 2023. GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.2. Technical report on the state-of-the-art in support of Ecosystem-Based Management approaches to address Harmful Algal Blooms, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, as it is restricted to particular ecosystem components (species groups or habitats).</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	<p>The tool is still in development - testing it in case studies is required to consider its strengths.</p>

Tool name	MAMBO - Environmental Matrix for the Management of Blooms (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Overall Weaknesses	The tool is still in development - testing it in case studies is required to consider weaknesses.

Tool name	GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
<p>Uses of the tool</p>	<p>The GES4HABs decision tree defines a sequence of decision steps to identify HAB management strategies according to their state (evaluated against predefined baselines) and causes (anthropic or natural). The criteria included could also be applied for other environmental issues.</p>
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>The EBM elements considered among the decision tree nodes are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 – Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD <p>Once the tool is developed and in use, other tools will be required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p> <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is new and is not currently being used.</p> <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance communication and common understanding • Informing decision-making • Development of baseline thresholds • Development of appropriate indicators and thresholds • Optimization/adaptation or delivery of monitoring programmes • Delineate the framework for remediation/management measures and anticipatory and holistic approaches.
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool does not specifically prone which Descriptors and Criteria should be assessed as different ones may be relevant according to the regional nature of HABs and their associated impacts along with the existing pressures. This decision has to be made on the basis of the results of the initial assessment exercise and the analysis of pressures linked with these different types of HABs. A table with potential Descriptors and criteria that could be involved to support the managements decisions is provided in D2.2.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is a decision tree. The different decision nodes depend on the results of the interim analysis to be performed (i.e., initial assessment, thresholds and indicators, evidence for anthropic causes, etc.). Therefore, data will be required to carry out these interim procedures (not for the decision tree itself). In this sense, the quality of the data and the obtained</p>

Tool name	GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
	analysis outcomes will be linked to the confidence and success of the management decisions adopted.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background Knowledge and existing monitoring programmes of HAB events to support the initial assessment of HABs. Outputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of best options management strategies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ control and mitigation measures and surveillance monitoring, or ○ initiate also an EBM approach like MSFD to endorse more holistic management strategies, optimise/adapt/enhance monitoring programmes for HABs, and implement accountability for pressures and socio-economic impacts related with HABs.
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	The tool can use expert judgement instead of data, but endorses the implementation of several analysis that require the use of data.
Spatial and temporal scales	The tool can be used at different spatial scales (i.e., can be used by a local authority or an international organisation to address different cases of HAB events). The decision tree includes procedures and management to be implemented either at short time scales (control and mitigation measures) and multiyear time scales (assessments, thresholds, etc)
Confidence/Uncertainty	The tool does not produce a quantitative output and thus measure of confidence/uncertainty is not part of the OUTPUTS.
Other resources required	Expertise required to apply the tool: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HABs types and major impacts affecting an area. • European legislation (Food regulations and environmental directives applied in the marine realms (MSFD, WFD, MSP, BWD, etc) No specific software or hardware is required to apply the tool itself, although different external resources are required to implement the interim procedures and analysis requirements included as nodes) <p>The decision tree includes another conceptual matrix decision tool (MAMBO) described below.</p>
Tool references/links	Links to GES4SEAS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GES4HABs was developed under GES4SEAS Task 2.2 See Katsanevakis et al., 2023. GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.2. Technical report on the state-of-the-art in support of Ecosystem-Based Management approaches to address Harmful Algal Blooms, jellyfish outbreaks, invasive species, and decline of top predators.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	
Barriers to tool application	A basic understanding of what HAB events are, and the concepts and semantics of European legislation (Food regulations and environmental directives applied in the marine realms (MSFD, WFD, MSP, BWD, etc) are required to understand the decision tree flow.
Overall Strengths	The decision tree has been elaborated and agreed by a quite large (around 20) group of experts working on HABs. These experts include partners from GES4SEAS partners and invited experts from ACTNOW project and external invited experts).

Tool name	GES4HABs decision tree (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Conceptual models
Overall Weaknesses	The tool has still not been used, nor tested by users. It would be useful to evaluate the users experience and feedback (i.e., on ease of concept and flow understanding, perceived semantic quality and clarity, etc)

Semi-quantitative mental models – Fuzzy cognitive mapping

Semi-quantitative mental models represent a progression beyond conceptual models, as they not only document the connections between nodes (the primary components of the system) but also specify the direction and strength of interactions. This enables straightforward exploration of scenarios. Given the complexity of systems such as natural ecosystems, socioeconomic systems, and socio-ecological systems, these models serve as simplifications, valuable for enhancing shared understanding and communication. They are particularly beneficial when working with stakeholders, helping to identify common understanding, goals and objectives, and highlighting differences in perspective, values and priorities (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool, #2.1) [3 responses, Very familiar].

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 – Other policy requirements:

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan ● Act ● Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is not able to address additional EBM elements or additional PACE management phases.</p> <p>According to 2 of the responses (in a total of 3), other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. FCM has limited quantitative aspects, delivering an average general opinion based on qualitative data. To fully deliver any EBM element, quantitative data are also needed. FCM can indicate what elements and (type of) interactions are important in an area. The tool is very useful for scoping issues (e.g., with stakeholders, policy-makers, etc.) in the Plan stage (of PACE), and for identifying linkages and interdependencies in the Act stage - and can be used for some scenario analysis/trade-off identification where data are lacking. Where data are available, these methods should complement more quantitative approaches.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For EU project work ● Within ICES Working Groups ● Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informing decision-making ● Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>Most responses (67%) indicated that FCM is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria. The models are built according to the specific needs of the user, so they can be tailored to any of the descriptors or criteria (e.g., D1, D3).</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activities - as multiple variables ● Pressures - as multiple variables ● Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Policy/governance decisions (e.g., MPAs, Landing Obligation, Brexit, etc.) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually qualitatively). However, it is good to derive the relationships between variables from quantitative data. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually qualitatively). However, it is good to derive the relationships between variables from quantitative data. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the importance of factor (= variable) and/or vectors (= interaction between variables) following a Likert scaling. The majority of models are built on qualitative data using expert and/or stakeholder knowledge. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Statistical • Ecological knowledge • Communication skills • Social, Economic and Governance System knowledge • Familiarity with building conceptual models • Experience with running workshops, stakeholder engagement and facilitating such exercises <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (Mental Modeler). Alternatively, the gathering of data and analysis can also be carried out without software.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • www.mentalmodeler.org • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=By24uhlBn4 • Gray S., Zanre E., Gray S., 2013. Fuzzy Cognitive Maps as representations of mental models and group beliefs: theoretical and technical issues. In Fuzzy Cognitive maps for Applied Sciences and

Tool name	Fuzzy Cognitive Modelling (FCM) with Mental Modeler (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Semi-quantitative mental models - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping
	Engineering - From fundamentals to extensions and learning algorithms Ed: Elpiniki I. Papageorgiou. Springer Publishing
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	While most (67%) of the responses reported that the tool makes no specific assumptions, and should be widely applicable, one response indicated that there are assumptions deriving from the collaborative environmental management context where FCMs are generally applied. The determination of expert credibility is not always straightforward, and often one's expertise is not directly correlated with the quality of one's mental model.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • The tool does not require focus groups to be applied, but these will increase the relevance/usefulness of the resulting models
Overall Strengths	FCM is very flexible and easy to learn and can be used and adapted to most situations (social, economic, ecological), making it especially relevant for scoping complex questions. It is an excellent first step for many analyses (especially in multi-disciplinary groups and/or with stakeholders), and it can be carried out with all types of audiences, from skilled policy makers to practitioners or laymen. Its effectiveness lies in its ability to pinpoint issues and improve communication among stakeholders. It also enables the evaluation of potential policy options prior to their implementation and helps identify crucial gaps in knowledge that may affect the reliability of model predictions. The tool can also be coupled with outputs from other analyses (e.g., risk assessment) to elaborate interlinkages between elements, or to describe system understanding (very relevant for cumulative effects) to identify knowledge gaps and direct research effort.
Overall Weaknesses	The data used to build the model is often based on opinions which may deviate from facts. The tool is limited in what it can achieve on its own. During the verification stage of the participatory modelling, one of the potential drawbacks is the challenge of motivating stakeholders to thoroughly verify the accuracy of their models.

Knowledge Graphs

A knowledge graph is a structured representation of knowledge that encapsulates information on entities, their attributes, and the relationships between them. It consists of ‘nodes’ (representing entities) and ‘edges’ (representing the relationships between them) and can be visualized as a network or a graph. It is a type of information source that is used by search engines and other applications to provide more relevant and accurate information to users. A knowledge graph might be usefully viewed as a combination of a graphical network diagram allied to a database providing information on each of the nodes and links (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Knowledge Graphs (generic tool, #3) [1 response, Very familiar].
- Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool, #3.1) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs (generic tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*1.4) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*1.4) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*1.2) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*4.8) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.6) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.6) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.6) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*1) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.6) • EBM13 - Climate change (*3.4) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*3) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*0.8)

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs (generic tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EBM18 – Other policy requirements (*2.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Act <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements, as knowledge graphs are not fully-fledged intervention tools.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Within the context of sub-national regulatory authority <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informing decision-making ● Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>Knowledge Graphs are not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited to use in data-rich, skills-rich situations and not suitable for data-poor, skills-poor situations. It is moderately suited to use in data-rich, but skills-poor situations or data-poor, but skills-rich situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activities - as multiple variables ● Pressures - as multiple variables ● Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables ● Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activities - as single variables ● Pressures - as single variables ● Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables ● Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs (generic tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated. <p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). No temporal components are produced.</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS, as entries are manually tagged as to the level of confidence.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Penev L., Dimitrova M., Senderov V., Zhelezov G., Georgiev T., Stoev P., Simov K., 2019. Openbiodiv: a knowledge graph for literature-extracted linked open data in biodiversity science, Publications, 7(2), 38. • Babalou S., Zander F., Kleinsteuber E., El Haoui B., Schellenberger Costa D., Kattge J., Konig-Ries B., 2022. iKNOW- A Knowledge Graph Management Platform for the Biodiversity Domain, Biodiversity Information Science and Standards, 6.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability, as it assumes the DAPSIWRM framework.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	<p>It is a System approach.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Requires a degree of knowledge of systems.</p>

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (15, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Knowledge Graphs - EAD DAPSI(W)R(M) is intended to document the state of knowledge and hence, knowledge gaps. Once populated with concepts, the system could be used as a schema for modelling real-world instances of EBM concepts. The system does not hard code any thematic constraints - therefore, it can handle any thematic system provided it can be defined in terms of cause-effect. However, that knowledge must first be added.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emirate of Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Human needs and wants as Drivers and Complementary Capital as Enabler of Activities - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Human needs and wants as Drivers and Complementary Capital as Enabler of Activities - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The current system works at the concept level. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The current system works at the concept level. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The current system works at the concept level. <p>The system currently works with generic EBM concepts. The concepts and inter-concept relationships could be used as a schema for representing real systems and thus provide a framework for scenario modelling.</p> <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does produce a measure of use confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p>

Tool name	Knowledge Graphs - proprietary system custom built for EAD (based on DAPSI(W)R(M)) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Knowledge Graphs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological knowledge • Environmental systems knowledge (from all environmental domains) as well (high level) knowledge of socio-economic systems which interface with the natural environment <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is currently proprietary and not readily available. It may be made freely available in future.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	The software is proprietary – contact derek.gliddon@ead.gov.ae for more information.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The subject system is a knowledge organisation and research planning tool, and not an operational EBM decision-making.
Overall Strengths	It is designed to capture and share "State-of-knowledge" for an environmental system for a specific jurisdiction/region. It is based on an extended DAPSIWRM cause-effect framework. It takes a holistic and integrated earth-systems approach, accumulating cause-effect knowledge from multiple disciplines and sectors. It has the potential to develop a knowledge schema that could be used to define a holistic network of models.
Overall Weaknesses	The system was not designed in response to the needs of the European policy context. The current system works at the concept/meta-level. It develops holistic, multi-disciplinary, multi-sectoral frameworks that could be used to organise/interoperate data-driven models of DAPSIWRM concepts and their cause-effect connections.

BBN probabilistic models

Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs) are models that graphically and probabilistically represent correlative and causal relationships among variables and that account for uncertainty. BBNs are based on two structural elements: (1) a directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing dependencies among variables (nodes), and (2) conditional probability tables indicating link strengths in the graph. The DAG comprises variables representing the modelled system, connected by arrows denoting cause-and-effect relations and showcasing statistical dependencies. A lack of a link indicates statistical independence. There are no feedback paths from child to parent nodes. The DAG can be expert-designed or learned empirically, forming the basis for operational BBNs. Each node features a probability distribution representing uncertainty about its state, either continuous or discrete. The sum of state values in the probability distribution equals 1. BBNs are effective for integrating diverse data types and modelling complex systems with numerous uncertain variables (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- BBN probabilistic models (generic tool, #4) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name		BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group		BBN probabilistic models
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>The tool is not currently designed to address any EBM elements (and consequently any PACE management phases) because it needs to be tailored to the specific analysis required. This, in turn, will determine which EBM elements the tool can address.</p> <p>D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) identified the tool to deliver the following EBM elements (with a score > 4, as per Table 27 of 2.1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address the following EBM elements: (7, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) 	

Tool name	BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group	BBN probabilistic models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM16 - Uncertainty <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>The tool, by itself, is able to fully deliver against the requirements of the above EBM elements. BBN probabilistic models are statistical models that can be tailored to a wide range of analyses of complex relationships.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups <p>The tool is not relevant to marine governance.</p>
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>BBN models can be tailored to assess any of the GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is generally well-suited to use in skills-rich situations and poorly or not suitable in skills-poor situations (data-rich, but skills-poor situations and data-poor, skills-poor situations, respectively).</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For GES or CEA: Spatiotemporal data of criteria, activities or pressures are needed for spatial explicit assessments of effects and future change. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any data - the uncertainty depends on the spread of probability distributions. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any data - the uncertainty depends on the spread of probability distributions.

Tool name	BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group	BBN probabilistic models
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p> <p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The models do not require/produce any spatial or temporal inputs/outputs, but they can handle spatial and temporal data depending on the question addressed and the data available.</p>
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. All results are expressed as probabilities of a certain state or outcome.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs. For example, R software can be used. NETICA is an alternative commercial software.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
<p>Tool references/links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NETICA: https://www.norsys.com/tutorials/netica/nt_toc_A.htm • GeNIe: https://www.bayesfusion.com/genie/ • HUGIN: https://www.hugin.com/ • Stelzenmüller V., Lee J., Garnacho E., Rogers S.I., 2010. Assessment of a Bayesian Belief Network-GIS framework as a practical tool to support marine planning. <i>Marine Pollution Bulletin</i> 60: 1743-1754. • Pihlajamäki M., Helle I., Haapasaari P., Sarkki S., Kuikka S., Lehtikoinen A., 2020. Catching the future: Applying Bayesian belief networks to exploratory scenario storylines to assess long-term changes in Baltic herring (<i>Clupea harengus membras</i>, Clupeidae) and salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>, Salmonidae) fisheries. <i>Fish and Fisheries</i> 21, 797–812. <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p>

Tool name	BBN probabilistic models (generic tool)
Tool group	BBN probabilistic models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Under Task 3.4, capacity-building activities for BBNs are being organised.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, as all relationships between components are derived directly from data, interviews, or expert knowledge.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It requires focus groups to be applied <p>In this case, focus groups refer to expert groups. In a GES or Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA) context, the specified relationships, which are not based on data, are usually derived from expert workshops or collaborative approaches.</p>
Overall Strengths	It can integrate spatiotemporal data with semi-quantitative and qualitative data.
Overall Weaknesses	It requires skills to understand the statistics and related outcomes.

Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability

Risk assessment and risk management techniques (for example, using the ISO standard Bow-tie analysis) such as IEC/ISO 31010 (IEC/ISO, 2009) are fundamental to industrial and commercial applications and have only since 2010 been applied to environmental challenges. Bow-tie diagrams are a visual tool describing and analysing the pathways of a risk, from hazards to outcomes and reviewing controls (preventative and mitigation/compensation methods, the so-called Programmes of Measures). The approach shows the causes of a problem (to the left of the knot of a Bow-tie), the hazard and element of main concern (the knot of a Bow-tie) and the consequences of a hazard happening (to the right of the knot). Various controls can be placed on the left of the hazard to prevent the hazard from occurring, or on the right to reduce/mitigate/compensate for the magnitude of any consequences (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool, #5) [1 response, Expert].
- Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool, #5.1) [2 responses, Expert].

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*3.8) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2.1) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*2.3) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2.4) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*3.3) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1.9) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1.9) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.5) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*3.5) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.5)

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.9) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2.7) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*4.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.9) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*2.6) • EBM17 – Risks (*4.7) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*3.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional PACE management phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • In policy development <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development • To analyse, evaluate and implement appropriate measures
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>Overall, this tool group is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is generally moderately suited/well-suited to all data/skills situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies of activities, spatial and temporal extent of pressures, and probabilities of effects <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies of activities, spatial and temporal extent of pressures, and probabilities of effects <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies of activities, spatial and temporal extent of pressures, and probabilities of effects <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). No spatial components are produced.</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). No temporal components are produced.</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g. seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)
<p>Confidence/ Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical

Tool name	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability (generic tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelling • Ecological knowledge <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC31010: https://www.iso.org/standard/72140.html • WIND-ERA: https://aztidata.es/wind-era/; Galparsoro, I., I. Menchaca, J. M. Garmendia, Á. Borja, A. D. Maldonado, G. Iglesias, J. Bald, 2022. Reviewing the ecological impacts of offshore wind farms. <i>npj Ocean Sustainability</i>, 1:1 • WEC-ERA: https://aztidata.es/wec-era/; Galparsoro, I., M. Korta, I. Subirana, Á. Borja, I. Menchaca, O. Solaun, I. Muxika, G. Iglesias, J. Bald, 2021. A new framework and tool for ecological risk assessment of wave energy converters projects. <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i>, 151: 111539
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	No, the tool makes no specific assumptions, and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It lacks the policy scope, context and criteria, as well as the expected outcomes of the management measures <p>These barriers may be overcome by including the managers who have to use these tools and not policy developers.</p>
Overall Strengths	It is a good quality management approach typically found in other management standards, such as ISO9000.
Overall Weaknesses	It is not designed to identify, analyse, evaluate, and ultimately treat risks through the programme of measures to achieve GES.

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM16 - Uncertainty <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Bow tie analysis is valuable for outlining all the components and their interconnections. The tool is primarily qualitative, represented as a visual, but it would be enhanced if quantified by incorporating probabilities, allowing for its expansion into a BBN probabilistic model. The tool has utility in bringing together all elements of the socio-ecological system within EBM and can be informed by stakeholder input.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The Bow-tie analysis could be applied to assess any GES descriptor or criteria. For example, the descriptors could serve either as the starting point (causes of change) or the consequences. For instance, descriptors like fishing (D3), pollution (D8, D10), contaminants in food (D9), etc., could be inserted as causes, while others such as biodiversity (D1) or seabed integrity (D6) could be defined as consequences.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited to use in skills-rich situations, and the suitability is lower in skill-poor situations (moderately suitable).</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amounts of factors that cause a change and the links from this to amounts of consequences; number of response measures that are available and any quantitative conditions for those responses. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p>

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amounts of factors that cause a change and the links from this to amounts of consequences; number of response measures that are available and any quantitative conditions for those responses. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any activities, pressures, receptors and management measures information. Qualitative indications of causes and consequences. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p> <p>The tool does not require spatial or temporal data, but these can be used depending on the question addressed and the data available. The qualitative inputs can be links between variables, causes, consequences, etc., without being time series, maps, etc. However, the output from that time series or map analysis would give the links in the Bow-tie, and perhaps the magnitude of causes and consequences.</p>
Confidence/ Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS, to the extent that the user should understand the likelihood of the causes of a particular problem.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS, to the extent that the user should understand the likelihood of a set of consequences and the ability of prevention and mitigation to address these.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modelling Ecological knowledge Understanding the concept of bow tie analysis <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs (BowTieXP). It can be obtained short term with not associated costs for education and research. However, Network diagrams in R can be a valid and effective alternative to apply the tool, or, ultimately, Bow-tie analysis can be done using power-point or any other drawing package.</p> <p>Additional resources needed can include flip charts, etc., when used in stakeholder engagement situations.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proprietary software with training - https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/solutions/enablon/bowtie Cormier, R., Elliott, M. and Rice, J., 2019. Putting on a bow-tie to sort out who does what and why in the complex arena of marine policy and management. Science of the Total Environment, 648, pp.293-305. Cormier, R., Elliott, M., and Kannen, A. 2018. IEC/ISO Bow-tie analysis of marine legislation: A case study of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. ICES Cooperative Research Report No. 342. 56 pp.

Tool name	Bow-tie analysis (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Risk-based approaches: exposure-effect-hazard-vulnerability
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	There are no real barriers to tool application other than recognising its limitations and its level of application (it can be applied conceptually or highly-qualitatively). One response indicated that when working with stakeholders, it might be helpful not to mention the tool, as some stakeholders become too centred on the tool and less focussed on the inputs/outputs.
Overall Strengths	It is an ISO-approved system, used by the industry to look at the cause-consequence & response chain and related to hazard and risk in both industrial and environmental concerns. It can be used with and without proprietary software and should be flexible. It can be used by and with stakeholders. It has the ability to link all the relevant aspects and fully fits the DAPSI(W)R(M) approach. The consequence from one analysis can become the cause for the next. It is flexible and can cover many elements. Ultimately, it is a visual representation of linkages, providing a convenient way to quickly sketch out connections.
Overall Weaknesses	It can become complex and may call for chained, parallel or serial bow-ties to be created. It can seem daunting for users and, therefore, requires guidance during application. Bow-tie XP is expensive and has very limited export functions. Using the bow-tie analysis in further work is a headache. While Visio and PowerPoint are acceptable, they can be time-consuming and, therefore, costly in terms of staff time. Sketching on paper and then using it to build a network diagram is a good compromise. Building the diagram in R means that further analysis can be easily done.

Cumulative impact spatial mapping

The global human impact assessment outlined by Halpern et al. (2008) is a spatial assessment (using a grid with a defined resolution for all spatial data) that includes (i) spatial layers representing pressures, (ii) spatial layers for ecosystem components (such as species, species groups, habitats), and (iv) weight scores that indicate the sensitivity of ecosystem components to each pressure (various methods exist for determining these weight scores). Depending on the specific application, the three scores obtained from the different layers may be summed, or the mean of impacted ecosystem components is calculated (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool, #6) [7 responses; 5 Expert, 2 Very Familiar].
- CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool, #6.1) [1 response, Expert].
- PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool, #6.2) [1 response, Very familiar].

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*4.7) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2.6) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*2.7) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*1.7) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.8) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*4) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*3.8) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*3.1) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.3) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*0.9) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1.9)

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.9) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.1) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2.6) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.5) • EBM17 – Risks (*2.5) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.6) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>According to a majority (57%) of respondents, additional tools are necessary to fully address the EBM elements mentioned above. While cumulative impact spatial mapping assesses potential activity-pressure effects, it falls short in determining the status and distance-to-target, confidence, and the identification of tipping points and thresholds of pressures resulting from multiple activities. Moreover, some EBM elements require the use of additional tools such as GIS, Species Distribution Modelling, and Statistical Modelling, especially when incorporating a risk-based approach, sensu Stelzenmüller et al. (2018). Cumulative impact spatial mapping can be easily adapted for various assessment purposes, including those related to the MSFD, MSPD, ecosystem services and more, or for evaluating the underlying causes of potential impacts. For example, Tools4MSP are a set of web and open-source tools developed to support the implementation of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), with a specific emphasis on the analysis of conflicts between marine uses and the analysis of cumulative impacts (CI) of human activities on marine environments. The Cumulative Effects Assessment tool aims to facilitate the MSP process within an Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) by assessing the potential cumulative impacts of maritime activities on the marine environment. Another example described the French case, where the "strong protection" requirements for MPAs entail measures that significantly reduce or eliminate human pressures. Cumulative impact spatial mapping helps to identify where activities and pressures are threatening marine ecosystems. This information, when combined with systematic planning tools like MARXAN or Prioritizr, assists in identifying locations for high protection areas effectively.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within ICES Working Groups <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development • Pressure indicators development • Assess the effectiveness of Programmes of Measures
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>29% of the responses indicated that the tool group is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria. 14% of the responses indicated that the tool can only assess descriptors, while 14% reported that the tool can only assess criteria. 43% of the responses reported that the tool group can assess both descriptors and criteria.</p> <p>Examples of GES descriptors and criteria that the tool is able to assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2C3, e.g., through the application of the CIMPAL index, which is a cumulative impacts spatial mapping tool (Katsanevakis et al. 2016) - CIMPAL is recommended for this criterion by Tsiamis et al. (2021) • D6 (Seafloor integrity); D6C1; D6C2; D6C3; D6C4; D6C5 • D7 (hydrographical changes); D7C1; D7C2 • D8C4; D8C2
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich situations. According to most of the responses, skills become relevant when applying the tool in data-poor situations. At least 1 response has reported that the tool is well-suited for all situations.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No mandatory quantitative data, but quantitative input data is preferred. Pressure intensity in space (and time), ecosystem components (e.g., densities) and ecosystem components sensitivity/vulnerability. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All inputs can be semi-quantitative (using indices) if quantitative is missing. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All inputs can be qualitative if better data is missing (e.g., Low/Medium/High abundance, minimal/minor/moderate/major/massive vulnerability, presence/absence). <p>The tool is a spatial tool, and the input/output layers can be of any quality. It requires spatial distribution of ecological features of interest and of pressures (ideally quantitative, e.g., abundance, coverage, but also semi-quantitative (indices) or qualitative).</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	Temporal data are not required for the approach, but it can be used to produce temporal outputs, which is a current research direction.
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>Most of the responses (57%) reported that the tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The uncertainty is assessed by estimating the quality of data, methodological approach, indicator used, etc. See Stock et al. (2016) and Stelzenmüller et al. (2018) for examples and recommendations for accounting for uncertainty. One response also mentioned that the R-coded versions of the cumulative impact mapping software could use uncertainty in input maps and impact weight scores.</p> <p>Most of the responses (57%) reported that the tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. The tool may include a general uncertainty analysis integrated with the cumulative impact assessment. It can generate a map of high and low confidence on cumulative impact using a Monte Carlo simulation.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Statistical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>To apply the tool, no specific software is required. However, there are freely available software with no licence costs (e.g., EcoImpactMapper, Tools4MSP).</p> <p>Additional resources needed include GIS software.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://figshare.com/articles/code/ImpactMapper/1519342 • https://geoplatform.tools4msp.eu/ • Stock, A., 2016. Open source software for mapping human impacts on marine ecosystems with an additive model. <i>Journal of Open Research Software</i>, 4(1). • Halpern B. S., Walbridge S., Selkoe K. A., Kappel C. V., Micheli F., D'Agrosa C., Bruno J.F., Casey K.S., Ebert C., Fox H.E., Fujita R., Heinemann D., Lenihan H.S., Madin E.M.P., Perry M.T., Selig E.R., Spalding M., Steneck R., Watson R., 2008. A global map of human impact on marine ecosystems. <i>Science</i> 319, 948–952. <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under GES4SEAS WP4, work is underway on cumulative impact spatial mapping (with the development of the GES4SEAS toolbox). The aim is to bridge the main weaknesses of the current tools and create linkages and synergies with the SCAIRM tool for impact risk ranking, as well as improving the linkages with ecosystem services (i.e., how multiple pressures affect the capacity of ecosystem services delivery).
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	All responses indicated that the tool makes assumptions, but 57% reported that these don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability,

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<p>while the remaining reported that the assumptions may potentially affect or restrict the applicability of the tool in some way.</p> <p>Two assumptions can be considered restrictive: all the impacts are additive, and the pressure-impact relationship is linear. There are also other assumptions that may affect the outcome: the fewer input data layers are added, the more the impact weight scores influence the outcome; and the temporal factor is poorly managed and may cause unnecessary noise in the output. When data are coarse or not quantitative, then an assumption must be made as to the spatial extent or intensity of, e.g., pressure data. Sensitivities of specific environmental components could be highly site-specific. Additionally, modelling pressures from human activities may involve some degree of approximation.</p>
<p>Barriers to tool application</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More funding should be allocated for systematic data collection in data-poor situations; • The application of the tool should be integrated with a monitoring field sampling to effectively assess how ecosystem components respond to multiple pressures; • Use of local expert opinion; • The uncertainty of different levels of spatial and temporal resolution should be estimated, as well as of the different data sources; • If pressure weighting scores are used, then these should be estimated by several groups of experts.
<p>Overall Strengths</p>	<p>Cumulative impact analyses offer an integrated assessment method for evaluating human impact on marine biodiversity. They facilitate mapping multiple pressures and identification of hotspots and dominating pressures. This approach is effective for broad-scale assessments, accommodating not only quantitative but also semi-quantitative or qualitative data. Geospatial datasets can be generated at various scales, emphasising the importance of supporting multi-scale spatial resolution analyses.</p> <p>The method provides valuable information on the spatial distribution of activities, pressures, and impact and this information can be utilized for management decisions, assisting in determining particular activities, areas, or ecological components. Additionally, it helps exploring how planned measures may affect cumulative impact (either decrease or increase). The outputs are easily understandable for policymakers, allowing straightforward prioritization of locations or specific pressures for management actions.</p> <p>Overall, this method can summarize potential impacts at any spatial scale, spanning from all human activities to any ecosystem component (or all). Successful comparisons with monitoring data provide evidence that the predictions of the tool are useful.</p> <p>As an example of a tool that has most of the characteristics indicated for the tool group, the approach of Tools4MSP is particularly flexible. It</p>

Tool name	Cumulative impact spatial mapping (generic tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<p>incorporates a multi-objective toolset (CEA and MUC) extendable for various analysis purposes. It enables the management and treatment of different datasets and formats and provides different levels of usability.</p>
<p>Overall Weaknesses</p>	<p>The linkages between most pressures and their environmental effects rely on sensitivity scores set by experts. There is low accuracy in estimating uncertainty. Commonly, there is high uncertainty in cause-effect relationships, which reduces confidence in Cumulative Effects Assessments. Improved uncertainty analysis is essential to better identify data gaps. Difficulties in the parameterization of the model have led to the implementation of an additive and linear model. However, ongoing research in cumulative assessment demonstrates the need for the integration of mitigative and antagonistic effects in the pressure-environmental components interaction. Therefore, the assumption of additive effects, commonly applied, is often unrealistic. Pressure impacts are treated as being linear, while sigmoidal or logarithmic responses are sometimes more realistic.</p> <p>The tool does not rely on the true state of ecosystem components and, therefore, cannot provide thresholds or tipping points. It requires high-resolution data for local-scale assessment.</p>

Tool name	CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. CIMPAL provides spatial explicit assessment and allows to integrate species model predictions supporting scenarios testing (e.g., manager effectiveness, climate change). However, it does not consider all the elements of the natural ecosystems, as well as other EBM elements such as stakeholders, management scenarios, etc. It can be used together with Species Distribution Models for simulations.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc.

Tool name	CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>CIMPAL is able to assess both GES descriptors and criteria.</p> <p>Examples: D2C1, D2C2, D2C3.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich situations and moderately suited for data-poor situations. Skills are less relevant when applying the tool.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geo-referenced species occurrence, habitat distribution, species-specific dispersion radius. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species-habitat specific impacts weights. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species pathways of introduction. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The uncertainty associated with the strength of evidence of the species-habitat impact weight is accounted for, and the magnitude of the impact can be downgraded accordingly. This is used to generate two CIMPAL scores: the CIMPAL precautionary approach and the CIMPAL uncertainty-averse

Tool name	CIMPAL - Cumulative impact of invasive alien species (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<p>strategy. Also, the species point occurrence has a 25-meters uncertainty buffer, and a species dispersion radius based on species-specific mobility traits is also defined.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. A confidence map can be generated based on the differences between the two CIMPAL approaches (the CIMPAL precautionary approach and the CIMPAL uncertainty-averse strategy).</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>Additional resources needed include GIS software to open and explore the outputs (e.g., TIFF and CSV files).</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access the LifeWatch IJI Biotope workflow and register at https://www.lifewatch.eu/internal-joint-initiative/workflows/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. The tool is specifically designed for non-indigenous species but apart from that, it should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>The CIMPAL tool is a cumulative assessment tool, and therefore, it provides a cumulative score that has no ceiling. In this sense, it is suitable for tracking trends but highly dependent on the context of application and on the baseline knowledge gathered for a given assessment, context, or region.</p>
Overall Strengths	The CIMPAL index is a framework for mapping the Cumulative IMPact of invasive ALien species. Computes negative impacts of invasive species on any environment, providing an overall cumulative impact map identifying areas at risk, hotspots of invasions and habitats according to their vulnerability. It ranks species according to their level of threat, supporting prioritisation of sites and species, and main pathways of introduction for management.
Overall Weaknesses	A key weakness is the amount of different types of data requirements.

Tool name	PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM13 – Climate change • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>The tool is able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures

Tool name	PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>PlanWise4Blue is able to assess both GES descriptors and criteria.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity) • D2 (Non-indigenous species) • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish) • D5 (Eutrophication) • D7 (Hydrographical changes) • D8 (Contaminants in the environment) • D9 (Contaminants in seafood) • D11 (Underwater noise)
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich situations and moderately suited for data-poor situations. Skills are less relevant when applying the tool.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions, multiple pressures (actual or theoretical). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions, multiple pressures (actual or theoretical). <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial/temporal data of habitat conditions, multiple pressures (actual or theoretical).

Tool name	PlanWise4Blue (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Cumulative impact spatial mapping
	The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.
Spatial and temporal scales	Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Scales: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. The results are expressed with confidence limits, the range of which is dependent on the quality of input data and empirical knowledge.
Other resources required	No specific expertise is required to apply the tool. No specific software is required to apply the tool. No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://gis.sea.ee/planwise4blue
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability; namely, results are scale-dependent.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data. Suggestions to overcome the barrier identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some criteria need increased empirical knowledge to reduce reliance on expert opinion.
Overall Strengths	PlanWise4Blue is a freely-available user-friendly geoportal that combines novel spatial modelling of environmental background (e.g., maps of benthic habitats) with spatial data related to marine resources with an emphasis on fishery, shipping and energy. Freely available, its algorithm is based on continuous layers of nature assets data and impacts based on empirical data. The tool assesses cumulative impacts - both positive and negative - of multiple pressures, both actual and theoretical.
Overall Weaknesses	Some impacts depend largely on expert opinion. Additional empirical data is continuously being incorporated to reduce this reliance.

Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks

An assessment methodology developed, e.g., in ODEMM and AQUACROSS projects, tracing sector–pressure–ecosystem component pressure pathways (also known as ‘linkage chains’) and scoring them through expert judgement and data where available. The approach consists of two main steps, identifying where linkages exist (mapping in a ‘linkage matrix’) and then scoring each linkage that does occur for a number of attributes (e.g., spatial overlap, temporal overlap, degree of impact, resilience or resistance, although there are variations on these) (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool, #7) [3 responses; 2 Expert, 1 Familiar].
- SCAIRM (specific/particular tool, #7.1) [1 response, Expert].
- ODEMM (specific/particular tool, #7.2) [2 responses; 1 Expert, 1 Very familiar].
- Aquacross (specific/particular tool, #7.3) [1 response, Very familiar].
- ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool, #7.4) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*4.1) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*1.9) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*3.2) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.3) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*3.1) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.9) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*4.8) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.8) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.2)

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1.7) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.6) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*3.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.3) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.6) • EBM17 – Risks (*3.9) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks is essentially a first screening tool to identify main human activities, pressures induced and ecosystem components impacted. It functions as a tool for a broad risk assessment, identifying risk hotspots by assessing the overlap of the presence of components with activities and pressures. This approach is semi-quantitative and can be subsequently employed in conjunction with specific modelling tools within a given context. However, it has limitations in terms of real spatial extent and lacks essential spatial and geospatial elements. Therefore, other tools are needed, including those that facilitate the spatial representation of information. Additionally, complementary indicators for different components along the linkage chains are also necessary.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors, although the responses diverged. One response considered that the tool is not able to assess descriptors or criteria, while another response indicated that the tool is able to assess both descriptors and criteria. All descriptors can be assessed by the tool to some</p>

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	extent, but it is particularly effective for D1 (Biodiversity) and D6 (Sea-floor integrity).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any quantitative data available for any activity, pressure and state/impact, although not strictly required (gross estimates will work). Once the relevant links between components are established, it is possible to quantify them if proper indicators (e.g., pressures, state change, etc.) are available. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valuation of some components (if not all) can be semi-quantitative (like categorial data), e.g., the specific Activity-Pressure-Ecosystem component chain characterisation, or Ecosystem Services expert-based valuation. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several (if not all) components, pressures and activities, but this would provide only limited evidence, ultimately only the identification of presence/absence of relevant links between components. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	No spatial components are required.

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The approach often uses spatial maps of activities and pressures to evaluate pressures and temporal information for some or all of the year. Outputs are not mapped but could be in forecast mode. Temporal dimension can be included depending on the type of data available; if so, temporal outputs are also possible.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The input information may have associated uncertainty, such as weighting/markings expert knowledge on input variables. One response reported a 5-level score based on data support, considering factors like whether the data is from the study region or not, part of a data series or not, and whether it was published peer-review or not.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (spreadsheet software).</p> <p>Additional resources needed include GIS software or R if the information is to be spatialised.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedreschi D., Niiranen S., Skern-Mauritzen M., Reid D.G., 2023. Operationalising ODEMM risk assessment for Integrated Ecosystem Assessment scoping: Complexity vs. manageability. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i>, 9, 2766. • Borgwardt, F., Robinson, L., Trauner, D., Teixeira, H., Nogueira, A.J., Lillebø, A.I., Piet, G., Kuemmerlen, M., O'Higgins, T., McDonald, H. and Arevalo-Torres, J., 2019. Exploring variability in environmental impact

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>risk from human activities across aquatic ecosystems. Science of the total environment, 652, pp.1396-1408</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teixeira, H., Lillebø, A.I., Culhane, F., Robinson, L., Trauner, D., Borgwardt, F., Kuemmerlen, M., Barbosa, A., McDonald, H., Funk, A. and O'higgins, T., 2019. Linking biodiversity to ecosystem services supply: Patterns across aquatic ecosystems. Science of the Total Environment, 657, pp.517-534.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. These assumptions are generally related to pressures, to linking the frequency of pressures to impacts without really looking at the intensity of pressures.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No monitoring data available The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements It requires focus groups to be applied It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some barriers can be overcome by revisiting the input categories bands (e.g., extent overlap % categories, less gross spatial overlap categories) and working further on the method to be more compatible with policy requirements. However, a major issue is posed by the lack of geospatial information (there is a risk from the overlap of a component from a pressure, but the location within the system is unknown, and, therefore, it is uncertain whether it is in an area with other risk hotspots or not). It requires assembling a group of experts across a range of disciplines - it would be possible, but not recommendable, to apply the method with only 2 or 3 experts. While it cannot really produce thresholds, targets could be something along the lines of "reducing risks".
Overall Strengths	It is a comprehensive risk assessment tool that considers all factors and provides the top impact risk combinations. Establishing linkage chains that connect human activities (A), associated pressures (P), ecosystem components (Ec) they impact, and the services (ESS) and functions (EF) they perform, it offers a thorough overview of all interacting elements. This approach effectively captures the big picture and enables the construction of scenarios to support EBM. The tool is capable of evaluating all sectors, pressures, and impacted components without requiring detailed information, though it benefits where this is available. Overall, it is an excellent first-level screening tool, identifying key risks and knowledge gaps.
Overall Weaknesses	No fine spatial or geospatial inputs and outputs are available. It requires expert groups and expert knowledge and is not directly compatible with policy. Robust assessments demand a large amount of diverse information, posing challenges in integrating varying data types, even within the same components (e.g., different measures of pressure) and considering the scale of assessment for different components. Another key weakness is the categorical nature of the inputs, preventing the ability to determine uncertainty statistically. The new approach developed in Aquacross has

Tool name	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks (generic tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	mitigated this. The outcomes are broad in scope, so fishing, for example, is usually considered a single sector but can be subdivided if needed.

Tool name	SCAIRM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (13, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABS) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional PACE management phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives <p>SCAIRM is able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. The tool can be applied for all steps except Plan (of PACE), and its application is dependent on data availability.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development

Tool name	SCAIRM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	SCAIRM is able to assess all GES descriptors. The output is a measure of Impact Risk, which can be shown against GES Descriptors. Results could also be linked to relevant criteria, but it does not assess if thresholds/targets are exceeded/reached.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCAIRM can be applied without quantitative input data. But if available, data can be used to assess exposure (spatial data of activities, pressures and ecosystem components) and/or the effect potential (dose-effect relations, specific recovery durations, etc). In all cases, quantitative data can be used to replace qualitative/semi-quantitative scores. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km)

Tool name	SCAIRM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The SCAIRM tool can be applied using limited (qualitative or semi-quantitative) data, using spatial/temporal data (fully quantitative), or a combination of both. Scenarios can be evaluated, but the tool does not provide any trends as such.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The expertise required depends on the input data used. In the most basic application (qualitative/semi-quantitative), no specific expertise is required. If quantitative data is used, proficiency in GIS and/or R is necessary. Additionally, to analyse quantitative data on effects, some ecological knowledge is required.</p> <p>The tool runs on R code and associated databases, which are not yet publicly available.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<p>The tool runs on R code and associated databases, which are not yet publicly available.</p> <p>Links with GES4SEAS: Under GES4SEAS WP4, work is being undertaken on cumulative impact spatial mapping (with the development of the GES4SEAS toolbox), which will create linkages and synergies with the SCAIRM tool for impact risk ranking.</p>
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<p>No other potential barriers limiting the application of the tool.</p>
Overall Strengths	<p>It is a generic tool and not limited by data availability.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>At this moment, it is mostly based on semi-quantitative data and without confidence assessment.</p>

Tool name	ODEMM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (10, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. ODEMM is not standalone for most of the elements; it requires further development in terms of scale, resolution, and geospatial capabilities. While the tool is valuable for guiding assessments or providing a general overview of conditions, it lacks the necessary level of detail for conducting a comprehensive assessment; its primary role is in gross risk prioritisation. To maximize its effectiveness, it should integrate evidence and data from various sources. It is worth noting that more recent tool Aquacross was derived from ODEMM, and the principles underlying both tools can be adapted to suit a variety of purposes.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups

Tool name	ODEMM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>ODEMM is able to assess GES descriptors, mostly focusing on D1 (Biodiversity) and D6 (Seafloor integrity). One response indicated that the tool could be used for any descriptor, with the limiting factor being the evidence to support the weighting.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited in data-rich, skills-rich situations. In data-poor or skills-poor situations, it is considered moderately suited.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables • Eco-components (not species groups) – as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity/Pressure footprint, eco-component distribution. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures, eco-components, interactions, effects and impacts. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p>

Tool name	ODEMM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>The tool deals with the assessment area as a point. Some spatial distributions might be considered within reasoning (knowledge), but they are not treated as input or output data. The same is true for temporal data, which is considered as one collective time in the assessment. Under the Defra UK-funded MSPri programme, a quantitative spatial and temporal aspect is being built.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. The measure is qualitative, as experts put their level of confidence into the assessment.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Stakeholder engagement experience • Advanced knowledge on how to link multiple matrices if using a spreadsheet software, e.g., Excel <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (Spreadsheet software or R software).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pedreschi D., Bouch P., Moriarty M., Nixon E., Knights A. M., Reid D. G., 2019. Integrated ecosystem analysis in Irish waters; providing the context for ecosystem-based fisheries management. Fisheries Research, 209, 218–229. • Pedreschi D., Niiranen S., Skern-Mauritzen M., Reid D.G., 2023. Operationalising ODEMM risk assessment for Integrated Ecosystem Assessment scoping: Complexity vs. manageability. Frontiers in Marine Science, 9, 2766.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. The general knowledge gaps in the impacts of human activities can be limiting. The tool assumes that all the users comprehend the categories and overlaps (severity, footprint, frequency, persistence, impact, recovery) and their local variability. Distribution of some pressures, particularly contaminants from land, can also be a limiting factor.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • The spreadsheet tables can be very large and take a long time to go through, with constant checking for consistency <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should be applied within an expert group and with very clear guidelines.

Tool name	ODEMM (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<p>One response reported that perhaps the biggest issue so far is that users have expected all the answers from a single tool. ODEMM and its variants provide evidence to inspire future discussions, investigations, and evidence on trade-offs.</p>
Overall Strengths	<p>It is an expert-driven assessment of risk combinations. It is relatively easy to apply and can be used with numerous datasets of Activity, Pressure and Receptor linkages. When coupled with outputs such as Sankey plots, it can be very useful for inspiring discussions around what we really know about impacts on the environment.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Including a confidence factor is challenging; this aspect has not been well-addressed so far. Additionally, without knowledge about the effectiveness of management measures, it is difficult to incorporate them. This is a critical area that needs attention. The tool is not quantitative nor spatially differentiated (outputs). It only becomes temporal if repeated for a different time and compared. The overlap of pressures and components is not specific to a specific area. It is time and expert-intensive; it should ideally be conducted in a workshop setting. Pressures, activities, components and habitats need to be updated to align with the last MSFD definitions (2017), and interactions need to be re-evaluated.</p>

Tool name	Aquacross (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Aquacross brings together evidence and data from numerous other sources to be most effective.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within other National Competent Authorities • Defra, UK (Marine Spatial Prioritisation (MSPri) Programme) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess any GES descriptor or criteria, with the limiting factor being the evidence to support the weighting.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).

Tool name	Aquacross (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and temporal activities/pressures data and environmental receptors. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and temporal activities/pressures data and environmental receptors. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and temporal activities/pressures data and environmental receptors. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). No temporal components produced. Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal)

Tool name	Aquacross (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years) <p>Under the Defra UK-funded MSPri programme, a quantitative spatial and temporal aspect is being developed.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Stakeholder engagement experience <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool. However, it is more convenient to apply with R and GIS software, though not essential.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://aquacross.eu/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. The general knowledge gaps in the impacts of human activities can be limiting. Distribution of some pressures, particularly things contaminants from land, can also be a limiting factor.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	<p>It is relatively easy to apply and can be used with numerous datasets of Activity, Pressure and Receptor linkages. When coupled with outputs such as Sankey plots, it can be very useful for inspiring discussions around what we really know about impacts on the environment.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Including a confidence factor is challenging; this aspect has not been well-addressed so far. Additionally, without knowledge about the effectiveness of management measures, it is difficult to incorporate them.</p>

Tool name	ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (17, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABS) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. ICES/Mission Atlantic variation is highly valuable as an initial screening tool, providing a comprehensive perspective and helping to prioritise and narrow the scope further. Like all Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks tools, it informs on context, risk, priorities and gaps. However, for quantitative assessments, supplementary tools are needed.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making

Tool name	ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is generally well-suited for all data and skills situations (data/skill rich/poor).
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities - as multiple variables Pressures - as multiple variables Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nothing specific is required. Anything relevant to the components included can be incorporated (usually by informing a scale, risk, impact or condition score). Maps and temporal data (occurrence, frequency, effort) are the most useful. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All the input variables are included in a semi-quantitative way. Nothing specific is required, but all available data relating to components can be used. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All variables. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>No temporal components are required/produced.</p> <p>All information can be incorporated (including spatial and temporal data) and used to inform risk scores. However, the bare minimum is expert and/or stakeholder knowledge.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecological knowledge Knowledge of social, economic and governance systems Familiarity with the approach and experience with running workshops, stakeholder engagement and facilitating such exercises <p>No specific software is required to apply the tool.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>

Tool name	ICES/Mission Atlantic variation (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Impact risk ranking through linkage-chain-frameworks
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scripts for analysis are available at https://github.com/missionatlantic/MissionAtlantic-RISK-Analysis • https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1037878
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. It assumes directionality of effects and does not account for interactions among pressures/sectors.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires focus groups to be applied • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceptable risk levels could be identified - but this is likely a case by case/regional issue. • If used as a part of a wider assessment, and treated as a living document, the risk assessment is easier to maintain and remains useful. This also limits the need for additional focus groups. Many regions already have an assessment that can be adapted/built on.
Overall Strengths	The tool is relatively simple, and (once learnt) is easily updated. It allows a holistic view of all relevant aspects and can be carried out in data-rich and poor situations. It is an excellent first step for many analyses - enabling prioritising and focusing effort on more quantitative analyses while identifying knowledge gaps.
Overall Weaknesses	It does not take interactions into account (cumulative and or interactive effects). Current scoring categories are broad, limiting detailed inferences (improvements in progress).

Single species models

Single-species models are mathematical representations used to study and understand the dynamics of a particular species within an ecosystem. The models focus on the population size, growth, and interactions of a single species, while often considering the species' interactions with its environment and other factors that influence its population dynamics. These models can incorporate limited ecosystem or multispecies information. Single-species models are useful for understanding factors influencing the abundance, distribution, and sustainability of marine organisms by, for example, elucidating causal processes underpinning declines of individual species. Single-species models have also been traditionally used in fisheries management for estimating stock status and fluctuations over time and providing management advice (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Single species models (generic tool, #8) [2 responses, Familiar].

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*1.3) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*0.9) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*0.6) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.6) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.4) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*0.9) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*0.5) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*1) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*3.3) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.7)

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*1.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.9) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*2.1) • EBM17 – Risks (*1.7) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*1.6) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. While single species models are the best approach for managing fish stocks, true EBM needs a combination with ecosystem models such as EwE or Atlantis, among others. This is because the approach primarily provides information on biomass and fishing mortality for the assessed species, typically commercial stocks. Therefore, it does not encompass the entirety of ecosystem components but is an essential part of Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management (EBFM). To extend beyond the fishing activity-pressure-state links, it is necessary to incorporate other functional relationships, such as the impact of climate change on recruitment. Without these additions, the tool remains primarily focused on fisheries-related aspects. Although it could potentially be expanded to include direct links with climate change and primary production, it still operates at the single species level.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the achievement of overarching policy goals, in particular in the Common Fisheries Policy and as elements of the MSFD D3 assessment for criteria D3C1 and D3C2
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish); D3C1; D3C2 D1 (Biodiversity)
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in situations of data-poor or skills-poor situations and poorly suited in data-poor, skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities - as multiple variables Pressures - as multiple variables Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities - as multiple variables Pressures - as multiple variables Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landings and catches (by metier, season), fishery-independent data (abundance, biomass, size, maturity), biological data (growth, asymptotic length, etc.). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the absence of catches, survey indices can be used. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> None. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p> <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting).</p>

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
	<p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. Depending on the application, in theory, the variance of all inputs is considered, but rarely taken full advantage of, e.g., surveys.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. Depending on the application, but most models can provide error bounds for both the current estimates and projections under different fishing scenarios.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (e.g., SAMtool: Stock Assessment Methods Toolkit).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SAMtool: Stock Assessment Methods Toolkit - https://rdr.io/cran/SAMtool/man/SAMtool-package.html
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. The most relevant assumptions are about life history parameters being consistent, and also assumptions about stock-recruitment relationships and their consistency and not being affected by ecosystem variables, such as temperature.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • Depending on the data available, approaches may differ (the lower the data quality, the higher the uncertainty in the output) <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-stock assessments are accessible for numerous species, yet commercial species of minor interest receive limited consideration or assessment. To address the constraint of data availability, one option is to increase the provision of sampling data through enhanced catch monitoring and more accurate surveys. Another option is to facilitate the testing or official adoption of methods for reporting poor data that could improve the spread of assessments.
Overall Strengths	<p>The tool is applicable in data-rich and data-poor conditions and provides uncertainty. It can allow tracking of several species and a good share of ecosystem components. Clear pressure-state relationship underpinning it. It can be used directly to provide management thresholds and targets and to assess the effectiveness of measures. It is broadly understood conceptually by stakeholders.</p>

Tool name	Single species models (generic tool)
Tool group	Single species models
Overall Weaknesses	<p>It is a single-species tool, so multispecies and ecosystem interactions are not accounted for. Most often, environmental drivers are not considered (although they could be included in assessments, e.g., primary production). There are too many assumptions when applying the tool, such as stock-recruitment relationships, steady state in growth, maturity, etc. Increasing complexity in specific models often results in a decrease in understanding from stakeholders.</p>

Biogeochemical models

Biogeochemical models capture two-way interactions between the biology and chemistry of ecosystems. They are used to simulate how abiotic and biotic variables interact through time and across space and provide a means to explore management scenarios in relation to climate change and changes in the flow of nutrients from land into the ocean. Typically, biogeochemical models are used to study nutrient cycling (nitrogen, phosphorus, oxygen, silicon, and iron) and impacts on planktonic communities due to events such as eutrophication and oxygen depletion (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Biogeochemical models (generic tool, #9) [1 response, Expert].
- DCPM box model, also biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool, #9.1) [1 response, Familiar].

Tool name	Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*0.7) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*1.3) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*0.7) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*1.3) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*1.3) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*1) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*0.7) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.5)

Tool name	Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EBM17 – Risks (*0.5) <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan Act <p>Biogeochemical models are able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For EU project work Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tracking progress against action plans, etc. Informing decision-making Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, mostly D5 (Eutrophication) and related criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in situations of data-poor or skills-poor situations and poorly suited in data-poor, skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pressures - as multiple variables Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tides, meteo, nutrients. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> None. <p>The model is differential equation-based and deals with quantitative inputs/outputs only. Qualitative products would require human interpretation.</p> <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data).

Tool name	Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
	<p>Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Modelling • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>Additional resources needed include access to high-performance computers for large-scale 3D computation.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.pml.ac.uk/science/projects/ERSEM-(European-Regional-Seas-Ecosystem-Model). • Savchuk O.P., Gustafsson B.G., Muller-Karulis B., 2012. BALTSEM – a marine model for decision support within the Baltic Sea Region. Technical Report No 7. Baltic Nest Institute. Stockholm. • Butenschon M., Clark J., Aldridge J.N., Allen J.I., Artioli Y., Blackford J., Bruggeman J., Cazenave P., Ciavatta S., Kay S., Lessin G., van Leeuwen S., van der Molen J., de Mora L., Polimene L., Sailley S., Stephens N., Torres R., 2016. ERSEM 15.06: a generic model for marine biogeochemistry and the ecosystem dynamics of the lower trophic levels. <i>Geoscientific Model Development</i>, 9(4), 1293–1339.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, mostly because the models generally are not species-specific and are limited to the lower trophic levels.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<p>No potential barriers to tool application.</p>
Overall Strengths	<p>Within its domain of biogeochemistry and lower trophic levels (LTL), it encompasses numerous interactions and feedbacks. It can be applied to a wide range of scenarios, including climate, nutrient reduction, and trawling impacts.</p>

Tool name	Biogeochemical models (generic tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
Overall Weaknesses	Results depend on a large number of often poorly constrained parameters. Structural uncertainty arises from our (incomplete) knowledge of biogeochemical interactions, requiring some (possibly) simplistic assumptions.

Tool name	DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (12, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABS) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM13 - Climate change <p>DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR have the potential to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. While they primarily focus on eutrophication, they can readily be coupled with other tools to consider climate change, pelagic habitats, food webs and more.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, mostly D5 (Eutrophication) and related criteria (e.g., D5C1, D5C2).
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations.

Tool name Tool group	DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool) Biogeochemical models
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables Outputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	Quantitative: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riverine flows, nutrients, chl <i>a</i>, opportunistic algae, catchment size or area for larger models, salinity gradients, residence time. Semi-quantitative: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. Qualitative: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.
Spatial and temporal scales	Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data); No temporal components produced. Scales: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.
Other resources required	Expertise required to apply the tool: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Ecological knowledge
Tool references/links	No references or links provided.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data
Overall Strengths	Strengths include the development of thresholds across an entire region rather than nationally developed thresholds. It allows the identification of

Tool name	DCPM box model and biochemical models being used to consider eutrophication in the North East Atlantic by OSPAR (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Biogeochemical models
	further monitoring requirements and the use of satellite chlorophyll <i>a</i> data as an input. The tool also has the potential for considering climate change impacts and their possible effect on future threshold values.
Overall Weaknesses	Weaknesses include discrepancies in results when employing different models and the challenge of identifying ways to reconcile these differences.

Food-web models

Food-web (or mass-balance) models are a particular type of ecosystem models, which are often visualised as networks, where nodes denote interacting ecological components, and the causal relationships between them are shown by edges. They simulate the structure and flow of energy and nutrients between ecosystem components and are commonly used for quantifying food web interactions in a whole-ecosystem context. Generally, for modelling, multiple species are aggregated according to a certain criterion and represent a single species, groups of species or ontogenic phases of a species (juveniles and adults), which are different compartments in the network. Food web models aim to understand the population dynamics among predators and prey, the stability of communities and the implications of change for ecosystem structure, functioning and stability, as well as the flow of matter/energy among the nodes as an ecosystem or ecological network (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool, #10.1) [3 responses; 1 Very familiar, 2 Familiar].

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18.1 - Other policy requirements - MSPD • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>EwE and Ecospace have the potential to fully address the EBM elements mentioned above. However, their usefulness depends on the specific configurations of individual models and the inclusion or highlighting of particular groups and functions. For instance, when dealing with Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and Non-Indigenous Species (NIS), their incorporation as part of groups or individual species significantly influences the utility of the results for the purposes mentioned. This consideration also applies to birds. Moreover, for single species or single function assessments, there are more specialised tools available, although EwE can certainly be employed in such cases as well.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity); D1C1; D1C2; D1C4 • D2 (Non-indigenous species); D2C1; D2C2 • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish); D3C1; D3C2 • D4 (Food webs); D4C1, D4C2; D4C4 • D8C1
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. The suitability decreases with decreasing amounts of data and poor skills, becoming not suitable in data-poor, skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variables depend on the question addressed. Ecopath needs species diet matrices and abundance of the initial year. Ecosim requires a time-series of any variable: oceanographic, fishing effort, mortality, abundances, etc. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecospace maps can be semi-quantitative. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecospace maps can be qualitative. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data).</p>

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
	<p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>EwE explicitly uses time series as inputs, such as catch rates, biomass of components, etc. It can then output modelled trends. As Ecospace, it can use spatial distribution data from known features (e.g., fishing effort) and output spatially resolved species abundances, etc. All of these depend on the model and how it is built. However, Ecospace allows spatial-temporal input layers and produces spatial-temporal data. Spatial and temporal inputs are not required for the tool to work—again, this depends on the model and how it is built.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. All uncertainties associated with input parameters can be addressed. These measures can then be used to assess the uncertainty of the results. It is a qualitative assessment.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. EwE produces confidence intervals if the input data uncertainty is addressed in Ecopath.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>Additional resources needed include access to MS Access to work with EwE.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colleter M., Valls A., Guitton J., Gascuel D., Pauly D., Christensen V., 2015. Global overview of the applications of the Ecopath with Ecosim modeling approach using the EcoBase models repository. Ecological Modelling 302: 42-53 • https://ecopath.org/ <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under Task 3.4, capacity-building activities for Ecopath with Ecosim and Ecospace are being organised.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>While most responses (67%) considered that the tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable, the remaining reported that the tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or</p>

Tool name	Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Food-web models
	restrict its wider applicability. These assumptions relate to diet makeup, primary productivity, and mechanistic links.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring time series, oceanography, species abundances, fishing effort, and other human stressors are essential. Although it requires some initial data to start constructing the diet matrix, estimates can be made. • Initially, EwE may seem overwhelming, so connecting with an experienced user is often advisable.
Overall Strengths	It is a quantitative approach that gives a complete ecosystem perspective. The tool itself has wide capabilities. It is relatively simple to use. It can be adapted to many different situations and questions. It started life as a fisheries tool, but has been applied to contaminants, HABs, etc. It can be used to evaluate lots of scenarios, especially in Ecosim. It can be used to work with stakeholders.
Overall Weaknesses	It might be too easy to use. The mass balancing in Ecopath presents numerous potential outcomes, as it is only necessary to balance the energy flows without needing to be extremely precise. However, this approach could lead to unrealistic solutions, and therefore, the tool should be used with the guidance of an expert user. The functional group approach used can be arbitrary, so species can be grouped together by size, shape, or any other characteristic. It does not work well with more than 30+ functional groups. Each region/location needs to have a model built using the local data. The model building takes a lot of time and resources and hence limits the usability.

Ecosystem models

Ecosystem models describe the interactions between at least two ecosystem components (e.g., populations, species, functional groups), whereby the interactions are real ecological processes (e.g., predator–prey interactions, large and small perturbations, dispersal). End-to-end (E2E) models, a specific type of ecosystem model, offer a comprehensive mathematical representation of an entire ecosystem. They integrate physicochemical oceanographic factors with organisms ranging from microbes to higher-trophic-level organisms, including humans, and connect to marine socio-economic aspects. Developed for Ecosystem-Based Management, E2E models address bottom-up and top-down controls that operate simultaneously and vary in time and space, accommodating multiple impacts. These models are employed to characterise the current ecosystem, project scenarios, and inform management decisions (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Ecosystem models (generic tool, #11) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20) (* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.3) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*2) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*3.5) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*2.1) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.5) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*3.3) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1.1) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*2.4) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.4) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.4) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2.3)

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.7) • EBM17 – Risks (*1.8) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM18.1 - Other policy requirements - MSPD <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check <p>The tool is able to fully deliver against the selected EBM elements. It is best suited for 'what-if' planning scenarios, but it can also serve as a counterfactual tool to understand effects or for conducting benefit evaluations. There is potential to use it in planning monitoring activities, although it is advisable not to rely on it for annual decision-making processes. Additionally, it can be employed to characterise impact response functions, which can then be integrated into other tools (e.g., the Halpern modified Halpern approach) for the analysis of non-additive effects.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. Skills are highly relevant for using this tool, making it moderately suited for data-poor situations and poorly or even not suitable for skills-poor situations.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numbers or biomass of each biological component of the model (typically biomass pools for invertebrates and abundance at age for vertebrates) - which might be species or functional group of taxonomic resolution. In addition, it needs a map of the bottom type and time series of hydrodynamic flows and physical environmental state (temperature, salinity, etc.). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While the quantitative values input might be "best guess" and thus, in theory, semi-quantitative, all inputs are treated as quantitative. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps).</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting).</p> <p>Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years) <p>The tool requires spatial initial conditions and time series of forcing for activities if they are not dynamically represented within the model. It also needs parameters defining the timing of processes such as migration and</p>

Tool name	Ecosystem models (generic tool)
Tool group	Ecosystem models
	reproduction. The output is a 3D spatially resolved time-series for each model variable.
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. It is necessary to run multiple simulations with different parameterisations across plausible parameter spaces to produce confidence bands. The model will not do that in isolation (i.e., the user has to do the runs; the model does not just produce confidence bands on the output), but it is best practice.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (e.g., Atlantis).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://research.csiro.au/atlantis/home/links/ • www.mathstat.strath.ac.uk/outreach/e2e
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. The user must define what options are being used for movement, recruitment, feeding relationships, etc. Once selected, the model will use the assumptions inherent in those relationships. The model also makes some simple assumptions about how things are distributed (homogeneous, Poisson, etc.) within a spatial cell.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<p>Suggestions to overcome barriers to tool application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert user guidance/training can help any new users deal with data shortages/patchiness and how to follow best practice guidelines in model use
Overall Strengths	<p>It represents the dynamic spatiotemporal outcomes of the complexity of interactions and processes that occur in real systems. This extends beyond equilibrium assumptions, static maps and the assumption of additive in cumulative effects.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>Data-intensive can be hard to use (e.g., Atlantis) or easily accidentally misused (e.g., Ecopath with Ecosim*), so it is best to have an expert user to guide any new users.</p> <p><i>*Note: Ecopath with Ecosim is a food-web model – a specific case of Ecosystem Models. For details on this tool refer to the tool group “Food-web models”.</i></p>

Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)

Habitat suitability models (HSM), also referred to in the literature as species distribution models (SDMs) or predictive habitat distribution models, are predictive models used to predict the spatial distribution of species based on their observed relationship with environmental conditions. On calibration of the model, the species-environment relationship is established based on data on the species distribution and the environmental conditions where it occurs. It is used to identify the key environmental predictors which determine the suitability of a location for the species. On prediction, the environmental conditions are used as predictors of the likelihood of the presence or density of the species throughout a study area. As such, this modelling approach can be seen as an operational application of the potential ecological niche (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool, #12) [2 responses; 1 Expert, 1 Very familiar].

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (11, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.5) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*1.9) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.8) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*3.2) • EBM13 - Climate change (*2.4) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*2.1) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*1.9) • EBM17 – Risks (*1.8) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	<p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Species distribution models (SDMs) are able to fully deliver against the selected EBM elements. The tool enables the assessment and prediction of the environmental envelope of marine species, thus predicting the distribution of these biodiversity assets, including potential changes, such as those resulting from different climate scenarios. Consequently, SDMs play a crucial role in supporting planning efforts by identifying areas of risk, where negative interactions between assets and activities may occur, and by pinpointing conservation priority areas. These priority areas can be determined, for instance, by combining the results of SDMs for multiple species, aiding in the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and highlighting diversity hotspots.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • Research supporting management (a fisheries management tool in the US (through Essential Fish Habitats), trying to be implemented in the UK) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool can assess GES descriptors and criteria. While it does not provide a direct assessment, the outputs of SDMs support assessments primarily related to D1 (Biodiversity). Examples of criteria include D1C2, D1C4, D1C5, and D2C2.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-rich, skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for any data-poor situation.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p>

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Species distribution and abundance data (density, catches, sightings, etc.) - from monitoring. Environmental data layers (oceanographic, topographic, geomorphologic, etc., variables) to calibrate and predict the model. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maybe species abundance could be represented in a semiquantitative way (e.g., on a discrete scale/score), but it's unusual. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Species occurrence (presence/absence) from monitoring, if no abundance data are available. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p> <p>Spatial inputs = spatial layers of environmental data (model predictors) + spatial distribution of monitoring data (abundances, sightings, etc.). Spatial outputs = maps of predicted species variable (e.g., probability of presence, density). Temporal inputs = not really a requirement, but the wider spatial and temporal coverage of the input data (e.g., for multiple years), the better the model predictions are likely to be (higher confidence). A SDM does not per se provide future trends, as its outputs represent a snapshot in time (related to the timing of the environmental predictor layers to which the model is applied). However, if environmental layers are available as predictions for multiple points in future time, the different outputs from the SDM application to each of these can be interpreted to forecast potential future trends in the species distribution.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The confidence can be estimated qualitatively based on the quality of the input data. Quantitative estimates (S.D., CV) can also be used. The tool allows, for instance, the inclusion of information about sampling bias as input data.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS, such as statistical confidence based on model predictive ability. Additional</p>

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	confidence estimates can be combined with statistical confidence based on the quality of the input data, their uncertainty, etc. The tool can also produce uncertainty maps in addition to the maps about the potential distribution of species/habitats.
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs. The models can be implemented using various statistical approaches (GLM, GAMS, CART, etc.), and R software can be used for this purpose. However, there may be some statistical packages that offer specific applications.</p> <p>Additional resources needed depend on the volume of data - a computational cluster may be required to model large datasets.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fortuna, C.M., Cañadas, A., Holcer, D., Brecciaroli, B., Donovan, G.P., Lazar, B., Mo, G., Tunesi, L. and Mackelworth, P.C., 2018. The coherence of the European Union marine Natura 2000 network for wide-ranging charismatic species: a Mediterranean case study. <i>Frontiers In Marine Science</i>, 5, p.356. • Sillero, N., Arenas-Castro, S., Enriquez-Urzelai, U., Vale, C.G., Sousa-Guedes, D., Martínez-Freiría, F., Real, R. and Barbosa, A.M., 2021. Want to model a species niche? A step-by-step guideline on correlative ecological niche modelling. <i>Ecological Modelling</i>, 456, p.109671 • Naimi, B. and Araújo, M.B., 2016. sdm: a reproducible and extensible R platform for species distribution modelling. <i>Ecography</i>, 39(4), pp.368-375. • Galparsoro, I., Á. Borja, J. Bald, P. Liria, G. Chust, 2009. Predicting suitable habitat for the European lobster (<i>Homarus gammarus</i>), on the Basque continental shelf (Bay of Biscay), using Ecological-Niche Factor Analysis. <i>Ecological Modelling</i>, 220: 556-567 https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0304380008005395 • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=83dMS3bcjJM
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. One such assumption is that observed species-environment relationships can be extrapolated for prediction. While the tool can be theoretically applied anywhere, users must consider the validity and confidence in predictions, especially beyond calibrated environmental ranges, for appropriate use and interpretation of the outputs. The tool benefits from the availability of wide-ranging and long-term datasets, resulting in better confidence and wider validity of results. Additionally, the tool assumes that the species assessed is in equilibrium with the environment, the biases in the

Tool name	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (generic tool)
Tool group	Habitat suitability/species distribution models (spp. predictive distribution)
	<p>modelling system are minimal, all predictors included in the model describe the species niche, and that the species niche is conserved across space and time.</p>
<p>Barriers to tool application</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available <p>The tool can be applied with limited data, but this would affect the confidence and validity of outputs. Data from broad-scale sampling programmes is preferred to provide input data on species. Limited availability of species monitoring data and of environmental data layers (for model calibration and prediction) in certain areas (e.g., inshore/estuarine areas) may be a barrier to the model implementation.</p> <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement broad-scale, coordinated/harmonised monitoring programmes (species and environmental variables) encompassing poorly covered areas.
<p>Overall Strengths</p>	<p>The tool allows mapping potential distribution of biodiversity assets (species) in an objective way (based on an environmental envelope), thus supporting the identification of key areas for spatial management (conservation, MPAs, areas of risk). It provides continuous estimations of species/habitat's potential distribution over the study area using point information on species occurrence/abundance. Some specific techniques were developed to overcome limitations related to data-poor species.</p>
<p>Overall Weaknesses</p>	<p>The models are data-driven, so the quality of the data is key to the quality of the output (affecting confidence). One model applies to one species (but outputs can be combined across species in a community, e.g., to identify biodiversity hotspots). A continuous representation of the environmental predictors over the study area is required in order to produce maps of potential distribution for species/habitats. This requirement is sometimes difficult to achieve for all ecologically relevant predictors, particularly for future environmental conditions when the objective is to forecast the impacts of climate change on the species/habitats distribution range.</p>

Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation

The natural capital approach to policy and decision-making considers the value of the natural environment for people and the economy, providing a tool to support the protection and management of the natural environment and to facilitate the engagement of stakeholders within management decisions. Natural capital accounts are developed to assess and monitor the contribution of natural resources to economic activity. Physical accounts tables provide basic information on the state of the environment (the stock and the flows of the natural capital, analogous to ecological structure and functioning) in a specific geographical area. When a condition table is also populated, this information can indicate at what level of the ecosystem an impact of economic activities is occurring (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool, #13) [2 responses; 1 Very familiar, 1 Familiar].
- Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool, #13.1) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (11, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*0.8) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*4.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*2.7) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*0.5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1) • EBM13 - Climate change (*0.8) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*1.8) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	<p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. The tool focusses on natural capital and ecosystem service valuation and not all aspects of the ecosystem. Its foundation lies in monetary valuation, and currently, not all benefits derived from ecosystem services can be quantified in monetary terms. Furthermore, the tool is not yet fully developed or operationalized. Non-monetary valuation is an area that is currently receiving significant attention in research.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • National governments (national reporting) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-rich, skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for any data-poor situation.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as single variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat extent, geography and condition, and prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services. Where possible, both spatial and temporal data to provide the best outputs. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative components are an additional source of information to supplement the monetary values derived from these tools.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. EUNIS habitats have associated confidence scores. There are assumptions made regarding confidence in monetary prices inputted into the tools.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS

Tool name	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological knowledge • Economics • Management <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gacutan, J., Pınarbaşı K., Agbaglah M., Bradley C., Galparsoro I., Murillas A., Adewumi I., Praphotjanaporn T., Bordt M., Findlay K., Lantz C., Milligan B. M., 2022a. The emerging intersection between marine spatial planning and ocean accounting: A global review and case studies. <i>Marine Policy</i>, 140: 105055. The model described in this paper is operational and freely available here: https://aztidata.es/vapem/ • United Nations et al. (2021). System of Environmental-Economic Accounting— Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA). White cover publication, pre-edited text subject to official editing. Available at: https://seea.un.org/ecosystem-accounting. <p>Links with GES4SEAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under Task 3.4, capacity-building activities for Capacity to Deliver Ecosystem Services and links to GES are being organised.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, primarily influenced by the confidence in valuation and mapping data, often focusing on one biological element at a time in some cases.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It requires focus groups to be applied • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • It requires the availability of habitat and valuation data <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More evidence collection on societal benefits and their value. Identification of data gaps within EUNIS mapping. • Time and resources.
Overall Strengths	Strengths include ensuring the societal benefits of natural environments are included within wider accounting and inform decision-making. There are standard sets of agreed rules (e.g., UN SEEA) emerging for the application of these tools, and this facilitates consistent application across geographical locations and over time.
Overall Weaknesses	Data availability impacting on its ability to cover societal benefits in a comprehensive way. The tool is still in development.

Tool name	Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (9, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Ocean accounts require environmental/ecosystem services valuation tools, as they are separate from accounting. The tool is useful to provide information to decision support systems.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • The Global Ocean Accounts Partnership (GOAP) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors and criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor, skills-poor situations.

Tool name	Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as single variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat extent, geography and condition, and prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. This is a recent functionality of the tool.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. This is a recent functionality of the tool.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Economics <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs, but its application to the marine environment is still in development (ARIES).</p>

Tool name	Ocean Accounts (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Natural capital accounting, ecosystem services valuation
	No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://aries.integratedmodelling.org/ (the application to the marine environment is still in development)
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, depending on the ecosystem service considered.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collecting more ad hoc data
Overall Strengths	The tool provides a complete, succinct summary of the environmental extent, condition and economic value of an area.
Overall Weaknesses	It is still a recent tool and is under experimentation/development.

Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation

This tool group includes tools such as: (i) Bio-economic models, i.e. integrated economic-ecological models used for resource management and sustainable resource use; (ii) Valuation of Societal Benefits, which determines the ‘total social value’ (comprising of ecological value, economic value, and socio-cultural value) of marine ecosystem services leading to benefits for society; (iii) Cost-benefit analysis (CBA), a core tool of public policy consisting in the systematic process of calculating the benefits and costs, expressed in monetary units, of policy options and projects (environmental CBA is the application of CBA to projects or policies that have the deliberate aim of environmental improvement or actions that somehow affect the natural environment as an indirect consequence) (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool, #14) [1 response, Very familiar].

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (5, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change (*0.5) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*1.5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives <p>In its current state, the tool is able to address PACE management phases, but the respondent was unsure when.</p> <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements, as these tools focus on monetary valuation.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
marine governance/management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within other National Competent Authorities • National governments <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat extent, geography and condition, and prices of societal benefits secured from ecosystem services. Where possible, both spatial and temporal data to provide the best outputs. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the societal benefits are not amenable to monetary valuation. <p>Qualitative components are an additional source of information to supplement the monetary values derived from these tools.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km)

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
	<p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS • Ecological knowledge • Economics <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is readily available, but there are associated purchase and/or licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atkins J.P., Burdon D., Elliott M., Gregory A.J., 2011. Management of the marine environment: integrating ecosystem services and societal benefits with the DPSIR framework in a systems approach. Marine Pollution Bulletin, 62, pp. 215-226 • Burdon D., Boyes S.J., Elliott M., Smyth K., Atkin J.P., Barnes R.A., Wurzel R.K., 2018. Integrating natural and social marine science to sustainably manage vectors of change: Dogger Bank transnational case study. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 201: 234-247
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way, primarily influenced by the confidence in valuation and mapping data.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • The tool is not fully compatible with policy requirements • It requires focus groups to be applied • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • It requires the availability of habitat and valuation data <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More evidence collection on societal benefits and their value • Time and resources

Tool name	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation (generic tool)
Tool group	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation
Overall Strengths	Bioeconomic models, socioeconomic models (CBA), societal goods and benefits valuation tools measure the benefits of the natural environment to human welfare in value terms and thereby support decision-making.
Overall Weaknesses	These tools attempt to provide evidence to inform decision-making on aspects which have not previously been included in decision-making as such evidence was absent.

Spatial planning models and tools

Spatial planning models, adapted to the marine environment, are tools used to help planners and policymakers make informed decisions about the use of marine space and resources. The models are designed to provide insights into the potential impacts of different planning scenarios, and to help identify the most effective strategies for achieving specific planning goals. There are several different types of spatial planning models, each of which is suited to different types of planning challenges. Overall, these models play a crucial role in supporting informed decision-making by evaluating the impact of diverse land-use and development scenarios on environmental quality and natural resources. They contribute to the identification of vulnerable areas, habitat loss, or other environmental hazards, and evaluate the effectiveness of different conservation strategies (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool, #15) [1 response, Very familiar].
- GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool, #15.1) [1 response, Very familiar].

Tool name	Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (10, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.8) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*1.5) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1.7) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.2) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.9) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*1.5) • EBM17 – Risks (*2.1) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
	<p>D2.1 (Papadopoulou et al., 2023) identified the tool to deliver the following EBM elements (with score > 4, as per Table 27 of 2.1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Check • Evaluate <p>The tool is able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • For EEA assessments • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Informing decision-making • Design of remediation/management measures • Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in any other situation.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as single variables

Tool name	Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of activities and pressures, and potentially their intensity. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables can be semi-quantitative data. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All variables can be qualitative data. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (QGIS).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • www.qgis.org • VAPEM tool: Environmental Assessment and Marine Spatial Planning tool: https://aztidata.es/vapem/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. These assumptions could involve factors such as the knowledge on the spatial distribution of some variables. Despite these assumptions, mapping can still be performed; however, the accuracy may be reduced compared to using more detailed data.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available

Tool name	Spatial planning models and tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	The spatial aspect is the strength, as this allows for analyses that are not restricted to a single spot.
Overall Weaknesses	It requires good knowledge of the tool and how to properly handle the data.

Tool name	GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (13, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. For example, the tool does not have any associated thresholds or targets to determine GES.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and Criteria. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1C2; D1C4; D1C5; D1C6 • D2C1; D2C3 • D5C3 D5C8 • D6 (Sea-floor integrity) • D7 (Hydrographical changes)

Tool name	GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D8C3 • D10C1; D10C2
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures, species abundance, species potential distribution, area/extent. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures, risk. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities, habitat, species occurrence. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data); Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., >10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.

Tool name	GIS – Geographic Information System (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Spatial planning models and tools
	The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Modelling • GIS <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs (e.g., QGIS).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://qgis.org/en/docs/index.html
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets
Overall Strengths	GIS allows storing, managing and mapping different types of data (e.g., physical, biological, environmental, ecological, geological, etc) that can be further analysed using spatial analysis supported by statistical and modelling approaches. These capabilities can, therefore, support monitoring of, for instance, detrimental environmental changes and shifts in species distribution and habitat extent and, at the same time, support the development of mitigation/restoration measures.
Overall Weaknesses	It requires expertise in manipulating and processing spatial data and georeferenced information.

Conservation planning models

Conservation planning is the process of locating, configuring, implementing and maintaining areas that are managed to promote the persistence of biodiversity and other natural values. Systematic conservation planning (SCP) uses an explicit and transparent methodology to locate and design new reserves complementing the existing network of protected areas. It applies explicit criteria for implementing conservation actions and adopting explicit objectives and mechanisms for maintaining the needed conditions in protected areas required to foster the persistence of the protected ecological features (used as surrogates for overall biodiversity), as well as adequate monitoring schemes and adaptive management. SCP is goal-oriented (with operational targets) and recognizes the level of achievement of conservation goals in the existing protected areas. Decision support tools have been developed to facilitate systematic conservation planning, the most widely used being MARXAN and ZONATION (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool, #16) [1 response, Very familiar].
- MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool, #16.1) [2 responses, Very familiar].

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (11, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*1.8) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*0.8) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.2) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.7) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.6) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.3) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*4.6) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*2) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*3.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address additional EBM elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. For some EBM elements, outputs from additional tools are needed, such as Species Distribution Models, Cumulative Impact Mapping, GIS, and vulnerability assessments (linking activities, pressures, and impacts).</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited in any skills-rich situations and poorly suited in any skills-poor situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p>

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species abundance, habitat coverage, metrics of activities/pressures (e.g., actual fishing effort per grid cell, level of disturbance by towed gears), and contribution of human activities to GDP. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indices of species abundance, indices of the intensity of human activities. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For species, habitats, and activities: presence data or data in a Likert scale (e.g., low/medium/high abundance - low/medium/high fishing effort). <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., >100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. For instance, Marxan with Probability considers 4 types of uncertainty: the probability that a feature exists in a particular place; the probability that features in a site will be lost in the future due to a threatening process; the probability that a feature will exist in the future due to natural successional processes; and probability the feature exists but has been degraded by threatening processes, such as overfishing or pollution, and thus cannot contribute to conservation goals.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. Multiple runs are necessary to produce selection frequency maps (indicating how often, under different runs, a grid cell is proposed to be prioritised for protection). High frequencies indicate high confidence in the importance of specific cells.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge

Tool name	Systematic conservation planning tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the use of specific software (e.g., MARXAN, ZONATION, prioritizer) <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://marxansolutions.org/ • https://zonationteam.github.io/Zonation5/ • https://prioritizr.net/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions, but they don't (or are unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability. For example, specific assumptions about connectivity regarding ecosystem components or threats, data-driven assumptions about the distribution of ecological components, and assumptions about the vulnerability of ecological components to specific activities/pressures.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It requires focus groups to be applied <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species distribution models (SDMs) can be used to deal with data gaps. • Adaptive management.
Overall Strengths	The tool provides an efficient and cost-effective way of creating/expanding MPA networks, e.g., to support the Biodiversity Strategy, accounting for both the distribution of ecological and socioeconomic features as well as accounting for existing spatial management measures.
Overall Weaknesses	It is not easy for the stakeholders to perceive how the outputs of the tool have been produced. Although the tool is based on a transparent methodology, high technical and analytical skills are required for its implementation.

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (19, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM17 - Risks <p>MARXAN family tools are able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. The tool has the capacity to integrate a wide range of information and outputs from other tools, depending on the concept developed and the questions set.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For EU project work • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing decision-making

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool does not directly address a policy need, but provides valuable supporting evidence for policy development
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	The tool is not able to assess GES descriptors or criteria.
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations and poorly suited in any skills-poor situations. In data-poor, skills-rich situations, the tool is moderately suited.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The full distribution of features (e.g., species, habitat, process, cultural site, etc.) targeted for protection expressed as continuous values (e.g., species population, model outputs, indicators, proxies); pressures and management cost expressed in relevant units (e.g., fishing effort) or as distance-based cost; opportunity cost or action-based cost; numerical conservation targets for each feature targeted for protection, etc. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of features (e.g., species, habitat, process, cultural site, etc.) targeted for protection based on expert judgement; or through indicators and proxies; presence of an activity (e.g., port); cost expressed as pressure (e.g., fishing effort) or as distance/area-based cost. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data).</p> <p>Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps).</p> <p>Scales:</p>

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required/produced.</p> <p>As outputs represent a snapshot in time, to obtain temporal outputs, it is possible to run the tool multiple times using relevant information that corresponds to the targeted temporal scale (e.g., per season).</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. The tool provides output showing the number of times each planning unit was selected across all solutions (selection frequency). It provides an indication of how useful each planning unit is for creating an efficient reserve system. See also Confidence/Uncertainty information for the generic tool.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. It allows the development of portfolios of solutions.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://marxansolutions.org/software/ • https://prioritizr.net/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires focus groups to be applied • No temporal or 3-d dimension • In some cases, proxies for socio-economic data may have high uncertainty <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the temporal dimension, it is possible to run MARXAN multiple times using the relevant information that corresponds to the targeted temporal scale (e.g., per season).
Overall Strengths	MARXAN is the most widely used conservation planning tool to support decision-making regarding the design of terrestrial, marine, and/or aquatic reserves and management areas. It produces objective and transparent

Tool name	MARXAN family tools (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Systematic conservation planning tools
	outcomes, enhancing participative planning and stakeholder engagement. It integrates various types of information and enables the development of sophisticated planning.
Overall Weaknesses	Poor data quality and quantity significantly impact outputs. Other significant weaknesses include the absence of a temporal dimension, large spatial information requirements, and increased processing time in complex planning scenarios and extensive areas. Moreover, targets must be determined based on expert opinion.

Simple assessment index

Simple assessment indices are methods for classifying marine systems according to human pressures and include those focusing on the primary community structural variables (abundance, species richness, and biomass) and derived community structural variables (such as diversity indices, abundance and biomass ratios, and evenness indices). Functional analyses, including those involving feeding guilds and responses to organic matter inputs or other human pressures, are also part of these indices, often referred to as “biotic indices”. There are numerous biotic indices covering different biological elements, including phytoplankton, zooplankton, macroalgae, seagrasses, macroinvertebrates and fishes. Among these, indices using several metrics (e.g., richness, diversity, proportion of opportunistic/sensitive species, etc.) and combined in different ways (e.g., multimetric, multivariate) have been very successful (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Simple assessment index (generic tool, #17) [3 responses; 2 Expert, 1 Very familiar].

Tool name	Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group	Simple assessment index
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (18, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*1.1) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*3) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*0.8) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*3.1) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*2.2) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*0.8) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*1.2) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*2.5) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*1.9) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.4) • EBM13 - Climate change (*0.7)

Tool name	Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group	Simple assessment index
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*1.6) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*1.4) • EBM17 – Risks (*0.9) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.4) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM16 - Uncertainty <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements.</p> <p>A simple assessment index is usually limited to a specific aspect of the element being assessed, and by design, it cannot comprehensively cover all aspects on its own. Utilizing multiple simple indexes and other methods provides a more holistic view of the status or biodiversity parameters.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Groups within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean • Within other National Competent Authorities • Water Framework Directive (WFD) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess GES criteria. Various criteria within D1 (Biodiversity), D2 (Non-indigenous species), D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish), D6 (Sea-floor integrity) (e.g., D6C3), D10 (Marine litter). Also, criteria linked to the WFD, such as D5C8.</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	

Tool name	Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group	Simple assessment index
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	The tool is well-suited for use in most situations, except in data-poor and skills-poor situations, when it becomes moderately suited.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abundance, biomass, biovolume, age distribution, species count, body size, arrivals. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence/absence. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs are produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	Expertise required to apply the tool:

Tool name	Simple assessment index (generic tool)
Tool group	Simple assessment index
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Ecological knowledge <p>Overall, no specific software is required. Some assessment indices might require software (e.g., M-AMBI).</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://ambi.azti.es/ • Borja A., Mader J., Muxika I., Rodriguez J. G., Bald J., 2008. Using M-AMBI in assessing benthic quality within the Water Framework Directive: Some remarks and recommendations. Marine Pollution Bulletin, 56: 1377-1379
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes assumptions that may potentially affect or restrict its applicability in some way. Generally, reference conditions are needed to apply the tool. The simplicity of the tool means that the real world is represented in a very simple manner as well. This results in a coarse representation of the world but makes the indices manageable. For example, for AMBI and similar indices, types of species are assigned to species classes based on sensitivity.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While all countries/regions currently have monitoring programmes, it is desirable to extend these to fully cover their areas.
Overall Strengths	Simple and easy to understand, making it accessible for communication with stakeholders. Applicable in any location. There are numerous simple assessment indices, and they all can tell a story or address specific aspects of any issue.
Overall Weaknesses	The simplicity of the tool group can also be a weakness due to its highly sectoral approach. It demands extensive and potentially costly monitoring coverage, especially for tasks like benthic sampling. Typically, multiple indices are necessary to accurately describe the status. Furthermore, there is a requirement for establishing reference conditions.

Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models

The indicator-based multi-metric assessment tools integrate quantitative indicators to inform of the integrated state of the assessment area. Tools have been developed for hazardous substances (CHASE), eutrophication (HEAT), and biodiversity (BEAT). The indicators use a threshold value indicating the acceptable state from the unacceptable state, and the indicators can be grouped within the tool to best reflect the assessment topic. For example, in the integrated biodiversity assessment, habitat-related indicators are assessed together, while species population indicators are assessed in another group of indicators. The integration of the indicators is done on two levels: indicators within a group are first integrated by weighted averaging to derive a state of the group, and then (2) each of the groups is compared: the group with the worst state is selected to represent the integrated state of the area, following the precautionary principle (for the full description of the tool group, refer to Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool, #18) [2 responses; 1 Expert, 1 Very familiar].

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (16, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.4) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*4.8) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*3.3) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*2.3) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*2.5) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*1.5) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*1.6) • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABS) (*4.8) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.5) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*2.6)

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.1) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (3.1) • EBM17 – Risks (1.4) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*2.9) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Following further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address 1 additional EBM element:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM13 - Climate change <p>Descriptor or theme-specific combinations of indices and models are able to fully deliver against the above EBM elements. Examples of tools considered: HEAT, BEAT, CHASE, and MESH tools.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within ICES Working Groups • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity) • D5 (Eutrophication) • D8 (Contaminants in the environment)
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for use in any data-rich situations. It is poorly suited for use in data-poor, skills-poor situations, but its suitability can be improved with an improvement in skills.</p>
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the tool and purpose: e.g., pressure data in terms of concentrations of chemicals or abundance of species. For indicators, annual means plus target values are usually needed. Overall, the tools in this category span a wide range of possibilities. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the tool and purpose: e.g., pressure data in terms of categorised pressure levels of chemicals or abundance of species. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the tool and purpose, e.g., presence/absence of ecosystem components. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., >100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) <p>HEAT, BEAT, CHASE-based assessments usually focus on specific assessment periods (5-6 years).</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. There are two approaches: a simple expert-based ranking system and the system used in NEAT/WATERS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical • Programming (e.g., R) • Ecological knowledge

Tool name	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models (generic tool)
Tool group	Descriptor or theme-specific combination of indices and models
	<p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HELCOM, 2010. Ecosystem Health of the Baltic Sea 2003–2007: HELCOM Initial Holistic Assessment. Balt. Sea Environ. Proc. No. 122 • Andersen J.H., Carstensen J., Conley D.J., Dromph K., Fleming-Lehtinen V., Gustafsson B., Josefson A., Norkko A., Villnas A., Murray C., 2017. Long-term temporal and spatial trends in eutrophication status of the Baltic Sea. Biological Reviews 92: 135–149
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>One response reported that the tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable, while another response noted that integration principles, such as 'one-out, all-out' may influence the result, but this assumption does not (or is unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available <p>HEAT, BEAT, CHASE, MESH (and also NEAT, WATERS, MALT) are fundamentally rooted in the initial HEAT version adopted by HELCOM in the period of 2009-2010. The primary challenge has consistently been achieving acceptance.</p>
Overall Strengths	<p>Simple and easy to use, with wide applicability - HEAT (and spin-out tools) are now widely used in Europe.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>A broad generalising approach that disregards having all indicators in the same scale. The tools heavily rely on data, and in many locations/countries, particularly offshore, the inadequacy of monitoring compromises the ability to make robust assessments.</p>

Overarching assessment tools

Overarching assessment tools are used to combine a potentially broad range of individual indicators to produce an overall assessment of the ecosystem status. The indicators to combine may belong to different stages of the management cycle (e.g., the stages in DAPSI(W)R(M)). These tools typically compare the results of the indicators against a set of target or threshold values, and through various combination rules, the overall (integrated) compliance with the final target can be assessed. Combination rules can include weighted averages or more sophisticated rules such as decision trees, spatial threshold application or the one-out-all-out rule (e.g., employed in the European Water Framework Directive for biological quality elements). The rules may vary at different aggregation/integration levels of the overarching assessment. Some assessment tools include a hierarchy of indicators, which gives an implicit weighting of indicator results based on their level of aggregation in the hierarchy. The critical aspect of an overarching assessment tool is to combine highly diverse indicators in a meaningful and transparent manner.

Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Overarching assessment tools (generic tool, #19) [4 responses; 2 Expert, 2 Very Familiar].
- NEAT (specific/particular tool, #19.1) [3 responses; 2 Expert, 1 Familiar].

Tool name		Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group		Overarching assessment tools
Uses of the tool		
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20) <i>(* indicates the EBM elements identified for this tool in D2.1, with the mean score (on a scale 0-5) indicating the ability of the tool to deliver the EBM element as per Table 27 of D2.1; Papadopoulou et al. 2023)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA (*2.7) • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments (*4.5) • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments (*4.5) • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services (*1.5) • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts (*1.5) • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) (*1.4) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint (*2.7) • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) (*2.8) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts (*2.5) 	

Tool name	Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) (*3.3) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change (*2.9) • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species (*3.1) • EBM13 - Climate change (*1.9) • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation (*2.5) • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures (*3.7) • EBM16 - Uncertainty (*4) • EBM17 – Risks (*0.7) • EBM18 - Other policy requirements: (*3) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EBM18.1 - MSPD ○ EBM18.2 - Birds and Habitats Directives ○ EBM 18.3 - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Most respondents (75%) considered that the tool is able to fully deliver the above EBM elements. The remaining respondents considered that the tool needs to fulfil pressure assessment. They noted that the tool needs to incorporate pressure assessment. They also highlighted that the tool does not cover all the PACE management phases and requires upgrades to accommodate PACE requirements, such as Plan and Act.</p>
<p>How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management</p>	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • For official EU MSFD reporting • Within other National Competent Authorities <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
<p>GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed</p>	<p>The tool is able to assess all GES descriptors and criteria, but it is typically used for D1 (Biodiversity), D5 (Eutrophication) and D6 (Sea-floor integrity).</p>
<p>Requirements for the tool application and its outputs</p>	
<p>Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation</p>	<p>The tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations.</p>

Tool name	Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
<p>DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool</p>	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Societal Goods & Benefits (Impacts on Welfare) - as single variables
<p>Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components</p>	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptor indicators (e.g., nutrients) - both synoptic monitoring data and target values (for NEAT). <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk-based approaches. Semi-quantitative data can, in principle, be used but are typically transferred to a quantitative scale. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observation notes, semi-structured interviews, concept maps, case studies. Qualitative data are typically transferred to a quantitative scale using some assumptions. <p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>No spatial components are required. Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>No temporal components required. Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years)

Tool name	Overarching assessment tools (generic tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>The requirements depend on the tool: it may require spatial input (OHI) or not (NEAT). In the latter case, NEAT will still apply to a specific spatial area. Also, NEAT can be based on modelling and be used for forecasting.</p>
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS. Standard errors of indicators should be provided, or they can be computed with access to monitoring data. However, not all tools allow this functionality (NEAT/WATERS/BEAT2.0 all include confidence assessment).</p> <p>The tool produces a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. Not all tools have this functionality, but NEAT, for example, has it built-in. All measures produced are based on Monte Carlo calculations.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • GIS • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://oceanhealthindex.org/
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	<p>Most of the responses (75%) reported that the tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable. However, it was noted that integration principles used by some tools, such as 'one-out-all-out', may influence the result, but this assumption does not (or is unlikely to) affect or restrict its wider applicability.</p>
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available
Overall Strengths	<p>Wide applicability, overarching approach with confidence assessment. NEAT/WATERS/BEAT2.0 are state of the art and used by researchers, competent authorities, as well as HELCOM and EEA.</p>
Overall Weaknesses	<p>The tool typically requires a significant amount of input data. It does not account for ecological interactions. Data cannot be entered in bulk, and it does not keep a history of entries in the database. A wider acceptance is desired.</p>

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
Uses of the tool	
How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM	<p>EBM elements addressed by the tool in its current state: (20, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM1 - Cumulative effects assessments – CEA • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM3 - Whole ecosystem assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM5 - Special biotic effects/impacts • EBM6 - Specific Ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions) • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM10 - Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, NIS, HABs) • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM13 - Climate change • EBM14 - Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures • EBM16 - Uncertainty • EBM17 – Risks • EBM18.1 - Other policy requirements - MSPD • EBM18.2 - Other policy requirements - Birds and Habitats Directives • EBM 18.3 - Other policy requirements - Biodiversity Strategy <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool in its current state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Most respondents (66%) considered that other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. The tool requires improved spatial integration, and the links between activity-pressure, pressure-impacts, and impacts-ecosystem services are not explicitly established (conclusions can be drawn, but this is not explicit). The assessment of ecosystem services could be achieved if the tool is adapted.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is being currently used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For official EU MSFD reporting • For EU project work • Within EU Technical Expert Groups • Within Regional Sea Convention (assessment) groups • For EEA assessments • Within other National Competent Authorities • Specific projects (impact assessment) <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it is used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of monitoring programmes

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1 (Biodiversity) • D2 (Non-indigenous species) • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish) • D5 (Eutrophication) • D6 (Sea-floor integrity) • D8 (Contaminants in the environment) • D9 (Contaminants in seafood) <p>It requires adapting for assessing criteria.</p>
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	Overall, the tool is well-suited for data-rich, skills-rich situations. It becomes moderately suited in data-poor or skills-poor situations, but it is poorly suited for data-poor and skills-poor situations. One response considered the tool well-suited for all situations.
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities - as multiple variables • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as multiple variables • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Habitat(s) (representing State change) - as multiple variables • Responses or management measures - as multiple variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measured values: biota mortality, biota biomass, pollutant concentrations, nutrient concentrations. Indicator values and standard errors (e.g., temporal data, spatial area). Preferably long-time data series. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species, seagrass distribution. Assigns approximate measurements to data: biotic index. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitats, threatened species. Surveys, observation notes.

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
<p>Spatial and temporal scales</p>	<p>The tool cannot use expert judgement instead of data.</p> <p>Spatial inputs required (e.g., maps, GIS data). Spatial outputs produced (e.g., maps). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site level (e.g., < 10 sq.km) • Local (e.g., 10-100 sq.km) • National (e.g., 100-10,000 sq.km) • Regional (e.g., 10,000-100,000 sq.km) • European (e.g., > 100,000 sq.km) <p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term (e.g., seasonal) • Short/medium-term (e.g., 1 year) • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years) <p>NEAT does not require maps, but requires information on the area to which each indicator is applied (this was considered here as spatial data). It also requires temporal data to produce indicators with associated standard error; otherwise, the assessment cannot be carried out. Spatial outputs refer to assessments done for Spatial Assessment Units (SAUs), while temporal outputs refer to the assessments done for a specific time. Furthermore, if done in different years, it provides a temporal series of assessments.</p>
<p>Confidence/Uncertainty</p>	<p>The tool uses confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS. NEAT automatically calculates confidence (uncertainty) using Monte Carlo simulations.</p>
<p>Other resources required</p>	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical • Analytical • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
<p>Tool references/links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.azti.es/productos/neat/ • Berg T., Murray C., Carstensen J., Andersen J.H., 2018. NEAT – Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool. Manual version 1.4. 38pp. • Frascchetti S., Fabbrizzi E., Tamburello L., Uyerra M. C., Micheli F., Sala E., Pipitone C., Badalamenti F., Bevilacqua S., Boada J., Cebrian E., Ceccherelli G., Chiantore M., D'Anna G., Di Franco A., Farina Si., Giakoumi S., Gissi E., Guala I., Guidetti P., Katsanevakis S., Manea E., Montefalcone M., Sini M., Asnaghi Va., Calo A., Di Lorenzo M.,

Tool name	NEAT (specific/particular tool)
Tool group	Overarching assessment tools
	Garrabou J., Musco L., Oprandi A., Rilov G., Borja A., 2022. An integrated assessment of the Good Environmental Status of Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas, <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 305, 114370.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable. Users have the flexibility to make assumptions when applying the tool, such as assigning equal weight to all ecosystem components or using different weights.
Barriers to tool application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No monitoring data available • It requires specific, extensive sampling programme(s) to provide the input data • It does not have any associated thresholds or targets • It requires good ecological understanding to interpret adequately both inputs and outputs <p>Suggestions to overcome the barriers identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In situations with limited data, effective interpretation is crucial. • In situations with limited skills, the tool is not complex to learn, and training would be sufficient.
Overall Strengths	NEAT provides an integrative evaluation of ecological status, aligning seamlessly with MSFD assessment requirements. It is easy to learn, free, and uses hierarchical integration. The tool incorporates uncertainty and is suitable for data-poor areas, though careful interpretation of results is necessary. NEAT has the potential for adaptation to other assessments. It is a holistic integration assessment that considers spatial and temporal scales, employs an ecosystem-based approach, and identifies environmental issues requiring management attention and corresponding measures.
Overall Weaknesses	NEAT cannot integrate indicators based on expert knowledge or present-absence data. It cannot import data from Excel. It lacks the capability to produce "map" outputs. It would need adaptation to meet the new MSFD (criteria assessment, functional groups assessments, etc.). Targets/thresholds are necessary, and cumulative impact assessment is still pending. Sometimes, errors occur that are difficult to identify.

Size spectrum models

Size-spectrum models are physiologically-structured models that provide a way of investigating the structure and dynamics of complex ecological communities through the distribution of abundance or biomass against the body size of individuals on a log–log scale. The use the of the body size is a central feature of these models because this trait correlates strongly with several biological processes, including metabolism, predator-prey relations, encounter rates, functional responses, reproductive effort, and other vital rates. Overall, there are there are three model types that differ in their degree of complexity: the food-web, the trait-based and the community models. The size spectrum approach offers several advantages, including the use of a limited number of parameters, minimal computational requirements, and a robust mechanistically basis, providing a framework of low to intermediate complexity. This framework is particularly well-suited for assessing the impact of pressures such as fishing and environmental changes on marine ecosystems (Andersen et al., 2015). Tools assessed within this group resulting from the responses to the questionnaire (the number of responses obtained for each tool and the level of confidence are indicated in square brackets):

- Size spectrum models (generic tool, #20) [1 response, Expert].

Tool name	Size spectrum models (generic)
Tool group	Size spectrum models
Uses of the tool	
<p>How the tool delivers element(s) of EBM</p>	<p>The tool is not considered to address any EBM elements (and consequently any PACE management phases) in its current state because the tool is not currently being used.</p> <p>After further development or adaptation, the tool is able to address the following EBM elements: (8, in a total of 20)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBM2 - GES MSFD assessments • EBM4 - Ecosystem Services • EBM7 - Pressures-Activities footprint • EBM8 - Effects footprints (and/or Impacts footprints) • EBM9 - Links activities pressures impacts • EBM11 - Single species, ecosystem Components State change • EBM12 - Threatened habitats and species • EBM15 - Spatial and other measures <p>PACE management phases addressed by the tool following further development or adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan

Tool name	Size spectrum models (generic)
Tool group	Size spectrum models
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act • Check • Evaluate <p>Other tools are required to fully deliver the above EBM elements. Adequate size spectrum models, such as the Non-Linear Species Size Spectrum Model, have been demonstrated to predict real size spectra over a wide parameter range to a management-relevant accuracy. They also predict the relevant time scales of dynamics.</p>
How the tool is commonly used and its relevance to marine governance/management	<p>The tool is not currently being used.</p> <p>The tool is relevant to marine governance, and it can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development or setting of targets, e.g., CBD, SDG • Tracking progress against action plans, etc. • Design of remediation/management measures • Informing decision-making • Development of MSFD thresholds
GES Descriptors and Criteria assessed	<p>The tool is able to assess GES descriptors and criteria, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D3 (Commercially exploited fish and shellfish) • D1C3; D1C6 • D4C3
Requirements for the tool application and its outputs	
Data/skill rich – Data/skill poor situation	<p>The tool is well-suited for use in skills-rich situations and moderately suited in skills-poor situations.</p>
DAPSIWRM components covered by the tool	<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures - as single variables <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species or species groups (representing State change) - as single variables • Effects on Ecosystem Services, or their components (representing State change) - as single variables
Data requirements on DAPSIWRM components	<p>Quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressures on populations in the form of changes in mortality or respiration rate. <p>Semi-quantitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Qualitative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. <p>Size-spectrum models convert pressures on ecosystems into size-spectrum responses.</p> <p>The tool can use expert judgement instead of data.</p>
Spatial and temporal scales	<p>No spatial components are required/produced.</p>

Tool name	Size spectrum models (generic)
Tool group	Size spectrum models
	<p>Temporal inputs required (e.g., annual occurrences, time series data). Temporal outputs produced (e.g., trend forecasting). Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium/long-term (e.g., 2-10 years) • Long-term (e.g., > 10 years)
Confidence/Uncertainty	<p>The tool does not use confidence/uncertainty as part of its INPUTS.</p> <p>The tool does not produce a measure of confidence/uncertainty as part of its OUTPUTS.</p>
Other resources required	<p>Expertise required to apply the tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modelling • Ecological knowledge <p>The necessary software to apply the tool is freely available with no licence costs.</p> <p>No other additional resources (e.g., specific hardware) are needed.</p>
Tool references/links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rossberg, A.G., Gaedke, U. and Kratina, P., 2019. Dome patterns in pelagic size spectra reveal strong trophic cascades. <i>Nature communications</i>, 10(1), p.4396.
Strengths and Weaknesses	
Limitations to tool applicability	The tool makes no specific assumptions and should be widely applicable.
Barriers to tool application	No additional potential barriers to application.
Overall Strengths	Size-spectrum models have always been studied because of their potential use in ecosystem management and because of their intrinsically low data requirements, robustness and transparency. The problem, until recently, was just that the proposed models were too simple to reproduce observed phenomenology. The non-linear SSM has overcome these problems.
Overall Weaknesses	Size-spectrum models inevitably make simplifying assumptions that limit the accuracy of their predictions. They will, therefore, not be able to reproduce a detailed ecosystem state. However, at the level of detail required for GES descriptors, this is not an issue.

8.1.3 References for factsheets

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2023